

SHERPA
Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces

**THEMES OF INTEREST TO
HORIZON EU PROGRAMMING
ON RURAL/SOCIAL**

REPORT ON DEMAND

SEPTEMBER 2021

THEMES OF INTEREST TO HORIZON EU PROGRAMMING ON RURAL/SOCIAL

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1. Introduction

Building on the successful experience gained in the FP7 project “AgriPolicy”, the concept of “Report on Demand” has been retained in SHERPA. The concept offers the possibility for DG AGRI to ask the SHERPA team to prepare a report on a specific subject at any time of the project. Both the topic and the time of delivery of the report are flexible, in order to allow targeted and timely contribution to the work of DG AGRI.

During the kick-off meeting of SHERPA organised on 21-22 October 2019, officers from DG AGRI expressed an interest to receive a contribution before the end of December 2019, to support them in the preparation of the work programmes of the first call for proposals of Horizon Europe. To help identifying topics for research projects, the demand was to receive an overview of the research projects relevant to “rural policy” previously financed by the EU in the Framework Programme (FP6, FP7, H2020) and in other initiatives such as ESPON or INTERREG.

This document presents the outcomes of this analysis carried out between 20 November 2019 and 18 December 2019.

2. Methodology

Based on the list of themes on rural/social and associated with them keywords provided by DG AGRI (see Annex 1), a three-member team from the Agricultural University of Athens proceeded to thorough search for research projects addressing the themes under investigation. The Cordis database (<https://cordis.europa.eu/en>) provided the necessary pool of research projects and was searched by making use of the available keyword list.

Projects that were returned as search results were examined with regard to their relevance to the theme that was, each time, under investigation. Assessment of relevance was based on the degree of matching between project aim and objectives and the theme under investigation. In the case that few project details were made available by Cordis, there was an effort to find the project website and retrieve relevant information from there.

Analysis of results has been based upon the extraction of quantitative indicators and statistics. In addition to that, more details are made available by providing: (i) tables with research project details per investigated theme (see Annex 2), and (ii) a summary of each project (see Annex 3). Analysis on the basis of quantitative indicators and statistics aimed to offer an overview of the whole landscape of rural-/social-related research projects, as well as illustrate the situation with regard to each concrete theme under investigation.

3. Results

A point that needs to be stressed before proceeding to the presentation of analysis results is that, in many cases, there is not a unique theme assignment per project. Thus, a research project may be associated with more than one themes.

Quantitative indicators on which analysis has been based are the following:

- total number of projects for all themes and total number of projects per theme;
- number of {FP6, FP7, H2020, ESPON, INTERREG} projects per theme;
- total project budget;
- total project budget per programme for all themes;

- total project budget per theme for all programmes;
- total number of countries from which coordinating organisations come from;
- number of coordinating organisations per country for all themes and number of coordinating organisations for each theme per country;
- maximum, minimum and average project budget per theme;
- number of completed and ongoing research projects per theme for all programmes, as well as for each concrete theme.

Very few ESPON and INTERREG projects have been found: there are only two research projects that have been identified and retrieved, which relate to the “rural and biodiversity” theme. Few details for these projects are available.

3.1. General overview

In total, 151 projects relevant to “rural policy” have been identified, for a budget of € 970 million. The number of projects identified in each of the 15 themes is provided below.

- Total number of identified research projects: 151
- Number of research projects per theme:
 - Characterising rural/rural diversity: **19**
 - Well-being, quality of life and attractiveness of rural territories as places to live and work: **16**
 - Social capital, social processes, social networks and social innovation: **20**
 - Generation renewal: renewing farming and rural generations: **2**
 - Rural women/Gender in rural development: **0**
 - Vulnerable groups in rural communities: **3**
 - Rural labour/jobs: **10**
 - Rural and climate: **9**
 - Rural and biodiversity: **26**
 - Rural and circular and efficient resource use: **12**
 - Rural values and income: **30**
 - Rural and digital: **29**
 - Smart villages/communities: **8**
 - Territorial approaches and policies: **20**
 - Innovation policies and innovation ecosystems for rural communities: **37**
 - Policy performance evaluation: **28**

The above information is also illustrated in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 Number of research projects per theme (all programmes)

Figures 2 to 4 that follow present the number of FP6, FP7 and H2020 projects per theme¹.

Figure 2: Number of FP6 research projects per theme

Figure 3: Number of FP7 research projects per theme

¹ ESPON and INTERREG projects have not been included due to their limited number (only one ESPON and one INTERREG project associated with the “rural and biodiversity theme”).

Figure 4: Number of H2020 research projects per theme

- Total project budget (all programmes and all themes): € 970,551,049.78
- Total project budget per programme for all themes:
 FP6 projects budget: **€ 235,119,459.00** FP7 projects budget: **€ 182,066,665.43**
 H2020 projects budget: **€ 553,364,925.35**

The above information is also illustrated in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: Total project budget per programme for all themes

- Total project budget per theme for all programmes:
- Characterising rural/rural diversity: **€ 34,115,649.95**
- Well-being, quality of life and attractiveness of rural territories as places to live & work: **€ 57,139,937.79**
- Social capital, social processes, social networks and social innovation: **€ 61,418,046.37**

- Generation renewal: renewing farming and rural generations: **€ 8,064,176.80**
- Rural women/Gender in rural development: **€ 0**
- Vulnerable groups in rural communities: **€ 5,098,188.60**
- Rural labour/jobs: **€ 24,560,385.63**
- Rural and climate: **€ 18,953,030.04**
- Rural and biodiversity: **€ 88,939,604.98**
- Rural and circular and efficient resource use: **€ 40,493,818.25**
- Rural values and income: **€ 103,197,864.75**
- Rural and digital: **€ 211,245,835.16**
- Smart villages/communities: **€ 44,250,566.00**
- Territorial approaches and policies: **€ 48,167,407.50**
- Innovation policies and innovation ecosystems for rural communities: **€ 135,860,286.51**
- Policy performance evaluation: **€ 89,046,251.45**

The above information is also illustrated in Figure 6 below.

Figure 6: Total project budget per theme for all programmes

More detail is offered by Figures 7 to 9, which show allocation of project budget per theme².

² ESPON and INTERREG projects have not been included due to lack of budget-related information for these projects.

Figure 7: Budget of FP6 research programmes per theme

Figure 8: Budget of FP7 research programmes per theme

Figure 9: Budget of H2020 research programmes per theme

- Total number of countries from which coordinating organisations come from: **18**
- Number of coordinating organisations per country for all themes:

Austria	Belgium	Bulgaria	Czechia	Denmark	France	Germany	Greece	Hungary
11	8	1	3	4	22	44	17	5
Ireland	Italy	Netherlands	Norway	Portugal	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	United Kingdom
6	23	34	7	5	30	6	5	36

The above information is also illustrated in Figure 10 below.

Figure 10: Number of coordinating organisations per country for all themes

3.2. Results per theme

3.2.1. Characterising rural/rural diversity

This theme covers economic and social analysis tools (including statistics & indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability. In total, 19 projects have been identified, including 4 FP6 projects, 14 FP7 projects and 1 H2020 project, for a total budget of € 34 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **19**

FP6 projects: **4**

FP7 projects: **14**

H2020 projects: **1**

Total budget spent: **€ 34,115,649.95**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 3,618,266.00**

FP7 projects budget: **€ 27,967,488.63**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 2,529,895.32**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 3,777,931.00	€ 175,974.60	€ 1,795,560.52	15	1

Figure 11: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 12: Theme-related project budget per programme

Figure 13: Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

3.2.2. Well-being, quality of life and attractiveness of rural territories as places to live and work

This theme covers well-being, quality of life, rural attractiveness and job attractiveness in rural areas. In total, 16 projects have been identified, including 4 FP6 projects, 3 FP7 projects and 9 H2020 projects, for a total budget of € 57 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **16**

FP6 projects: **4**

FP7 projects: **3**

H2020 projects: **9**

Total budget spent: **€ 57,139,937.79**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 18,959,451.00**

FP7 projects budget: **€ 2,977,828.00**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 35,202,658.79**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 8,826,736.00	€ 212,532.00	€ 3,571,246.11	10	6

Figure 14: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 15: Theme-related project budget per programme

Figure 16: Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

Theme-related information is also illustrated with the help of Figures 14 to 16 above.

3.2.3. Social capital, social processes, social networks and social innovation

This theme covers social capital, social processes, social networks and social innovation in rural areas, including the role of community-led structures and initiatives. In total, 20 projects have been identified, including 8 FP6 projects, 5 FP7 projects and 7 H2020 projects, for a total budget of € 61 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **20**

FP6 projects: **8**

FP7 projects: **5**

H2020 projects: **7**

Total budget spent: **€ 61,418,046.37**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 21,721,702.00**

FP7 projects budget: **€ 6,743,083.80**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 32,953,260.57**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 10,276,187.50	€ 175,974.60	€ 3,232,528.76	13	6

The above, as well as additional, information is illustrated with the help of Figures 17 to 19 that follow.

Figure 17: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 18: Theme-related project budget per programme

Figure 19: Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

3.2.4. Generation renewal: renewing farming and rural generations

This theme focuses on rural demography and generation renewal in both the farming sector and rural areas. Two projects have been identified (1 in FP7 and 1 in Horizon 2020) for a total budget of € 8 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **2**

FP6 projects: **0** FP7 projects: **1** H2020 projects: **1**

Total budget spent: **€ 8,064,176.80**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 0.00** FP7 projects budget: **€ 2,068,272.80**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 5,995,904.00**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 5,995,904.00	€ 2,068,272.80	€ 4,032,088.40	1	1

The above, as well as additional, information is illustrated with the help of Figures 20 and 21 that follow.

Figure 20: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 21: Theme-related project budget per programme

3.2.5. Rural women/ Gender in rural development

This theme focuses on gender issues in rural areas, covering the role of woman in farming and in rural areas. No project has been identified for this topic.

Theme-related projects: **0**

FP6 projects: **0** FP7 projects: **0** H2020 projects: **0**

Total budget spent: **€ 0.00**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 0.00**

FP7 projects budget: **€ 0.00**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 0.00**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 0.00	€ 0.00	€ 0.00	0	0

3.2.6. Vulnerable groups in rural communities

This theme covers research project focusing on vulnerable group in rural areas (migrants, people at risk of poverty and social exclusion, people with disabilities). Three FP7 projects have been identified for a budget of € 5 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **3**

FP6 projects: **0**

FP7 projects: **3**

H2020 projects: **0**

Total budget spent: **€ 5,098,188.60**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 0.00**

FP7 projects budget: **€ 5,098,188.60**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 0.00**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 2,644,116.60	€ 537,850.00	€ 1,699,396.20	3	0

The above, as well as additional, information is illustrated with the help of Figures 22 and 23 that follow.

Figure 22: Theme-related projects per programme **Figure 23:** Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

3.2.7. Rural labour/jobs

This theme covers rural labour and rural jobs, including working conditions, labour laws, health and safety at the work place and farmers suicide. In total, 10 projects have been identified, including 6 FP6 projects, 1 FP7 projects and 3 H2020 project, for a total budget of € 24 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **10**

FP6 projects: **6** FP7 projects: **1** H2020 projects: **3**

Total budget spent: **€ 24,560,385.63**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 5,098,188.60** FP7 projects budget: **€ 1,400,173.00**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 9,088,921.63**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 8,826,736.00	€ 350,200.00	€ 2,728,931.74	9	1

The above, as well as additional, information is illustrated with the help of Figures 24 to 26 that follow.

Figure 24: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 25: Theme-related project budget per programme

Figure 26: Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

3.2.8. Rural and climate

This theme covers the theme of climate adaptation, climate mitigation and energy in rural areas. In total, 9 projects have been identified, including 4 FP6 projects, 2 FP7 projects and 3 H2020 project, for a total budget of € 18 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **9**

FP6 projects: **4**

FP7 projects: **2**

H2020 projects: **3**

Total budget spent: **€ 18,953,030.04**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 4,866,547.00**

FP7 projects budget: **€ 4,015,307.79**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 10,071,175.25**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 4,999,998.75	€ 71,249.00	€ 2,369,128.76	7	2

The above, as well as additional, information is illustrated with the help of Figures 27 to 29 that follow.

Figure 27: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 28: Theme-related project budget per programme

Figure 29: Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

3.2.9. Rural and biodiversity

This theme covers research projects focusing on rural areas and biodiversity (including nature-based solutions, green infrastructures, public goods or ecosystem services etc.). In total, 26 projects have been identified, including 9 FP6 projects, 8 FP7 projects, 1 H2020 project, as well as 1 ESPON and 1 INTERREG project, for a total budget of € 57 Mln.

Theme-related projects: 88

FP6 projects: **9**

FP7 projects: **8**

H2020 projects: **1**

ESPON projects: **1**

INTERREG projects: **1**

Total budget spent: **€ 88,939,604.98**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 12,571,836.00** FP7 projects budget: **€ 30,811,082.60**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 45,556,686.38**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 10,457,923.75	€ 212,532.00	€ 3,866,939.35	20	6

It needs to be mentioned that no budget-related details were available for the ESPON and INTERREG projects. This is the reason why this kind of information is not presented, for these two projects, above. The above, as well as additional, information is illustrated with the help of Figures 30 to 32 that follow.

Figure 30: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 31: Theme-related project budget per programme

Figure 32: Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

3.2.10. Rural and circular and efficient resource use

This theme covers circular economy, including bio-based products in rural areas. In total, 12 projects have been identified, including 2 FP6 projects and 10 H2020 projects, for a total budget of € 40 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **12**

FP6 projects: **2** FP7 projects: **0** H2020 projects: **10**

Total budget spent: **€ 40,493,818.25**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 843,193.00** FP7 projects budget: **€ 0.00**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 39,650,625.25**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 8,377,867.50	€ 71,249.00	€ 3,374,484.85	5	7

Figure 33: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 34: Theme-related project budget per programme

Figure 35: Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

Theme-related information is also illustrated with the help of Figures 33 to 35 above.

3.2.11. Rural values and income

This theme covers business models and value chains in rural areas. In total, 30 projects have been identified, including 7 FP6 projects, 5 FP7 projects and 18 H2020 projects, for a total budget of € 103 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **30**

FP6 projects: **7**

FP7 projects: **5**

H2020 projects: **18**

Total budget spent: **€ 103,197,864.75**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 8,479,643.00**

FP7 projects budget: **€ 12,796,908.55**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 81,921,313.20**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 20,628,860.02	€ 225,000.00	€ 3,558,547.06	17	12

The above, as well as additional, information is illustrated with the help of Figures 36 to 38 that follow.

Figure 36: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 37: Theme-related project budget per programme

Figure 38: Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

3.2.12. Rural and digital

This theme covers the issue of digitalisation in rural areas (covering digital strategies, digital infrastructure, digital skills, e-services, e-health etc.). In total, 29 projects have been identified, including 7 FP6 projects, 3 FP7 projects and 19 H2020 projects, for a total budget of € 211 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **29**

FP6 projects: **7**

FP7 projects: **3**

H2020 projects: **19**

Total budget spent: **€ 211,245,835.16**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 47,664,864.00**

FP7 projects budget: **€ 9,498,855.11**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 154,082,116.05**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 34,234,990.42	€ 937,336.00	€ 7,284,339.14	14	15

The above, as well as additional, information is illustrated with the help of Figures 39 to 41 that follow.

Figure 39: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 40: Theme-related project budget per programme

Figure 41: Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

3.2.13. Smart villages/communities

This theme covers smart villages and smart communities in rural areas. In total, 8 projects have been identified, including 2 FP6 projects, 2 FP7 projects and 4 H2020 project, for a total budget of € 44 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **8**

FP6 projects: **2**

FP7 projects: **2**

H2020 projects: **4**

Total budget spent: **€ 44,250,566.00**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 15,614,903.00**

FP7 projects budget: **€ 6,309,813.00**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 22,325,850.00**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 13,814,903.00	€ 1,365,123.00	€ 5,531,320.75	5	3

The above, as well as additional, information is illustrated with the help of Figures 42 to 44 that follow.

Figure 42: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 43: Theme-related project budget per programme

Figure 44: Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

Territorial approaches and policies This theme covers well-being, quality of life, rural attractiveness and job attractiveness in rural areas. In total, 16 projects have been identified, including 4 FP6 projects, 3 FP7 projects and 9 H2020 project, for a total budget of € 57 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **20**

FP6 projects: **3**

FP7 projects: **8**

H2020 projects: **9**

Total budget spent: **€ 48,167,407.50**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 2,052,133.00**

FP7 projects budget: **€ 13,293,008.25**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 32,822,266.25**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 5,999,987.50	€ 178,307.05	€ 2,675,967.08	12	7

The above, as well as additional, information is illustrated with the help of Figures 45 to 47 that follow.

Figure 45: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 46: Theme-related project budget per programme

Figure 47: Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

3.2.14. Innovation policies and innovation ecosystems for rural communities

This theme covers knowledge and innovation systems and policies, in the context of rural communities. In total, 37 projects have been identified, including 16 FP6 projects, 6 FP7 projects and 15 H2020 projects, for a total budget of € 135 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **37**

FP6 projects: **16**

FP7 projects: **6**

H2020 projects: **15**

Total budget spent: **€ 135,860,286.51**

FP6 projects budget: **€ 60,464,405.00**

FP7 projects budget: **€ 23,046,425.38**

H2020 projects budget: **€ 52,349,456.13**

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 15,553,272.00	€ 173,076.00	€ 3,773,896.85	29	8

The above, as well as additional, information is illustrated with the help of Figures 47 to 50 that follow.

Figure 48: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 49: Theme-related project budget per programme

Figure 50: Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

3.2.15. Policy performance evaluation

This theme covers the evaluation of social and environmental performance of initiatives/policies. In total, 28 projects have been identified, including 8 FP6 projects, 14 FP7 projects and 6 H2020 project, for a total budget of € 89 Mln.

Theme-related projects: **28**

FP6 projects: **8**

FP7 projects: **14**

H2020 projects: **6**

Total budget spent: **€ 89,046,251.45**

FP6 projects budget: € 24,191,225.00 FP7 projects budget: € 36,040,229.92

H2020 projects budget: € 28,814,796.53

Maximum project budget	Minimum project budget	Average project budget	Completed projects	Ongoing projects
€ 15,553,272.00	€ 232,684.02	€ 3,180,223.27	22	5

The above, as well as additional, information is illustrated with the help of Figures 51 to 53.

Figure 51: Theme-related projects per programme

Figure 52: Theme-related project budget per programme

Figure 53: Relative frequencies of European countries participation in project coordination

4. Conclusion

This report was sent to the European Commission (DG AGRI) on 23 December 2019 as a contribution to the preparation of the first call for proposals for Horizon Europe. The review of research projects in the area of “rural policy” allowed to identify the extent to which thematic areas were covered in research projects supported by the EU. In total, 151 relevant projects were identified, for a total budget of € 970 million. These numbers should be interpreted with caution as one project can cover several thematic areas.

A main finding of the report is that from the 15 thematic areas of interest of DG AGRI, all of them were already addressed by research projects, except for the topic of rural woman/ Gender in rural areas. The review also showed that the number of projects related to social dimension (e.g. generation renewal, vulnerable groups in rural communities) is lower compared to the number of projects related to economic and environmental dimensions of rural areas.

In addition to support DG AGRI in the identification of topics for Horizon Europe work programmes, these findings will also guide the choice of thematic areas that will be discussed in the SHERPA Multi-Actor Platforms.

Annex 1: Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

Theme #1

Characterising rural/rural diversity

economic and social analysis tools (including statistics & indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability

Associated key words/notions

"Rural" as an object/category; defining rural; rural delineation; "functional geographies" AND "rural"; rural areas; rural population; rural demography; inner peripheries; internal areas; remote areas; "Rural" AND "Sustainability"; socio-cultural indicators; urban-rural/rural-urban divide/gap; digital gap; indicators at high-level of disaggregation/geographical levels (EU to local); evaluation frameworks building on these tools; data collection and data sourcing; data crowd sourcing; innovative data collection techniques.

Theme #2

Well-being, quality of life and attractiveness of rural territories as places to live and work

Associated key words/notions

Measuring well-being/quality of life; rural attractiveness; job attractiveness in rural areas

Theme #3

Social capital, social processes, social networks and social innovation

Associated key words/notions

"Rural" AND: social capital/innovation; social capital/innovation and local/rural development; social networks; community-led structures/bodies/organisations; social enterprises; role of social enterprises/community-led initiatives versus public sector/infrastructures; social perception of farmers.

Theme #4

Generation renewal: renewing farming and rural generations

Associated key words/notions

Young farmers, new entrants, new farmers, farmers of the future, newcomers, neorural, start-ups, start-up aid, setting-up of young farmers; rural demography.

Theme #5

Rural women/ Gender in rural development

Associated key words/notions:

"Rural" OR "Farming" AND "Women"; gender issues/studies/balance; women in farming; women entrepreneurs/entrepreneurship.

Theme #6

Vulnerable groups in rural communities

Associated key words/notions:

"Rural" or "Farming/agriculture" AND: migrants; migration; poor; poverty; social inclusion; people at risk of poverty and social exclusion; integration of migrants/ handicapped/ people with disabilities; social farming; care farming.

Theme #7

Rural labour/jobs

Associated key words/notions

"Rural" or "Farming/agriculture" AND: Working conditions (farming and rural); labour laws; rural jobs; health and safety at work; farmers suicide.

Theme #8

Rural and climate

Associated key words/notions

"Rural" AND: Climate adaptation; climate mitigation; energy; renewable energy; distributed energy production and consumption; CO2 market; mobility; clean mobility; carbon neutral; resilience; carbon-neutral; climate-neutral; passive; carbon taxes etc.

Theme #9

Rural and biodiversity

Associated key words/notions

"Rural" AND: biodiversity; nature; nature-based solutions; green infrastructure(s); public goods and ecosystem services; biosphere reserves; nature protection; environment.

Theme #10

Rural and circular and efficient resource use

Associated key words/notions

"Rural" AND: circular; circular economy/resource-use/resource management; resource flows; nutrients; waste; bio-based products.

Theme #11

Rural values and income

Associated key words/notions

"Rural" AND: business models; value creation/retention; value chains; cross-sectoral value chains; technological mega-trends (e.g. decentralised manufacturing; future of work, future of employment, digital etc.); social/environmental/territorial claims; regional/territorial/local value chains; culture; creative industries.

Theme #12

Rural and digital

Associated key words/notions

"Rural" AND: digital; digital strategies; digital infrastructure; digital skills; digital services; e-services; e-health; digital and mobility; driverless cars/trucks

Theme #13

Smart villages/communities

Associated key words/notions

Smart villages; smart communities; smart cities and rural; rural services.

Theme #14

Innovation policies and innovation ecosystems for rural communities

Associated key words/notions

"Rural" AND: innovation; innovation policies; smart specialisation; smart diversification; knowledge and innovation systems; innovation ecosystems; triple/quadruple helix; AKIS; education; skills; innovation brokers; living labs.

Theme #15

Policy performance evaluation

Associated key words/notions:

"Rural" AND: joint evaluation of social and environmental performance of initiatives/policies; result-based/performance-based policies; multi-dimensional policies; supporting transition: governance for sustainability; sustainable development goals; monitoring and evaluation frameworks.

Annex 2: Research projects per theme

Characterising rural/rural diversity

no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
1	CORASON	A Cognitive approach to rural sustainable development the dynamics of expert and lay knowledges	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/79248/reporting/en	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,131,033.00	2004	2007	TRINITY COLLEGE DUBLIN	Ireland
2	RAPIDO	Rural areas, people and innovative development	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/84088/reporting/en	FP6	SSA - Specific Support Action	350,200.00	2007	2009	ECOLOGIC - INSTITUTE FOR INTERNATIONAL AND EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY	Germany
3	RURACTION	Social Entrepreneurship in Structurally Weak Rural Regions: Analysing Innovative Troubleshooters in Action	https://ruraction.eu/	H2020	MSCA-ITN-ETN - European Training Networks	2,529,895.32	2016	2020	LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR RAUMBEZOGENE SOZIALFORSCHUNG (IRS) EV	Germany
4	SMARTOPEN DATA	Linked Open Data for environment protection in Smart Regions	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/603824	FP7	FP7-ENVIRONMENT	3,189,042.11	2013	2015	EMPRESA TRANSFORMACION AGRARIA SA DE	Spain
5	ENVIEVAL	Development and application of new methodological frameworks for the evaluation of environmental impacts of rural development programmes in the EU	https://www.envieval.eu/	FP7	FP7-KBBE	2,335,877.00	2013	2015	JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI	Germany
6	FARMPATH	Farming Transitions: Pathways Towards Regional Sustainability of Agriculture in Europe	https://farmpath.hutton.ac.uk/partners	FP7	FP7-KBBE	2,068,272.80	2011	2014	THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE	United Kingdom

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7	C-BIRD	Cooperative Business and Innovative Rural Development: Synergies between Commercial and Academic Partners	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/611490	FP7	FP7-PEOPLE	597,663.91	2014	2017	TRAKIYSKI UNIVERSITET	Bulgaria
8	MEMOLA	MEditerranean MOuntainous LAndscapes: an historical approach to cultural heritage based on traditional agrosystems	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/613265?rcn=197932	FP7	FP7-SSH	2,940,722.56	2014	2017	UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA	Spain
9	SOLINSA	Agricultural Knowledge Systems in Transition: Towards a more effective and efficient support of Learning and Innovation Networks for Sustainable Agriculture	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/266306	FP7	FP7-KBBE	3,153,275.00	2011	2014	FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG	Switzerland
10	SUSTAINMED	Sustainable agri-food systems and rural development in the Mediterranean Partner Countries	https://sustainmed.iamm.fr/index.php/project-presentation	FP7	FP7-KBBE	2,644,116.60	2010	2013	CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE HAUTES ETUDES AGRONOMIQUES MEDITERRANEENNES	France
11	RURAGRI	Facing sustainability: new relationships between rural areas and agriculture in Europe	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/235175	FP7	FP7-KBBE	1,208,730.00	2009	2014	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE	France
12	SPARD	Spatial Analysis of Rural Development Measures	http://project2.zalf.de/spard/	FP7	FP7-KBBE	1,900,000.00	2010	2013	Leibniz-Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF)	Germany
13	CAP-IRE	Assessing the multiple Impacts of the Common Agricultural Policies (CAP) on Rural Economies	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/216672	FP7	FP7-SSH	1,881,354.00			ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	Italy
14	DARDRA	Defining and Assessing Rurality/Urbanity and Delineating Rural/Urban Areas in Europe	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/220832	FP7	FP7-PEOPLE	178,307.05	2009	2010	UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHAMPTON	United Kingdom
15	DERREG		https://www.global-rural.org/about/	FP7	FP7-SSH	1,916,222.00	2009	2011	ABERYSTWYTH UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
16	EASTGRAB	Understanding Land Grabbing in Eastern Europe and Central Asia: an	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/326781	FP7	FP7-PEOPLE	175,974.60			ERASMUS UNIVERSITEIT ROTTERDAM	Netherlands

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		Integrated Assessment of Impacts, Conflicts and Trade-offs								
17	COEXIST	Interaction in European coastal waters: A roadmap to sustainable integration of aquaculture and fisheries	https://www.coexistproject.eu/coexist-project/coexist-overview	FP7	FP7-KBBE	3,777,931.00			Institute of Marine Research (IMR)	Norway
18	TERESA	Types of interaction between economy, rural society, environment and agricultural activities in European regions	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44400	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,006,000.00	2007	2009	OESTERREICHISCHES INSTITUT FUER RAUMPLANUNG	Austria
19	CORASON	A Cognitive Approach to Rural Sustainable Development the dynamics of expert and lay knowledges	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/506049	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,131,033.00	2004	2007	THE PROVOST FELLOWS AND SCHOLARS OF THE COLLEGE OF THE HOLY AND UNDIVIDED TRINITY OF QUEEN ELIZABETH NEAR DUBLIN HEREINAFTER TRINITY COLLEGE DUBLIN	Ireland

Well-being, quality of life and attractiveness of rural territories as places to live and work

no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
1	RURAL WINGS	RURAL WINGS	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/80103/factsheet/en	FP6	IP - Integrated Project	8,826,736.00	2006	2009	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	Greece
2	TWISTER	Terrestrial Wireless Infrastructure integrated with Satellite Telecommunications for E-Rural applications	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/72828/factsheet/en	FP6	IP - Integrated Project	6,828,502.00	2004	2007	EADS ASTRIUM SAS	France

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3	NEWBIE	New Entrant netWork: Business models for Innovation, entrepreneurship and resilience in European agriculture	http://www.newbie-academy.eu/	H2020	CSA	1,995,040.75	2018	2021	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	Netherlands
4	PoliRural	Future Oriented Collaborative Policy Development for Rural Areas and People	https://polirural.eu/	H2020	RIA	5,999,875.28	2019	2022	CESKA ZEMEDELSKA UNIVERZITA V PRAZE	Czech Republic
5	PROVIDE	PROVIDing smart DELivery of public goods by EU agriculture and forestry	http://www.provide-project.eu/	H2020	RIA	2,991,436.25	2015	2018	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	Italy
6	CONSOLE	CONtract SOLutions for Effective and lasting delivery of agri-environmental-climate public goods by EU agriculture and forestry	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223126/factsheet/en	H2020	RIA	4,999,998.75	2019	2022	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	Italy
7	FAirWAY	Farm systems that produce good Water quality for drinking water supplies	https://www.fairway-project.eu/	H2020	RIA	4,999,865.00	2017	2021	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	Netherlands
8	BE-Rural	Bio-based strategies and roadmaps for enhanced rural and regional development in the EU	https://be-rural.eu/region/about/	H2020	CSA	2,996,288.75	2019	2022	ECOLOGIC INSTITUT gemeinnützige GmbH	Germany
9	ROBUST	Rural-Urban Outlooks: Unlocking Synergies	http://www.rural-urban.eu/	H2020	RIA	5,999,937.50	2017	2021	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	Netherlands
10	SafeWaterAfrica	Self-Sustaining Cleaning Technology for Safe Water Supply and Management in Rural African Areas	https://safewaterafrica.eu/en/home	H2020	RIA	2,989,998.13	2016	2019	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FÖRDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V.	Germany
11	HNV-Link	High Nature Value Farming: Learning, Innovation and Knowledge	http://www.hnvlink.eu/	H2020	CSA	2,230,218.38	2016	2019	CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE HAUTES ETUDES AGRONOMIQUES MEDITERRANEENNES	France
12	TUCAN 3G	Wireless technologies for isolated rural communities in developing	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/601102	FP7	FP7-ICT	1,365,123.00	2013	2016	UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE CATALUNYA	Spain

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		countries based on cellular 3G femtocell deployments								
13	BIR AL-NAS	Bottom-up Integrated Approach for sustainable groundwater management in rural areas	https://biralnas.wordpress.com/papers-publications/my-publications-map/	FP7	FP7-PEOPLE	212,532.00	2013	2016	UNIVERSITA CA' FOSCARI VENEZIA	Italy
14	RURALJOBS	New Sources of Employment to Promote the Wealth-Generating Capacity of Rural Communities	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/211605	FP7	FP7-KBBE	1,400,173.00	2008	2010	DEBRECENI EGYETEM	Hungary
15	TOP-MARD	Towards a Policy Model of Multifunctional Agriculture and Rural Development	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/501749/reporting	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	2,495,080.00	2005	2008	UHI MILLENNIUM INSTITUTE	United Kingdom
16	SCARLED	Structural change in Agriculture and rural livelihoods	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44201	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	809,133.00	2007	2010	LEIBNIZ INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE (IAMO)	Germany

Social capital, social processes, social networks and social innovation

no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
1	RurInno	Social Innovations in Structurally Weak Rural Regions: How Social Entrepreneurs Foster Innovative Solutions to Social Problems	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/199946/factsheet/en	H2020	MSCA-RISE	225,000	2016	2018	LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR RAUMBEZOGENE SOZIALFORSCHUNG EV (IRS)	Germany
2	SIMRA	Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas	http://www.simra-h2020.eu/	H2020	RIA	5,935,828.75	2016	2020	THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE	United Kingdom
3	RURACTION	Social Entrepreneurship in Structurally Weak Rural Regions:	https://ruraction.eu/	H2020	MSCA-ITN-ETN	2,529,895.32	2016	2020	LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR RAUMBEZOGENE SOZIALFORSCHUNG EV (IRS)	Germany

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		Analysing Innovative Troubleshooters in Action									
4	RURALIZATION	The opening of rural areas to renew rural generations, jobs and farms	http://www.ruralization.eu/	H2020	RIA	5,995,904.00	2019	2023	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT	Netherlands	
5	DESIRA	Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223227/factsheet/en	H2020	RIA	4,994,156.25	2019	2023	UNIVERSITA DI PISA	Italy	
6	RURITAGE	Rural regeneration through systemic heritage-led strategies	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/776465	H2020	IA	10,276,187.50	2018	2022	ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	Italy	
7	BE-Rural	Bio-based strategies and roadmaps for enhanced rural and regional development in the EU	https://be-rural.eu/region/about/	H2020	CSA	2,996,288.75	2019	2022	ECOLOGIC INSTITUT gemeinnützige GmbH	Germany	
8	RURAL WINGS	RURAL WINGS	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/80103/factsheet/en	FP6	IP - Integrated Project	8,826,736.00	2006	2009	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	Greece	
9	TWISTER	Terrestrial Wireless Infrastructure integrated with Satellite Telecommunications for E-Rural applications	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/72828/factsheet/en	FP6	IP - Integrated Project	6,828,502.00	2004	2007	EADS ASTRIUM SAS	France	
10	TUCAN 3G	Wireless technologies for isolated rural communities in developing countries based on cellular 3G femtocell deployments	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/601102	FP7	FP7-ICT	1,365,123.00	2013	2016	UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE CATALUNYA	Spain	
11	BIR AL-NAS	Bottom-up IntegRated Approach for sustainabLe grouNdwater mAnagement in rural areaS	https://biralnas.wordpress.com/papers-publications/my-publications-map/	FP7	FP7-PEOPLE	212,532.00	2013	2016	UNIVERSITA CA' FOSCARI VENEZIA	Italy	
12	SOLINSA	Agricultural Knowledge Systems in Transition: Towards a more effective and efficient support of Learning and	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/266306	FP7	FP7-KBBE	3,153,275.00	2011	2014	FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG	Switzerland	

		Innovation Networks for Sustainable Agriculture								
13	RUFUS	Rural Future Networks	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/217381	FP7	FP7-SSH	1,836,179.20	2008	2011	GOTTFRIED WILHELM LEIBNIZ UNIVERSITAET HANNOVER	Germany
14	EASTGRAB	Understanding Land Grabbing in Eastern Europe and Central Asia: an Integrated Assessment of Impacts, Conflicts and Trade-offs	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/326781	FP7	FP7-PEOPLE	175,974.60			ERASMUS UNIVERSITEIT ROTTERDAM	Netherlands
15	A-BARD	Analysing Broadband Access for Rural Development	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/513697	FP6	Coordination action	629,100.00	2005	2006	THE NATIONAL MICROELECTRONICS APPLICATIONS CENTRE LTD	Ireland
16	SEACASE	Sustainable extensive and semi-intensive coastal aquaculture in Southern Europe	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44483	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	2,415,002.00	2007	2010	CENTRO DE CIENCIAS DO MAR DO ALGARVE	Portugal
17	FARMING ECONOMICALLY	Farming economically, a new path to sustainable rural development in Galicia, Spain	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/10680/reporting	FP6	Marie Curie actions- Intra-European Fellowships		2004	2006	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT	Netherlands
18	ETUDE	Enlarging the theoretical understanding of rural development	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44245	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	713,229.00	2007	2009	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT	Netherlands
19	TERA	TERRITORIAL ASPECTS OF ENTERPRISE DEVELOPMENT IN REMOTE RURAL AREAS	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/6469	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,500,000.00	2005	2008	UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA	Italy
20	SCARLED	Structural change in Agriculture and rural livelihoods	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44201	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	809,133.00	2007	2010	LEIBNIZ INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE (IAMO)	Germany

Generation renewal: renewing farming and rural generations

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no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
1	RURALIZATION	The opening of rural areas to renew rural generations, jobs and farms	http://www.ruralization.eu/	H2020	RIA	5,995,904.00	2019	2023	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT	Netherlands
2	FARMPATH	Farming Transitions: Pathways Towards Regional Sustainability of Agriculture in Europe	https://farmpath.hutton.ac.uk/partners	FP7	FP7-KBBE	2,068,272.80	2011	2014	THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE	United Kingdom

Vulnerable groups in rural communities

no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
1	DERREG		https://www.global-rural.org/about/	FP7	FP7-SSH	1,916,222.00	2009	2011	ABERYSTWYTH UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
2	SUSTAINMED	Sustainable agri-food systems and rural development in the Mediterranean Partner Countries	https://sustainmed.iamm.fr/index.php/project-presentation	FP7	FP7-KBBE	2,644,116.60	2010	2013	CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE HAUTES ETUDES AGRONOMIQUES MEDITERRANEENNES	France
3	SOFAR	Social Services in Multifunctional Farms - Social Farming	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/22682	FP7	Specific Action Support	537,850.00	2006	2009	UNIVERSITY OF PISA	Italy

Rural labour/jobs

no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
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D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

1	RURAL WINGS	RURAL WINGS	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/80103/factsheet/en	FP6	IP - Integrated Project	8,826,736.00	2006	2009	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	Greece
2	RAPIDO	Rural areas, people and innovative development	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/84088/reporting/en	FP6	SSA - Specific Support Action	350,200.00	2007	2009	ECOLOGIC - INSTITUTE FOR INTERNATIONAL AND EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY	Germany
3	NEWBIE	New Entrant netWork: Business models for Innovation, entrepreneurship and resilience in European agriculture	http://www.newbie-academy.eu/	H2020	CSA	1,995,040.75	2018	2021	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	Netherlands
4	SUFISA	Sustainable finance for sustainable agriculture and fisheries	https://www.sufisa.eu/	H2020	RIA	4,863,662.50	2015	2019	KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN	Belgium
5	HNV-Link	High Nature Value Farming: Learning, Innovation and Knowledge	http://www.hnvlinc.eu/	H2020	CSA	2,230,218.38	2016	2019	CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE HAUTES ETUDES AGRONOMIQUES MEDITERRANEENNES	France
6	ACARI	Accident causation at rural intersections: influential safety critical factors and processes	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/25686	FP6	Marie Curie actions- Intra-European Fellowships		2005	2006	INSTITUTE FOR TRANSPORT STUDIES UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	United Kingdom
7	RURAL ETINET	Economic and technological intelligence project to facilitate SMEs in rural areas to participate in the Sixth Framework Programme	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/508500	FP6	Network of Excellence	979,453.00	2003	2006	BETA TECHNOLOGY LTD	United Kingdom
8	RURALJOBS	New Sources of Employment to Promote the Wealth-Generating Capacity of Rural Communities	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/211605	FP7	FP7-KBBE	1,400,173.00	2008	2010	DEBRECENI EGYETEM	Hungary
9	SEACASE	Sustainable extensive and semi-intensive coastal aquaculture in Southern Europe	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44483	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	2,415,002.00	2007	2010	CENTRO DE CIENCIAS DO MAR DO ALGARVE	Portugal

10	CARERA	The Impact of CAP Reform on the Employment Levels in Rural Areas	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/2653	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,499,900.00	2006	2008	ARISTOTLE UNIVERSITY THESSALONIKI	OF	Greece
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Rural and climate

no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
1	GLOCHAMORE	Global Change in Mountain Regions: An Integrated Assessment of Causes and Consequences	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/74304/factsheet/en	FP6	Specific Support Action	448,265.00	2003	2005	UNIVERSITÄT WIEN	Austria
2	NB4WASTE	Narrowband IoT for Waste Collection in Rural Areas	http://www.syltec.es/	H2020	SME instrument phase 1	71,249.00	2017	2017	ALPHA INGENIERIA SL	Spain
3	TRUE	Transition paths to sustainable legume based systems in Europe	https://www.true-project.eu/	H2020	RIA	4,999,927.50	2017	2021	THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE	United Kingdom
4	CONSOLE	CONtract SOLutions for Effective and lasting delivery of agri-environmental-climate public goods by EU agriculture and forestry	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223126/factsheet/en	H2020	RIA	4,999,998.75	2019	2022	ALMA STUDIORUM UNIVERSITA BOLOGNA	Italy
5	MEDRES	Cost-effective renewable energy for rural and peri urban areas in the Mediterranean region	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/32020	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	2,015,182.00	2007	2009	OBSERVATOIRE MEDITERRANEEN L'ENERGIE	France
6	ARANGE	Advanced multifunctional forest management in European mountain ranges	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/289437	FP7	FP7-KBBE	3,802,775.79	2012	2015	UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN	Austria
7	BIR AL-NAS	Bottom-up IntegRATED Approach for sustainabLe grouNdwater mAnagement in rural areaS	https://biralnas.wordpress.com/papers-publications/my-publications-map/	FP7	FP7-PEOPLE	212,532.00	2013	2016	UNIVERSITA FOSCARI VENEZIA	Italy

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8	ADHOCSYS	Development of long-term shared vision on AMI technologies for a Networked agri-food sector	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/026548	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	2,403,100.00	2005	2007	EMISFERA SOCIETA COOPERATIVA	Italy
9	FARMING ECONOMICALLY	Farming economically, a new path to sustainable rural development in Galicia, Spain	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/10680/reporting	FP6	Marie Curie actions-Intra-European Fellowships		2004	2006	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT	Netherlands

Rural and biodiversity

no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
1	GLOCHAMORE	Global Change in Mountain Regions: An Integrated Assessment of Causes and Consequences	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/74304/factsheet/en	FP6	Specific Support Action	448,265.00	2003	2005	UNIVERSITÄT WIEN	Austria
2	MULTAGRI	Multifunctionality of Agriculture and Rural Areas	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/74250/factsheet/en	FP6	FP6-SUSTDEV	1,000,443.00	2004	2005	CENTRE NATIONAL DU MACHINISME AGRICOLE, DU GÉNIE RURAL, DES EAUX ET DES FORÊTS	France
3	RES-Integration	Rural sustainable development through integration of renewable energy technologies in poor European regions	https://www.res-integration.com/	FP6	FP6-INCO	1,150,000.00	2004	2007	GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMIO ATHINON	Greece
4	SPEAR	Sustainable options for people, catchment and aquatic resources	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/74226/reporting/en	FP6	FP6-INCO	1,929,144.00	2004	2008	INSTITUTO DO MAR	Portugal
5	LUMOCAP	Dynamic land use change modelling for CAP impact assessment on the rural landscape	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/6556/reporting/es	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,293,040.00	2005	2008	RESEARCH INSTITUUT VOOR KENNISSYSTEMEN	Netherlands
6	ERA-ARD	Agricultural Research for Development (ARD)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/75893/factsheet/en	FP6	FP6-COORDINATION	3,536,234.00	2005	2009	CENTRE DE COOPÉRATION INTERNATIONALE EN RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE POUR LE	France

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									DÉVELOPPEMENT - AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH CENTRE FOR INTERNATIONAL DEVELOPMENT	
7	AGRINERGY	EU Bioenergy Policies and their effects on rural areas and agriculture policies	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/85191/reporting/en	FP6	FP6-POLICIES	294,680.00	2007	2008	ECOLOGIC - INSTITUTE FOR INTERNATIONAL AND EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY GGBMH	Germany
8	REFORLAN	Restoration of forest landscapes for biodiversity conservation and rural development in the drylands of Latin america	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/81319/reporting/es	FP6	FP6-INCO	1,862,979.00	2007	2009	BOURNEMOUTH UNIVERSITY HIGHER EDUCATION CORPORATION	United Kingdom
9	4FCROPS	Future Crops for Food, Feed, Fiber and Fuel	http://www.4fcrops.eu/	FP7	FP7-KBBE	1,264,380.30	2008	2010	CENTRE FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND SAVING FONDATION	Greece
10	AGFORWARD	AGroFORestry that Will Advance Rural Development	https://www.agforward.eu/index.php/en/	FP7	FP7-KBBE	8,009,806.24	2014	2017	CRANFIELD UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
11	SMARTOPENDATA	Linked Open Data for environment protection in Smart Regions	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/603824	FP7	FP7-ENVIRONMENT	3,189,042.11	2013	2015	EMPRESA DE TRANSFORMACION AGRARIA SA	Spain
12	ENVIEVAL	Development and application of new methodological frameworks for the evaluation of environmental impacts of rural development programmes in the EU	https://www.envieval.eu/	FP7	FP7-KBBE	2,335,877.00	2013	2015	JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI	Germany
13	ARANGE	Advanced multifunctional forest management in European mountain ranges	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/289437	FP7	FP7-KBBE	3,802,775.79	2012	2015	UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN	Austria
14	BIR AL-NAS	Bottom-up IntegRated Approach for sustainabLe grouNdwater mAnagement in rural areaS	https://biralnas.wordpress.com/papers-publications/my-publications-map/	FP7	FP7-PEOPLE	212,532.00	2013	2016	UNIVERSITA CA' FOSCARI VENEZIA	Italy
15	MEMOLA	MEditerranean MOuntainous LAndscapes: an historical	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/613265?rcn=197932	FP7	FP7-SSH	2,940,722.56	2014	2017	UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA	Spain

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

		approach to cultural heritage based on traditional agrosystems									
16	VOLANTE	Visions Of LAND use Transitions in Europe	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/265104	FP7	FP7-ENVIRONMENT	9,055,946.60	2010	2015	STICHTING RESEARCH WAGENINGEN	Netherlands	
17	STEAMBIO	Flexible Superheated Steam Torrefaction and Grinding of Indigenous Biomass from Remote Rural Sources to Produce Stable Densified Feedstocks for Chemical and Energy Applications	https://www.steambio.eu/	H2020	H2020-EU.2.1.5.3.	6,979,982.05	2015	2018	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V.	Germany	
18	LANDMARK	LAND Management: Assessment, Research, Knowledge base	http://landmark2020.eu/	H2020	H2020-EU.3.2.	5,307,551.25	2015	2019	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	Netherlands	
19	NOAW	Innovative approaches to turn agricultural waste into ecological and economic assets	http://noaw2020.eu/	H2020	H2020-EU.3.2. H2020-EU.3.5.4.	7,816,232.50	2016	2020	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE	France	
20	DIVERFARMING	Crop diversification and low-input farming across Europe: from practitioners engagement and ecosystems services to increased revenues and chain organisation	http://www.diverfarming.eu/index.php/en/	H2020	H2020-EU.3.2.1.1. H2020-EU.3.2.6.1.	10,457,923.75	2017	2022	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE CARTAGENA	Spain	
21	UNISECO	Understanding and improving the sustainability of agro-ecological farming systems in the EU	https://uniseco-project.eu/en	H2020			2018	2021	Thünen Institute	Germany	
22	LIFT	Low-Input Farming and Territories - Integrating knowledge for improving ecosystem-based farming	https://www.lift-h2020.eu/	H2020	H2020-EU.3.2.1.1.	5,000,000.00	2018	2022	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE	France	

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

23	SUPER-G	Developing Sustainable Permanent Grassland systems and policies	https://www.super-g.eu/	H2020	H2020-EU.3.2.1.1. H2020-EU.3.2.1.3. H2020-EU.3.2.1.2.	9,994,996.83	2018	2023	UNIVERSITY OF NEWCASTLE UPON TYNE	United Kingdom
24	GRETA	GRETA – Green infrastructure: Enhancing biodiversity and ecosystem services for territorial development	https://www.espon.eu/green-infrastructure	ESPON			2017	2019		
25	AGRORES	Investing in Renewable Energies for Agriculture	https://www.interregeurope.eu/agrores/	INTERREG			2019	2023		
26	COCONUT	Understanding effects of land use changes on ecosystems to halt loss of biodiversity due to habitat destruction, fragmentation and degradation	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44346	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,057,051.00	2006	2009	SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET	Sweden

Rural and circular and efficient resource use

no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
1	NB4WASTE	Narrowband IoT for Waste Collection in Rural Areas	http://www.syltec.es/	H2020	SME instrument phase 1	71,249.00	2017	2017	ALPHA SYLTEC INGENIERIA SL	Spain
2	RURECO	Institutions for Resilient Groundwater Dependent Rural Economies	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/209980/factsheet/en	H2020	MSCA-IF-EF-ST Standard EF	173,076.00	2018	2020	BUREAU DE RECHERCHES GEOLOGIQUES ET MINIERES	France

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

3	WATERPROTECT	Innovative tools enabling drinking WATER PROTECTION in rural and urban environments	https://water-protect.eu/	H2020	RIA	4,997,006.50	2017	2020	VLAAMSE INSTELLING VOOR TECHNOLOGISCH ONDERZOEK N.V.	Belgium
4	SiEUGreen	Sino-European innovative green and smart cities	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/212412/factsheet/en	H2020	IA	8,377,867.50	2018	2021	NORGES MILJØ- OG BIOVITENSKAPLIGE UNIVERSITET	Norway
5	AgroCycle	Sustainable techno-economic solutions for the agricultural value chain	http://www.agrocycle.eu/	H2020	RIA	7,650,049.75	2016	2019	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN	Ireland
6	AGROinLOG	Demonstration of innovative integrated biomass logistics centres for the Agro-industry sector in Europe	http://agroinlog-h2020.eu/en/home/	H2020	IA	6,385,661.25	2016	2020	FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS	Spain
7	MAGIC	Marginal lands for Growing Industrial Crops: Turning a burden into an opportunity	http://magic-h2020.eu/	H2020	RIA	5,999,987.50	2017	2021	CENTRE FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND SAVING FOUNDATION	Greece
8	NUTRIMAN	Nutrient Management and Nutrient Recovery Thematic Network	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/818470	H2020	CSA	1,999,927.50	2018	2021	TERRA HUMANA TISZTA TECHNOLOGIAKATFEJLESZTO TERVEZO ES KIVITELEZO KFT	Hungary
9	INNOSETA	Accelerating Innovative practices for Spraying Equipment, Training and Advising in European agriculture through the mobilization of Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773864	H2020	CSA	1,998,562.50	2018	2021	UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE CATALUNYA	Spain
10	EuroDairy	A Europe-wide thematic network supporting a sustainable future for EU dairy farmers	https://eurodairy.eu/	H2020	CSA	1,997,237.75	2016	2019	THE AGRICULTURE AND HORTICULTURE DEVELOPMENT BOARD (AHDB)	United Kingdom
11	ETUDE	Enlarging the theoretical understanding of rural development	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44245	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	713,229.00	2007	2009	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT	Netherlands

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

12	ARSLAND	SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF ARSENIC CONTAMINATED WATER AND SOIL IN RURAL AREAS OF LATIN AMERICA	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/15114	FP6	Specific Action Support	129,964.00	2006	2007	INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO AGRARIO DE CASTILLA Y LEÓN	Spain
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Rural values and income

no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
1	RurInno	Social Innovations in Structurally Weak Rural Regions: How Social Entrepreneurs Foster Innovative Solutions to Social Problems	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/199946/factsheet/en	H2020	MSCA-RISE	225,000.00	2016	2018	LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FÜR RAUMBEZOGENE SOZIALFORSCHUNG (IRS) EV	Germany
2	SIMRA	Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas	http://www.simra-h2020.eu/	H2020	RIA	5,935,828.75	2016	2020	THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE	United Kingdom
3	AgriLink	AgriLink. Agricultural Knowledge: Linking farmers, advisors and researchers to boost innovation	https://www.agrilink2020.eu/	H2020	RIA	4,999,966.49	2017	2021	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE	France
4	BOND	Bringing Organisations and Network Development to higher levels in the farming sector in Europe	https://www.bondproject.eu/	H2020	CSA	2,890,691.25	2017	2021	COVENTRY UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
5	CORE Organic Cofund	Coordination of European Transnational Research in Organic Food and Farming Systems Cofund	https://projects.au.dk/coreorganiccofund/	H2020	ERA-NET-Cofund	20,628,860.02	2016	2021	AARHUS UNIVERSITET	Denmark
6	PROIntensAfrica	Towards a long-term Africa-EU partnership to raise sustainable food and nutrition security in Africa	http://www.intensafrika.org/	H2020	CSA	1,777,873.75	2015	2017	STICHTING RESEARCH WAGENINGEN	Netherlands

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

7	LIVERUR	Living Lab research concept in Rural Areas	https://liverur.eu/	H2020	RIA	4,107,005.00	2018	2021	FUNDACION UNIVERSITARIA SAN ANTONIO	Spain
8	RUBIZMO	Replicable business models for modern rural economies	https://rubizmo.eu/	H2020	RIA	3,928,852.04	2018	2021	RISE RESEARCH INSTITUTES OF SWEDEN AB	Sweden
9	AGRIFORVALOR	Bringing added value to agriculture and forest sectors by closing the research and innovation divide	http://www.agriforvalor.eu/	H2020	CSA	1,997,416.25	2016	2018	STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	Germany
10	DiverIMPACTS	Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains Towards Sustainability	https://www.diverimpacts.net/	H2020	RIA	11,192,323.50	2017	2022	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE	France
11	SMARTCHAIN	Towards Innovation - driven and smart solutions in short food supply chains	https://www.smartchain-h2020.eu/	H2020	RIA	5,998,373.75	2018	2021	UNIVERSITAET HOHENHEIM	Germany
12	FERTINNOWA	Transfer of INNOvative techniques for sustainable WAtter use in FERTigated crops	https://www.fertinnowa.com/	H2020	CSA	2,999,273.40	2016	2018	PROEFSTATION VOOR DE GROENTETEELT	Belgium
13	Legumes Translated	Translating knowledge for legume-based farming for feed and food systems	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/817634	H2020	CSA	2,159,043.75	2018	2021	JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI	Germany
14	Hennovation	Practice-led innovation supported by science and market-driven actors in the laying hen and other livestock sectors	http://hennovation.eu/results/index.html	H2020	CSA	2,094,055.00	2015	2017	UNIVERSITY OF BRISTOL	United Kingdom
15	EuroDairy	A Europe-wide thematic network supporting a sustainable future for EU dairy farmers	https://eurodairy.eu/	H2020	CSA	1,997,237.75	2016	2019	THE AGRICULTURE AND HORTICULTURE DEVELOPMENT BOARD (AHDB)	United Kingdom
16	Eu PiG	EU Pig Innovation Group	https://www.eupig.eu/	H2020	CSA	2,000,000.00	2016	2020	THE AGRICULTURE AND HORTICULTURE DEVELOPMENT BOARD (AHDB)	United Kingdom

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

17	OK-Net EcoFeed	Organic Knowledge Network on Monogastric Animal Feed	https://ok-net-ecofeed.eu/	H2020	CSA	1,990,368.75	2018	2020	INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE MOVEMENTS EUROPEAN UNION REGIONAL GROUP	Sweden
18	LIAISON	Better Rural Innovation: Linking Actors, Instruments and Policies through Networks	http://liaison2020.eu/	H2020	RIA	4,999,143.75	2018	2021	HOCHSCHULE FUR NACHHALTIGE ENTWICKLUNG EBERSWALDE	Germany
19	ENVIEVAL	Development and application of new methodological frameworks for the evaluation of environmental impacts of rural development programmes in the EU	https://www.envieval.eu/	FP7	FP7-KBBE	2,335,877.00	2013	2015	JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI	Germany
20	ARANGE	Advanced multifunctional forest management in European mountain ranges	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/289437	FP7	FP7-KBBE	3,802,775.79	2012	2015	UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN	Austria
21	MEMOLA	MEditerranean MOntainous LAndscapes: an historical approach to cultural heritage based on traditional agrosystems	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/613265?rcn=197932	FP7	FP7-SSH	2,940,722.56	2014	2017	UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA	Spain
22	RUFUS	Rural Future Networks	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/217381	FP7	FP7-SSH	1,836,179.20	2008	2011	GOTTFRIED WILHELM LEIBNIZ UNIVERSITAET HANNOVER	Germany
23	CAP-IRE	Assessing the multiple Impacts of the Common Agricultural Policies (CAP) on Rural Economies	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/216672	FP7	FP7-SSH	1,881,354.00			ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	Italy
24	SEACASE	Sustainable extensive and semi-intensive coastal aquaculture in Southern Europe	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44483	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	2,415,002.00	2007	2010	CENTRO DE CIENCIAS DO MAR DO ALGARVE	Portugal
25	FARMING ECONOMICALLY	Farming economically, a new path to sustainable rural development in Galicia, Spain	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/10680/reporting	FP6	Marie Curie actions- Intra-European Fellowships		2004	2006	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT	Netherlands

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

26	ETUDE	Enlarging the theoretical understanding of rural development	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44245	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	713,229.00	2007	2009	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEI	Netherlands
27	AG2020	Foresight analysis for world agricultural markets (2020) and Europe	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44280	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,996,146.00	2007	2010	DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET (TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF DENMARK)	Denmark
28	TERA	TERRITORIAL ASPECTS OF ENTERPRISE DEVELOPMENT IN REMOTE RURAL AREAS	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/6469	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,500,000.00	2005	2008	UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA	Italy
29	SCARLED	Structural change in Agriculture and rural livelihoods	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44201	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	809,133.00	2007	2010	LEIBNIZ INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE (IAMO)	Germany
30	FOODIMA	EU food industry dynamics and methodological advances	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44283	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,046,133.00	2007	2010	ARISTOTLE UNIVERSITY OF THESSALONIKI	Greece

Rural and digital

no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
1	RURAL WINGS	RURAL WINGS	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/80103/factsheet/en	FP6	IP - Integrated Project	8,826,736.00	2006	2009	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	Greece
2	TWISTER	Terrestrial Wireless Infrastructure integrated with Satellite Telecommunications for E-Rural applications	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/72828/factsheet/en	FP6	IP - Integrated Project	6,828,502.00	2004	2007	EADS ASTRIUM SAS	France

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

3	C@R	Collaboration@Rural: A collaborative platform for working and living in rural areas	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/80466/factsheet/en	FP6	IP - Integrated Project	14,955,657.00	2006	2009	TECNOLOGIAS Y SERVICIOS AGRARIOS SA	Spain
4	AGRICORE	Agent-based support tool for the development of agriculture policies	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223202/factsheet/en	H2020	RIA	3,937,248.75	2019	2023	OPTIMIZACION ORIENTADA A LA SOSTENIBILIDAD SL	Spain
5	DESIRA	Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223227/factsheet/en	H2020	RIA	4,994,156.25	2019	2023	UNIVERSITA DI PISA	Italy
6	NUTRIMAN	Nutrient Management and Nutrient Recovery Thematic Network	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/818470	H2020	CSA	1,999,927.50	2018	2021	TERRA HUMANA TISZTA TECHNOLOGIAKATFEJ LESZTO TERVEZO ES KIVITELEZO KFT	Hungary
7	FERTINNOWA	Transfer of INNOvative techniques for sustainable WAtter use in FERTigated crops	https://www.fertinnowa.com/	H2020	CSA	2,999,273.40	2016	2018	PROEFSTATION VOOR DE GROENTETEELT	Belgium
8	INNOSETA	Accelerating Innovative practices for Spraying Equipment, Training and Advising in European agriculture through the mobilization of Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773864	H2020	CSA	1,998,562.50	2018	2021	UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA CATALUNYA	Spain
9	FOX	Innovative down-scaled FOod processing in a boX	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/817683	H2020	RIA	7,065,223.75	2019	2023	DIL DEUTSCHES INSTITUT FUR LEBENSMITTELTECHNIK EV	Germany
10	Smart-AKIS	European Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) towards innovation-driven research in Smart Farming Technology	https://www.smart-akis.com/	H2020	CSA	1,997,756.15	2016	2018	GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON	Greece

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

11	4D4F	Data Driven Dairy Decisions 4 Farmers	https://4d4f.eu/	H2020	CSA	2,105,796.25	2016	2019	INNOVATION FOR AGRICULTURE	United Kingdom
12	IoF2020	Internet of Food and Farm 2020	https://www.iof2020.eu/	H2020	IA	34,234,990.42	2017	2020	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	Netherlands
13	PANTHEON	Precision Farming of Hazelnut Orchards	http://www.project-pantheon.eu/	H2020	RIA	3,144,452.50	2017	2021	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI ROMA TRE	Italy
14	ROMI	RObotics for MIcrofarms	https://romi-project.eu/	H2020	RIA	3,868,186.25	2017	2021	INSTITUT D'ARQUITECTURA AVANÇADA CATALUNYA	Spain
15	AfriCultuReS	Enhancing Food Security in AFRICan AgriCULTUral Systems with the Support of REmote Sensing	http://www.africultures.eu/project	H2020	RIA	8,531,533.20	2017	2021	GMV AEROSPACE AND DEFENCE SA	Spain
16	SmartAgriHubs	Connecting the dots to unleash the innovation potential for digital transformation of the European agri-food sector	https://smartagrihubs.eu/	H2020	IA	22,423,146.00	2018	2022	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	Netherlands
17	PANACEA	A thematic network to design the penetration PATH of Non-food Agricultural Crops into European Agriculture	http://www.panacea-h2020.eu/	H2020	CSA	1,999,500.00	2017	2020	CENTRE FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND SAVING FOUNDATION	Greece
18	SheepNet	Sharing Expertise and Experience towards sheep Productivity through NETworking	http://www.sheepnet.network/	H2020	CSA	1,995,289.38	2016	2019	INSTITUT L'ELEVAGE	France
19	FAIRshare	FAIRshare. Farm Advisory digital Innovation tools Realised and Shared	https://fairshareproject.eu/	H2020	CSA	6,998,652.50	2018	2023	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY	Ireland
20	NIVA	A New IACS Vision in Action	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/842009	H2020	IA	10,677,810.00	2019	2022	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	Netherlands

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

21	DEMETER	Building an Interoperable, Data-Driven, Innovative and Sustainable European Agri-Food Sector	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/857202	H2020	IA	17,704,191.25	2019	2023	WATERFORD INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY	Ireland
22	ATLAS	Agricultural Interoperability and Analysis System	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/857125	H2020	IA	15,406,420.00	2019	2022	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FÖRDERUNG ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG (E.V.)	Germany
23	TUCAN 3G	Wireless technologies for isolated rural communities in developing countries based on cellular 3G femtocell deployments	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/601102	FP7	FP7-ICT	1,365,123.00	2013	2016	UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA CATALUNYA	Spain
24	SMARTOPENDATA	Linked Open Data for environment protection in Smart Regions	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/603824	FP7	FP7-ENVIRONMENT	3,189,042.11	2013	2015	EMPRESA DE TRANSFORMACION AGRARIA SA	Spain
25	SmartRuralGrid	Smart ICT-enabled Rural Grid innovating resilient electricity distribution infrastructures, services and business models	https://smarruralgrid.eu/	FP7	FP7-ICT	4,944,690.00	2014	2017	ESTABANELL Y PAHISA ENERGIA SA	Spain
26	AMI-NETFOOD	Development of long-term shared vision on AMI technologies for a Networked agri-food sector	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/015776	FP6	Specific Support Action	937,336.00	2005	2006	INNOPOLE, S.L.	Spain
27	BROADWAN	Broadband services for everyone over fixed wireless access networks	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/01930	FP6	Integrated Project	13,814,903.00	2003	2006	TELENOR ASA	Norway
28	MOSAIC	Mobile worker support environments: Aligning innovation in mobile technologies, applications and workplaces for location-	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/014341	FP6	Specific Support Action	1,244,679.00	2004	2005	STICHTING TELEMATICA INSTITUUT	Netherlands

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

		independent cooperation and networking								
29	COCONUT	Understanding effects of land use changes on ecosystems to halt loss of biodiversity due to habitat destruction, fragmentation and degradation	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44346	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,057,051.00	2006	2009	SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET	Sweden

Smart villages/communities

no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/ project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
1	SALSA	Small farms, small food businesses and sustainable food security	http://www.salsa.uevora.pt/en/	H2020	RIA	4,958,172.50	2016	2020	UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA	Portugal
2	PROVIDE	PROVIDing smart DELivery of public goods by EU agriculture and forestry	http://www.provide-project.eu/	H2020	RIA	2,991,436.25	2015	2018	ALMA MATER STUDIUM UNIVERSITA BOLOGNA	Italy
3	SIEUGreen	Sino-European innovative green and smart cities	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/212412/factsheet/en	H2020	IA	8,377,867.50	2018	2021	NORGES MILJO-OG BIOVITENSKAPLIGE UNIVERSITET	Norway
4	SMARTCHAIN	Towards Innovation - driven and smart solutions in short food supply chains	https://www.smartchain-h2020.eu/	H2020	RIA	5,998,373.75	2018	2021	UNIVERSITAET HOHENHEIM	Germany
5	TUCAN 3G	Wireless technologies for isolated rural communities in developing countries based on cellular 3G femtocell deployments	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/601102	FP7	FP7-ICT	1,365,123.00	2013	2016	UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA CATALUNYA	Spain
6	SmartRuralGrid	Smart ICT-enabled Rural Grid innovating resilient electricity	https://smarruralgrid.eu/	FP7	FP7-ICT	4,944,690.00	2014	2017	ESTABANELL Y PAHISA ENERGIA SA	Spain

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

		distribution infrastructures, services and business models								
7	BROADWAN	Broadband services for everyone over fixed wireless access networks	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/001930	FP6	Integrated Project	13,814,903.00	2003	2006	TELENOR ASA	Norway
8	CRESMED	Cost efficient and reliable rural electrification schemes for South Mediterranean countries based on multi user Solar Hybrid grids	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/15286	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,800,000.00	2006	2009	TRAMA TECNOMBIENTAL S.L.	Spain

Territorial approaches and policies

no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
1	COASTAL	Collaborative And Sea InTegration pLatform	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/215939/factsheet/en	H2020	RIA	4,999,943.75	2018	2022	VLAAMSE INSTELLING VOOR TECHNOLOGISCH ONDERZOEK N.V.	Belgium
2	ROBUST	Rural-Urban Outlooks: Unlocking Synergies	http://www.rural-urban.eu/	H2020	RIA	5,999,937.50	2017	2021	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	Netherlands
3	LANDSUPPORT	Development of Integrated Web-Based Land Decision Support System Aiming towards the Implementation of Policies for Agriculture and Environment	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/215938/factsheet/en	H2020	RIA	6,999,771,25	2018	2021	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI NAPOLI FEDERICO II	Italy
4	AGRICORE	Agent-based support tool for the development of agriculture policies	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223202/factsheet/en	H2020	RIA	3,937,248.75	2019	2023	OPTIMIZACION ORIENTADA A LA SOSTENIBILIDAD SL	Spain

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

5	PEGASUS	Public Ecosystem Goods And Services from land management - Unlocking the Synergies	http://pegasus.ieep.eu/	H2020	RIA	3,007,800.00	2015	2018	INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY, LONDON	United Kingdom
6	Contracts2.0	Co-design of novel contract models for innovative agri-environmental-climate measures and for valorisation of environmental public goods	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/222534/factsheet/en	H2020	RIA	4,998,188.75	2019	2023	LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG (ZALF) e.V.	Germany
7	MAGIC	Marginal lands for Growing Industrial Crops: Turning a burden into an opportunity	http://magic-h2020.eu/	H2020	RIA	5,999,987.50	2017	2021	CENTRE FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND SAVING FOUNDATION	Greece
8	EURAKNOS	Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs: towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System	https://www.euraknos.eu/	H2020	CSA	2,101,286.25	2019	2020	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	Belgium
9	PROIntensAfrica	Towards a long-term Africa-EU partnership to raise sustainable food and nutrition security in Africa	http://www.intensafrica.org/	H2020	CSA	1,777,873.75	2015	2017	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	Netherlands
10	BIR AL-NAS	Bottom-up IntegRated Approach for sustainabLe grouNdwater mAnagement in rural areaS	https://biralnas.wordpress.com/papers-publications/my-publications-map/	FP7	FP7-PEOPLE	212,532.00	2013	2016	UNIVERSITA CA' FOSCARI VENEZIA	Italy
11	GLOBAL-RURAL	The Global Countryside: Rural Change and Development in Globalization	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/339567	FP7	FP7-IDEAS-ERC	2,263,107.00	2014	2019	ABERYSTWYTH UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
12	RURAGRI	Facing sustainability: new relationships between rural	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/235175	FP7	FP7-KBBE	1,208,730.00	2009	2014	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE	France

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

		areas and agriculture in Europe								
13	SPARD	Spatial Analysis of Rural Development Measures	http://project2.zalf.de/spard/	FP7	FP7-KBBE	1,900,000.00	2010	2013	Leibniz-Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF)	Germany
14	RUFUS	Rural Future Networks	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/217381	FP7	FP7-SSH	1,836,179.20	2008	2011	GOTTFRIED WILHELM LEIBNIZ UNIVERSITAET HANNOVER	Germany
15	COEXIST	Interaction in European coastal waters: A roadmap to sustainable integration of aquaculture and fisheries	https://www.coexistproject.eu/coexist-project/coexist-overview	FP7	FP7-KBBE	3,777,931.00			Institute of Marine Research (IMR)	Norway
16	DARDRA	Defining and Assessing Rurality/Urbanity and Delineating Rural/Urban Areas in Europe	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/220832	FP7	FP7-PEOPLE	178,307.05	2009	2010	UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHAMPTON	United Kingdom
17	DERREG		https://www.global-rural.org/about/	FP7	FP7-SSH	1,916,222.00	2009	2011	ABERYSTWYTH UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
18	TERESA	Types of interaction between economy, rural society, environment and agricultural activities in European regions	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44400	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,006,000.00	2007	2009	OESTERREICHISCHES INSTITUT FUER RAUMPLANUNG	Austria
19	RD-GOVERNANCE	The structures of civil society governance in promoting rural development (on the example of East Germany and Ukraine)	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/514036	FP6	Marie Curie actions-Incoming International Fellowships		2005	2007	INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE	Germany
20	FOODIMA	EU food industry dynamics and methodological advances	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44283	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,046,133.00	2007	2010	ARISTOTLE UNIVERSITY OF THESSALONIKI	Greece

Innovation policies and innovation ecosystems for rural communities

no	project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme	budget (in euros)	start year	end year	coordinator	country of coordinator
1	GLOCHAMORE	Global Change in Mountain Regions: An Integrated Assessment of Causes and Consequences	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/74304/factsheet/en	FP6	Specific Support Action	448,265.00	2003	2005	UNIVERSITÄT WIEN	Austria
2	RURAL WINGS	RURAL WINGS	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/80103/factsheet/en	FP6	IP - Integrated Project	8,826,736.00	2006	2009	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	Greece
3	TWISTER	Terrestrial Wireless Infrastructure integrated with Satellite Telecommunications for E-Rural applications	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/72828/factsheet/en	FP6	IP - Integrated Project	6,828,502.00	2004	2007	EADS ASTRIUM SAS	France
4	RAPIDO	Rural areas, people and innovative development	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/84088/reporting/en	FP6	SSA - Specific Support Action	350,200.00	2007	2009	ECOLOGIC - INSTITUTE FOR INTERNATIONAL AND EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY	Germany
5	RurInno	Social Innovations in Structurally Weak Rural Regions: How Social Entrepreneurs Foster Innovative Solutions to Social Problems	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/199946/factsheet/en	H2020	MSCA-RISE	225,000.00	2016	2018	LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FÜR RAUMBEZOGENE SOZIALFORSCHUNG (IRS) EV	Germany
6	AGRISPIN	Space for Agricultural Innovation	https://agrispin.eu/	H2020	CSA	1,994,306.75	2015	2017	LANDBRUG & FODEVARER F.M.B.A.	Denmark
7	RURECO	Institutions for Resilient Groundwater Dependent Rural Economies	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/209980/factsheet/en	H2020	MSCA-IF-EF-ST - Standard EF	173,076.00	2018	2020	BUREAU DE RECHERCHES	France

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

									GEOLOGIQUES ET MINIERES	
8	SUFISA	Sustainable finance for sustainable agriculture and fisheries	https://www.sufisa.eu/	H2020	RIA	4,863,662.50	2015	2019	KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN	Belgium
9	SUPREMA	SUpport for Policy RElevant Modelling of Agriculture	https://www.suprema-project.eu/	H2020	CSA	999,823.75	2018	2020	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	Netherlands
10	MIND STEP	Modelling INdividual Decisions to Support The European Policies related to agriculture	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223209/factsheet/en	H2020	RIA	4,000,000.00	2019	2023	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	Netherlands
11	LIVERUR	Living Lab research concept in Rural Areas	https://liverur.eu/	H2020	RIA	4,107,005.00	2018	2021	FUNDACION UNIVERSITARIA SAN ANTONIO	Spain
12	HNV-Link	High Nature Value Farming: Learning, Innovation and Knowledge	http://www.hnvlink.eu/	H2020	CSA	2,230,218.38	2016	2019	CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE HAUTES ETUDES AGRONOMIQUES MEDITERRANEENNES	France
13	NIVA	A New IACS Vision in Action	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/842009	H2020	IA	10,677,810.00	2019	2022	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	Netherlands
14	Hennovation	Practice-led innovation supported by science and market-driven actors in the laying hen and other livestock sectors	http://hennovation.eu/results/index.html	H2020	CSA	2,094,055.00	2015	2017	UNIVERSITY OF BRISTOL	United Kingdom
15	LIAISON	Better Rural Innovation: Linking Actors, Instruments and Policies through Networks	http://liaison2020.eu/	H2020	RIA	4,999,143.75	2018	2021	HOCHSCHULE FUR NACHHALTIGE ENTWICKLUNG EBERSWALDE	Germany

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

16	NEXTFOOD	Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/	H2020	RIA	7,000,000.00	2018	2022	SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET	Sweden
17	AgriDemo-F2F	Building an interactive AgriDemo-Hub community: enhancing farmer to farmer learning	https://agridemo-h2020.eu/	H2020	CSA	1,985,363.75	2017	2019	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK	Belgium
18	PLAID	Peer-to-Peer Learning: Accessing Innovation through Demonstration	https://www.plaid-h2020.eu/	H2020	CSA	2,187,767,50	2017	2019	THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE	United Kingdom
19	NEFERTITI	Networking European Farms to Enhance Cross Fertilisation and Innovation Uptake through Demonstration	https://nefertiti-h2020.eu/	H2020	CSA	6,999,991.25	2018	2021	Association de Coordination Technique Agricole	France
20	SMARTOPENDATA	Linked Open Data for environment protection in Smart Regions	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/603824	FP7	FP7-ENVIRONMENT	3,189,042.11	2013	2015	EMPRESA DE TRANSFORMACION AGRARIA SA	Spain
21	ARANGE	Advanced multifunctional forest management in European mountain ranges	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/289437	FP7	FP7-KBBE	3,802,775.79	2012	2015	UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN	Austria
22	AGFORWARD	AGroFORestry that Will Advance Rural Development	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/613520	FP7	FP7-KBBE	8,009,806.24	2014	2017	CRANFIELD UNIVERSITY	United Kingdom
23	SOLINSA	Agricultural Knowledge Systems in Transition: Towards a more effective and efficient support of Learning and Innovation Networks for Sustainable Agriculture	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/266306	FP7	FP7-KBBE	3,153,275.00	2011	2014	FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG	Switzerland

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

24	PRO AKIS	Prospects for Farmers' Support: Advisory Services in European AKIS	https://430a.uni-hohenheim.de/pro-akis	FP7	FP7-KBBE	1,861,524.24	2012	2015	UNIVERSITAET HOHENHEIM	Germany
25	TOP-MARD	Towards a Policy Model of Multifunctional Agriculture and Rural Development	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/501749/reporting	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	2,495,080.00	2005	2008	UHI MILLENNIUM INSTITUTE	United Kingdom
26	CAPRI-RD	Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact - The Rural Development Dimension	http://enrd.ec.europa.eu/enrd-static/networks-and-networking/research-initiatives/en/research-projects-capri_rd_en.html	FP7	FP7-KBBE	3,030,002.00	2009	2013	RHEINISCHE FRIEDRICH-WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAT BONN	Germany
27	AMI-NETFOOD	Development of long-term shared vision on AMI technologies for a Networked agri-food sector	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/015776	FP6	Specific Support Action	937,336.00	2005	2006	INNOPOLE, S.L.	Spain
28	ADHOCSYS	Development of long-term shared vision on AMI technologies for a Networked agri-food sector	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/026548	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	2,403,100.00	2005	2007	EMISFERA SOCIETA COOPERATIVA	Italy
29	BROADWAN	Broadband services for everyone over fixed wireless access networks	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/001930	FP6	Integrated Project	13,814,903.00	2003	2006	TELENOR ASA	Norway
30	MOSAIC	Mobile worker support environments: Aligning innovation in mobile technologies, applications and workplaces for location-independent cooperation and networking	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/004341	FP6	Specific Support Action	1,244,679.00	2004	2005	STICHTING TELEMATICA INSTITUUT	Netherlands
31	SEAMLESS	System for Environmental and Agricultural Modelling;	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/10036	FP6	Integrated Project	15,553,272.00	2005	2009	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT	Netherlands

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

		Linking European Science and Society								
32	COCONUT	Understanding effects of land use changes on ecosystems to halt loss of biodiversity due to habitat destruction, fragmentation and degradation	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44346	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,057,051.00	2006	2009	SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET	Sweden
33	ETUDE	Enlarging the theoretical understanding of rural development	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44245	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	713,229.00	2007	2009	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT	Netherlands
34	AG2020	Foresight analysis for world agricultural markets (2020) and Europe	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44280	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,996,146.00	2007	2010	DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET (TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF DENMARK)	Denmark
35	MEACAP	Impact of Environmental Agreements of the CAP	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/503604	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,940,640.00	2004	2007	INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY	United Kingdom
36	SCARLED	Structural change in Agriculture and rural livelihoods	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44201	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	809,133.00	2007	2010	LEIBNIZ INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE (IAMO)	Germany
37	FOODIMA	EU food industry dynamics and methodological advances	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44283	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,046,133.00	2007	2010	ARISTOTLE UNIVERSITY OF THESSALONIKI	Greece

Policy performance evaluation

project acronym	project full name	cordis/project website	programme	funding scheme				coordinator
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D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

no						budget (in euros)	start year	end year		country of coordinator
1	RAPIDO	Rural areas, people and innovative development	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/84088/reporting/en	FP6	SSA - Specific Support Action	350,200.00	2007	2009	ECOLOGIC - INSTITUTE FOR INTERNATIONAL AND EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY	Germany
2	SIMRA	Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas	http://www.simra-h2020.eu/	H2020	RIA	5,935,828.75	2016	2020	THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE	United Kingdom
3	SURE-Farm	Towards SUsustainable and REsilient EU FARMing systems	http://www.surefarmproject.eu/	H2020	RIA	4,875,616.25	2017	2021	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY	Netherlands
4	BESTMAP	Behavioral, Ecological and Socio-economic Tools for Modelling Agricultural Policy	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223207/factsheet/en	H2020	RIA	3,995,811.25	2019	2023	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	United Kingdom
5	PoliRural	Future Oriented Collaborative Policy Development for Rural Areas and People	https://polirural.eu/	H2020	RIA	5,999,875.28	2019	2022	CESKA ZEMEDELSKA UNIVERZITA V PRAZE	Czech Republic
6	PEGASUS	Public Ecosystem Goods And Services from land management - Unlocking the Synergies	http://pegasus.ieep.eu/	H2020	RIA	3,007,800.00	2015	2018	INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY, LONDON	United Kingdom
7	FAirWAY	Farm systems that produce good Water quality for drinking water supplies	https://www.fairway-project.eu/	H2020	RIA	4,999,865.00	2017	2021	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	Netherlands
8	TOP-MARD	Towards a Policy Model of Multifunctional Agriculture and Rural Development	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/501749/reporting	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	2,495,080.00	2005	2008	UHI MILLENNIUM INSTITUTE	United Kingdom

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

9	ENVIEVAL	Development and application of new methodological frameworks for the evaluation of environmental impacts of rural development programmes in the EU	https://www.envieval.eu/	FP7	FP7-KBBE	2,335,877.00	2013	2015	JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSGINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI	Germany
10	FARMPATH	Farming Transitions: Pathways Towards Regional Sustainability of Agriculture in Europe	https://farmpath.hutton.ac.uk/partners	FP7	FP7-KBBE	2,068,272.80	2011	2014	THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE	United Kingdom
11	ARANGE	Advanced multifunctional forest management in European mountain ranges	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/289437	FP7	FP7-KBBE	3,802,775.79	2012	2015	UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN	Austria
12	C-BIRD	Cooperative Business and Innovative Rural Development: Synergies between Commercial and Academic Partners	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/611490	FP7	FP7-PEOPLE	597,663.91	2014	2017	TRAKIYSKI UNIVERSITET	Bulgaria
13	RURAL DECISIONS	Development of a framework for managing uncertain decisions in agricultural and environmental policies – Towards an integrated policy for decision-making support in rural areas	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/235979/reporting/es	FP7	FP7-PEOPLE	232,684.02	2009	2012	HUMBOLDT-UNIVERSITAET ZU BERLIN	Germany
14	CLAIM	Supporting the role of the Common agricultural policy in LANDscape valorisation: Improving the knowledge base of the contribution of landscape Management to the rural economy	http://www.claimproject.eu/about.aspx	FP7	FP7-KBBE	1,874,220.00	2012	2014	ALMA MATER STUDIUM UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	Italy

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

15	SOLINSA	Agricultural Knowledge Systems in Transition: Towards a more effective and efficient support of Learning and Innovation Networks for Sustainable Agriculture	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/266306	FP7	FP7-KBBE	3,153,275.00	2011	2014	FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FÜR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG	Switzerland
16	SUSTAINMED	Sustainable agri-food systems and rural development in the Mediterranean Partner Countries	https://sustainmed.iamm.fr/index.php/project-presentation	FP7	FP7-KBBE	2,644,116.60	2010	2013	CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE HAUTES ETUDES AGRONOMIQUES MEDITERRANEENNES	France
17	SPARD	Spatial Analysis of Rural Development Measures	http://project2.zalf.de/spard/	FP7	FP7-KBBE	1,900,000.00	2010	2013	Leibniz-Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF)	Germany
18	RUDI	Assessing the Impact of Rural Development Policies	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/213034	FP7	FP7-KBBE	3,257,692.00	2008	2010	VEREIN FUER LANDLICHE STRUKTURFORSCHUNG EV	Germany
19	RUFUS	Rural Future Networks	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/217381	FP7	FP7-SSH	1,836,179.20	2008	2011	GOTTFRIED WILHELM LEIBNIZ UNIVERSITAET HANNOVER	Germany
20	CAP-IRE	Assessing the multiple Impacts of the Common Agricultural Policies (CAP) on Rural Economies	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/216672	FP7	FP7-SSH	1,881,354.00			ALMA MATER STUDIUM UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	Italy
21	VOLANTE	Visions Of LAND use Transitions in Europe	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/265104	FP7	FP7-ENVIRONMENT	9,055,946.60	2010	2015	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	Netherlands
22	RURALJOBS	New Sources of Employment to Promote the Wealth-Generating Capacity of Rural Communities	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/211605	FP7	FP7-KBBE	1,400,173.00	2008	2010	DEBRECENI EGYETEM	Hungary

D7.1 | Themes of interest to Horizon EU programming on rural/social

23	SEAMLESS	System for Environmental and Agricultural Modelling; Linking European Science and Society	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/10036	FP6	Integrated Project	15,553,272.00	2005	2009	WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT	Netherlands
24	TERESA	Types of interaction between economy, rural society, environment and agricultural activities in European regions	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44400	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,006,000.00	2007	2009	OESTERREICHISCHES INSTITUT FUER RAUMPLANUNG	Austria
25	CC NETWORK	Cross-compliance network	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/22727	FP6	Specific Support Action	300,000.00	2005	2007	INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY	United Kingdom
26	MEACAP	Impact of Environmental Agreements of the CAP	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/503604	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,940,640.00	2004	2007	INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY	United Kingdom
27	CARERA	The Impact of CAP Reform on the Employment Levels in Rural Areas	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/22653	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,499,900.00	2006	2008	ARISTOTLE UNIVERSITY OF THESSALONIKI	Greece
28	FOODIMA	EU food industry dynamics and methodological advances	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44283	FP6	Specific Targeted Research Project	1,046,133.00	2007	2010	ARISTOTLE UNIVERSITY OF THESSALONIKI	Greece

Annex 3: Research projects' details

FP6 PROJECTS

CORASON

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/rural diversity; Social capital, social processes, social networks and social innovation

Coordinator

TRINITY COLLEGE DUBLIN

Full name

A Cognitive approach to rural sustainable development the dynamics of expert and lay knowledges

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

1,131,033.00

Start/End

2004-2007

Participants

1. GOETEBORGS UNIVERSITET (SWEDEN).
2. HUNGARIAN ACADEMY SCIENCES (HUNGARY)
3. UNIVERSITAT DE VALENCIA (SPAIN)
4. JAGIELLONIAN UNIVERSITY (POLAND)
5. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI NAPOLI FEDERICO II. (ITALY)
6. AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS. (GREECE)
7. UNIVERSIDADE TECNICA DE LISBOA (Portugal)
8. UNIVERSITY COURT OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN (United Kingdom)
9. CENTRE FOR RURAL RESEARCH (Norway)
10. LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTS- UND LANDNUTZUNGSFORSCHUNG E.V. (Germany)
11. CESKA ZEMEDELSKA UNIVERZITA V PRAZE (Czechia)
12. UNIVERSITY OF NEWCASTLE UPON TYNE (United Kingdom)

Main objective

The CORASON project studied knowledge and knowledge use in European rural sustainable development. Its objective was to identify and explain the dynamics of the variety of knowledge forms (expert and lay, ranging from the scientific, economic, administrative, and managerial to local, practical, and ecological knowledge, traditional repertoires, trial and error or experientially-based discoveries) used in rural projects in relation to rural economic development, rural civil society and the protection of rural nature.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/79248/reporting/en>

Publications

not found

GLOCHAMORE**Addressed topics**

Rural and climate; Innovation policies and innovation ecosystems for rural; Rural and biodiversity

Coordinator

UNIVERSITÄT WIEN

Full name

Global Change in Mountain Regions: An Integrated Assessment of Causes and Consequences

Funding Scheme

SSA - Specific Support Action

Overall budget

448,265.00

Start/End

2003-2005

Participants

1. CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE (FRANCE)
2. CENTRE NATIONAL DU MACHINISME AGRICOLE, DU GÉNIE RURAL, DES EAUX ET DES FORÊTS (FRANCE)
3. EIDGENÖSSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZÜRICH (SWITZERLAND)
4. JAWAHARLAL NEHRU UNIVERSITY (INDIA)
5. PERTH COLLEGE (UK)
6. POTSDAM INSTITUTE FOR CLIMATE IMPACT RESEARCH (GERMANY)
7. TECHNOLOGICAL AND EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTE OF LAMIA (GREECE)
8. UNITED NATIONS EDUCATIONAL, SCIENTIFIC AND CULTURAL ORGANIZATION (FRANCE)
9. UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT (NETHERLANDS)
10. UNIVERSITY OF ZURICH (SWITZERLAND)
11. UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI-L'AQUILA' (ITALY)
12. UNIVERSITÄT BASEL (SWITZERLAND)
13. UNIVERSITÉ JOSEPH FOURIER GRENOBLE 1 (FRANCE)

Main objective

Many of the world's mountain ecosystems are moving along trajectories that couple high rates of environmental change with strong economic changes, whose collective effect may alter the ability of mountain regions to provide critical goods and services, both to mountain inhabitants and lowland communities. In order to address the environmental challenges facing the world's mountain regions in the 21st Century, we will develop an integrative research strategy for detecting signals of global environmental change in mountain environments, for defining the consequences of these changes for mountain regions as well as lowland areas dependent on mountain resources, and for facilitating the development of sustainable resource management regimes for mountain regions. Following a kick-off meeting, the details of the research strategy will be formulated through a series of product-oriented workshops dedicated to:

1. Long-term Monitoring,
2. Integrated Modelling,
3. Process Studies, and
4. Sustainable Development

The concepts developed in these Thematic Workshops will be revisited, refined and synthesised during a final Open Science Conference on Global Change in Mountain Regions. By gearing the research strategy toward implementation in mountain Biosphere Reserves, the project will take advantage of the existing UNESCO infrastructure and ongoing Global Change research in these areas. The structure of UNESCO mountain Biosphere Reserves provides ideal natural Global Change laboratories with core protected mountainous areas surrounded by lower-elevation buffer zones that are more strongly influenced by human activities. Adapting the research strategy for implementation in UNESCO's mountain Biosphere Reserves in both developed and developing countries will promote European scientific participation, capacity building and leadership. This will be achieved through the active participation of Biosphere Reserve managers in the development of the research strategy.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/74304/factsheet/en>

Publications

not found

Results and recommendations

not found

RURAL WINGS

Addressed topics

Well-being, quality of life; Social capital, social processes, social networks; Innovation policies; Rural labour; Rural and digital

Coordinator

INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS

Full name

not found

Funding Scheme

IP - Integrated Project

Overall budget

8,826,736.00

Start/End

2006-2009

Participants

1. ALFA-OMEGA COMMUNICATIONS LTD. (ESTONIA).
2. AVANTI COMMUNICATIONS LTD (UK)
3. BEN-GURION UNIVERSITY OF THE NEGEV (ISRAEL)
4. DBC GMBH (SWITZERLAND)

5. EADS ASTRIUM SAS (FRANCE)
6. ELLINOGERMANIKI AGOGI S.A. (GREECE)
7. EUROPEAN DISTANCE AND E-LEARNING NETWORK (UK)
8. EUROPEAN RESUSCITATION COUNCIL (BELGIUM)
9. EUTELSAT S.A. (FRANCE)
10. FOUNDATION FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY – HELLAS (GREECE)
11. FOURIER SYSTEMS (1989) LTD. (ISRAEL)
12. HELLAS SAT CONSORTIUM LTD. (CYPRUS)
13. HELLENIC TELECOMMUNICATIONS AND TELEMATICS APPLICATIONS COMPANY (GREECE)
14. INSTITUT EUROPEEN D'ADMINISTRATION DES AFFAIRES (FRANCE)
15. INTERNATIONAL ENVIRONMENT AND QUALITY SERVICES S.A. (GREECE)
16. IVANE JAVAKHISHVILI TBILISI STATE UNIVERSITY (GEORGIA)
17. PROGRESS AND BUSINESS FOUNDATION (POLAND)
18. STATE ENGINEERING UNIVERSITY OF ARMENIA (ARMENIA)
19. STOCKHOLM UNIVERSITY (SWEDEN)
20. TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT DRESDEN (GERMANY)
21. TELEMEDICINE TECHNOLOGIES S.A. (FRANCE)
22. UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA (SPAIN)
23. UNIVERSITATEA "POLITEHNICA" DIN BUCURESTI (ROMANIA)
24. UNIVERSITY OF AEGEAN (GREECE)

Main objective

The main aim of the proposed approach is to support the creation of a new culture in rural communities promoting digital literacy and reducing resistance to the use of new technologies. It will go a step further, encouraging users to add their significant contribution to the emerging applications by involving them in meaningful activities, tailored to address the needs of different user groups.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/80103/factsheet/en>

Publications

not found

TWISTER

Addressed topics

Rural and digital; Innovation policies; Well-being, quality of life; Social capital/ processes/ networks/ innovation

Coordinator

EADS ASTRIUM SAS

Full name

Terrestrial Wireless Infrastructure integrated with Satellite Telecommunications for E-Rural applications

Funding Scheme

IP - Integrated Project

Overall budget

6,828,502.00

Start/End

2004-2007

Participants

1. EUTELSAT S.A (FRANCE)
2. CENTRE NATIONAL D'ETUDES SPATIALES (FRANCE)
3. CENTRE NATIONAL DU MACHINISME AGRICOLE, DU GENIE RURAL, DES EAUX ET DES FORETS (FRANCE)
4. POLITECHNIKA WARSZAWSKA (POLAND)
5. UNIVERSITY OF MALTA (MALTA)
6. DIPUTACION PROVINCIAL DE ZARAGOZA (SPAIN)
7. ANETO (FRANCE)
8. FOUNDATION FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS (GREECE)
9. PICOPOINT B.V (NETHERLANDS)
10. ANSUR TECHNOLOGIES AS (NORWAY)
11. OURANOS NETWORKS SA (BELGIUM)
12. MARRATECH SYSTÈMES (FRANCE) SARL (FRANCE)

Main objective

The objective of TWISTER is to support the development and widespread adoption of satellite communication services to deliver broadband services for rural areas. TWISTER will provide innovative applications meeting the specific needs of rural user communities including local administrations, educational institutions, health care practitioners, Sees and agricultural communities.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/72828/factsheet/en>

Publications

not found

RAPIDO

Addressed topics

Characterizing rural; Rural labour; Innovation policies; Policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

ECOLOGIC - INSTITUTE FOR INTERNATIONAL AND EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY

Full name

Rural areas, people and innovative development

Funding Scheme

SSA - Specific Support Action

Overall budget

350,200.00

Start/End

2007-2009

Participants

1. FONDAZIONE ENI ENRICO MATTEI (ITALY)
2. FÖRDERGEMEINSCHAFT NACHHALTIGE LANDWIRTSCHAFT E.V. (ASSOCIATION FOR THE PROMOTION OF SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE) (GERMANY)
3. UNIVERSITY OF TRÁS-OS-MONTES E ALTO DOURO (PORTUGAL)

4. JOANNEUM RESEARCH FORSCHUNGSGESELLSCHAFT MBH (AUSTRIA)
5. LUBLIN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY (POLAND)
6. ENVIRONMENTAL FUTURES LTD. (UK)
UNIVERSITY OF NATIONAL AND WORLD ECONOMY (BULGARIA)
7. UNIVERSITY OF CRAIOVA (ROMANIA)
8. VERBAND DER LANDWIRTSCHAFTSKAMMERN E.V. (GERMAN CHAMBERS OF AGRICULTURE)
(GERMANY)
9. UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA (ESTUDI GENERAL) (SPAIN)

Main objective

RAPIDO aims to facilitate innovation and knowledge transfer in rural areas in Europe with a special focus on agriculture, forestry and food industry.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/84088/reporting/en>

Publications

not found

C@R

Addressed topics

Rural & digital; Rural & labor; Smart villages

Coordinator

TECNOLOGIAS Y SERVICIOS AGRARIOS SA

Full name

Collaboration@Rural: A collaborative platform for working and living in rural areas

Funding Scheme

IP - Integrated Project

Overall budget

14,955,657.00

Start/End

2006-2009

Participants

1. ARSLOGICA SRL (ITALY)
2. ATOS ORIGIN SOCIEDAD ANONIMA ESPANOLA (SPAIN)
3. BEIJING SOFTWARE ENTERPRISE ADVISORY CENTER (CHINA)
4. CITYPASSENGER SA (FRANCE)
5. EFITA (UNITED KINGDOM)
6. EMPRESA DE TRANSFORMACION AGRARIA SA (SPAIN)
7. EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY (FRANCE)
8. FOOD AND AGRICULTURE ORGANISATION OF THE UNITED NATIONS FAO (ITALY)
9. FRAUNHOFER IAF (GERMANY)
10. FUNDACAO CPQD CENTRO DE PESQUISA E DESENVOLVIMENTO EM TELECOMUNICACOES
(BRAZIL)
11. GEOSPATIAL PARTNERS S.R.L. (ITALY)

12. GILAT SATELLITE NETWORKS LTD (ISRAEL)
13. HELSINGIN KAUPPAKORKEAKOULU (FINLAND)
14. LOQUENDO SPA (ITALY)
15. NOKIA OYJ (FINLAND)
16. PHILIPS INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS NV (BELGIUM)
17. REGION ABOLAND R.F. (FINLAND)
18. SAP AG (GERMANY)
19. SIEMENS SA (SPAIN)
20. SZEGEDI TUDOMANYEGYETEM (HUNGARY)
21. TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET GRAZ (AUSTRIA)
22. TELEFONICA INVESTIGACION Y DESARROLLO SA UNIPERSONAL (SPAIN)
23. TELEFONICA PESQUISA E DESENVOLVIMENTO DO BRASIL LTDA (BRAZIL)
24. UNIVERSIDAD DEL PAIS VASCO/EUSKAL HERRIKO UNIBERTSITATEA (SPAIN)
25. UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID (SPAIN)
26. UNIWERSYTET IM. ADAMA MICKIEWICZA W POZNANIU (POLAND)
27. WIRELESSINFO (CZECHIA)
28. ZENON S.A. ROBOTICS AND INFORMATICS (GREECE)

Main objective

C@R aims to boost the introduction of Collaborative Working Environments (CWE) as key enablers catalyzing rural development. According to this strategic goal, C@R proposes a complete set of research activities and tasks which will identify, develop and validate technological responses to actual barriers jeopardizing the sustainable development in rural areas.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/80466/factsheet/en>

<http://www.c-rural.eu/>

Publications

not found

ACARI
Addressed topics
Rural labour

Coordinator

INSTITUTE FOR TRANSPORT STUDIES UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS

Full

Accident causation at rural intersections: influential safety critical factors and processes

name

Funding

EIF - Marie Curie actions-Intra-European Fellowships

Scheme

Overall

not found

budget

Start/End

2005-2006

Participants

not found

Main

The aim of the proposed project is to identify and quantify safety critical factors and processes specific to the rural environment from a traffic systems perspective (human, vehicle, and roadway environment)

objective**Website**

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/25686>

Publications

not found

A-BARD

Addressed topics

social capital-processes-networks-innovation; rural and digital; territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

THE NATIONAL MICROELECTRONICS APPLICATIONS CENTRE LTD

Full name

Analysing Broadband Access for Rural Development

Funding Scheme

CA - Coordination action

Overall budget

€ 629 100

Start/End

2005-2006

Participants

1. CESKE CENTRUM PRO STRATEGICKA STUDIA (CZECHIA)
2. CYBERMOOR LTD (UNITED KINGDOM)
3. INSTYTUT TECHNIK TELEKOMUNIKACYJNYCH I INFORMATYCZNYCH SP. Z O.O. (POLAND)
4. MANAGING INNOVATION STRATEGIES, S.L.L. (SPAIN)
5. NORTH WEST LABS. LIMITED (IRELAND)
6. POWER LAKE AKTIEBOLAG (SWEDEN)

Main objective

Analysing Broadband Access for Rural Development (A-BARD) is a Coordination Action to research rural broadband provision and use. ABARD will both identify views on the issues and barriers to widespread broadband provision and the extent to which broadband can act as an external driver of change in rural economies.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/513697>

Publications

not found

MEDRES

Addressed topics

Rural and climate

Coordinator

OBSERVATOIRE MEDITERRANEEN DE L'ENERGIE

Full name

Cost-effective renewable energy for rural and peri urban areas in the Mediterranean region”

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

2,015,182.00

Starts/Ends

2007-2009

Participants

1. ENEA - RICHERCA SUL SYSTEMA ELETTRICO S.P.A. (ITALY)
2. EUROPEAN INSTITUTE FOR ENERGY RESEARCH (GERMANY)
3. AGENCE NATIONALE POUR LA MAÎTRISE DE L'ENERGIE (TUNISIA)
4. Agence de l'environnement et de la Maitrise de l'energie (FRANCE)
5. CENTRE DE RECHERCHE ET DE DÉVELOPPEMENT DE L'ELECTRICITÉ ET DU GAZ (ALGERIA)
6. Centre de Développement des Energies Renouvelables (MOROCCO)
7. ELECTRICIENS SANS FRONTIÈRES (FRANCE)
8. Electricité de France (FRANCE)
9. FRAUNHOFER-GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FÖRDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V. (GERMANY)
10. Fundacion Labein (SPAIN)
11. Institut fuer Angewandte Forschung und Zusammenarbeit mit den Mena-Laendern EV (GERMANY)
12. National Research Centre (EGYPT)
13. New and Renewable Energy Authority (EGYPT)
14. SMA Technologie AG (GERMANY)
15. SOCIÉTÉ ALGERIENNE DE L' ÉLECTRICITÉ ET DU GAZ (ALGERIA)
16. Société Tunisienne de l'electricité et du Gaz (Tunisia) 17. Universitaet Kassel (GERMANY)

Main objective

The objectives of the MEDRES research are to assess the opportunities for cost-effective renewable energies (RE) for rural areas and villages, the real effectiveness of new technologies through better knowledge of end user acceptability for energy efficient technologies and practices and to measure the impact of electrification on socio-economic development in rural areas.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/32020>

Publications

not found

TOP-MARD

Addressed topics

Well-being, quality of life; innovation policies; policy performance

Coordinator

UHI MILLENNIUM INSTITUTE

Full name:

Towards a Policy Model of Multifunctional Agriculture and Rural Development [TOP-MARD]

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

2,495,080.00

Start/End

2005-2008

Participants

1. AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS (Greece)
2. INSTITUTE FOR RURAL DEVELOPMENT RESEARCH AT GOETHE UNIVERSITY FRANKFURT
- 3 . BUNDESANSTALT FUER BERGBAUERNFRAGEN (Austria)
4. FUNDACIO EMPRESA I CIENCIA - UNIVERSITAT AUTÒNOMA DE BARCELONA (Spain)
5. TEAGASC (Ireland)
6. DIPARTIMENTO DI ECONOMIA PUBBLICA, UNIVERSITA DI ROMA "LA SAPIENZA" (Italy)
7. NORDIC CENTRE FOR SPATIAL DEVELOPMENT (Sweden)
8. NORWEGIAN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS RESEARCH INSTITIUTE (Norway)
9. BIOTECHNICAL FACULTY OF THE UNIVERSITY OF LJUBLJANA (Slovenia)
10. BUDAPESTI CORVINUS EGYETEM (Hungary)
11. THE UNIVERSITY COURT OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN (UK)

Main objective

The aim of the TOP-MARD project was to build a policy model of multifunctional agriculture and rural development which would link the multiple functions of agriculture with the development and quality of life of rural regions, and explore the influence of different policies on rural development outcomes.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/501749/reporting>

Publications

not found

LUMOCAP

Addressed topics

Rural and biodiversity

Coordinator

RESEARCH INSTITUUT VOOR KENNISSYSTEMEN

Full name

Dynamic land use change modelling for CAP impact assessment on the rural landscape”

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

1,293,040.00

Start/End

2005-2008

Participants

1. KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN (Belgium)
2. INSTYTUT UPRAWY NAWOZENIA I GLEBOZNAWSTWA (INSTITUTE OF SOIL SCIENCE AND PLANT CULTIVATION) (Poland)
3. EUROPEAN COMMISSION, GENERAL DIRECTORATE JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE (Italy)

Main objective

LUMOCAP aims at delivering an operational tool for assessing land use changes and their impact on the rural landscape related to the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). The core of the system is a dynamic Cellular Automata based land use model enabling the user to enter policy options under a specific set of natural and socio-economic conditions as external driving forces, to formulate potential land use scenarios, and to assess their impact on the quality of rural landscapes through the analysis of selected landscape indicators.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/6556/reporting/es>

Publications

not found

RURAL ETINET

Adressed topics

Rural labour/jobs

Coordinator

BETA TECHNOLOGY LTD

Full name

Economic and technological intelligence project to facilitate SMEs in rural areas to participate in the Sixth Framework Programme

Funding Scheme

NoE - Network of Excellence

Overall budget

979,453.00

Start/End

2003-2006

Participants

1. ÖSTERREICHISCHE FORSCHUNGSFÖRDERUNGSGESELLSCHAFT MBH (Austria)
2. AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA (Italy)

3. THE SWEDISH EU R&D COUNCIL (Sweden)
4. TÜRKIYE BILIMSEL VE TEKNİK ARASTIRMA KURUMU (Turkey)
5. UNIVERSITY OF NATIONAL AND WORLD ECONOMY (Bulgaria)
6. RTD TALOS LIMITED (Cyprus)
7. FOOD INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT COMPANY SA (Greece)
8. RANNSOKNAMIDSTOD ISLANDS (THE ICELANDIC CENTER FOR RESEARCH) (Iceland)
9. SC TEMAGON ROMANIA S.R.L. (Romania)
10. INSTITUTE OF LANDSCAPE ECOLOGY OF THE SLOVAK ACADEMY OF SCIENCES (Slovakia)
11. SC F.M. MANAGEMENT CONSULTANCY S.L.R. (Romania)
12. SWEDIWH GOVERNMENT AGENCY FOR INNOVATION SYSTEMS (Sweden)
13. FOUNDATION FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS. (Greece)

Main objective

Activities under this specific programme will focus on improving the knowledge and capabilities of the different actors involved. Actors, such as researchers, industrialists, investors, public authorities at European, national and regional levels, will be encouraged to interact more closely by providing strategic information and services and by developing new methodologies and tools to assist them in their particular undertakings.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/508500>

Publications

not found

AMI-NETFOOD

Addressed topics

Rural and digital; innovation policies

Coordinator

INNOPOLE, S.L.

Full name

Development of long-term shared vision on AMI technologies for a Networked agri-food sector

Funding Scheme

SSA - Specific Support Action

Overall budget

937,336.00

Start/End

2005-2006

Participants

1. ARA ARASTIRMA TANITIM DANISMANLIK VE TEMSILCILIK LIMITED (Turkey)
2. CATT INNOVATION MANAGEMENT GMBH (Austria)
3. CYBELIA (France)
4. DEMOCENTER-SIPE CENTRO SERVIZI PER L'INNOVAZIONE E IL TRASFERIMENTO TECNOLOGICO SOCIETA CONSORTILE A RESPONSABILITA LIMITATA (Italy)
5. EXODUS A.E. (Greece)

6. INESC PORTO - INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES DO PORTO (Portugal)
7. INSTITUT FUER ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMTECHNIK BREMEN GMBH (Germany)
8. MAGYAR AGRARINFORMATIKAI SZOVETSEG (Hungary)
9. NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND – GALWAY (Ireland)
10. NYHERJI HF (Iceland)
11. POLITECHNIKA RZESZOWSKA IM. IGNACEGO AUKASIEWICZA (Poland)
12. TAMPEREEN YLIOPISTO (Finland)
13. WIRELESSINFO (Czechia)

Main objective

The objective of AMI@netfood project is to support the implementation of the IST Research Priority and Framework Programme, providing a long-term vision on future trends on Scientific and Technology Research oriented to the development and application of Ambient Intelligence technologies to the agrifood domain.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/015776>

Publications

not found

ADHOCSYS

Addressed topics

Rural labour

Coordinator

EMISFERA SOCIETA COOPERATIVA

Full name

Development of long-term shared vision on AMI technologies for a Networked agri-food sector

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

2,403,100.00

Start/End

2005-2007

Participants

1. ASOCIACION DE EMPRESAS TECNOLOGICAS INNOVALIA (Spain)
2. HAL SERVICE S.R.L. (Italy)
3. HEWLETT PACKARD ITALIANA SRL (Italy) 4. HIGH TECH S.R.L. (Italy)
5. POLITECNICO DI TORINO
6. TEKEVER - TECNOLOGIAS DE INFORMACAO, S.A. (Portugal)
7. UNIVERSITETSSTUDIENE PA KJELLER (Norway)
8. UNIVERSITY OF PATRAS (Greece)

Main objective

The project's goal is the provision of broadband fixed wireless access, based on the Ad-Hoc model, i.e. with peer devices co-operating for building and maintaining a reliable and flexible network. This network allows for providing broadband services to rural and mountain regions, and could also be used as a complete monitoring system, i.e. a network of devices which obtain in real time physical and multimedia information about a geographic area.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/026548>

Publications

not found

BROADWAN**Addressed topics**

Rural and digital; smart villages; innovation policies

Coordinator

TELENOR ASA

Full name

Broadband services for everyone over fixed wireless access networks

Funding Scheme

IP - Integrated Project

Overall budget

13,814,903.00

Start/End

2003-2006

Participants

1. ALCATEL CIT (France)
2. ALCATEL THALES III V LAB (France)
3. ALVARION LTD. (Israel)
4. APIF MOVIQUITY S.A. (Spain)
5. ASOCIACION DE EMPRESAS DE ELECTRONICA, TECNOLOGIAS DE LA INFORMACION Y TELECOMUNICACIONES DE ESPANA (Spain)
6. BUDAPESTI MUSZAKI ES GAZDASAGTUDOMANYI EGYETEM (Hungary)
7. CARDIFF UNIVERSITY (UK)
8. CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE (France)
9. CORITEL - CONSORZIO DI RICERCA SULLE TELECOMUNICAZIONI (Italy)
10. COUNCIL FOR THE CENTRAL LABORATORY OF THE RESEARCH COUNCILS (UK)
11. INFOGLOBAL CLM S.A. (Spain)
12. INSTITUT DE L'AUDIOVISUEL ET DES TELECOMMUNICATIONS EN EUROPE – IDATE (France)
13. JOANNEUM RESEARCH FORSCHUNGSGESELLSCHAFT MBH (Austria)
14. NAVUS GESELLSCHAFT FUER SOFTWARE-ENTWICKLUNG UND -VERTRIEB MBH (Germany)
15. NERA NETWORKS AS (Norway)
16. T-SYSTEMS RIC RESEARCH LTD. (Hungary)
17. TECNOLOGIE UNI.COM CENTRO RICERCHE TELECOMUNICAZIONI S.R.L. (Italy)

18. TELECOM CASTILLA LA MANCHA S.A. (Spain)
19. TELECOMS CONNECT LIMITED (UK)
20. THALES COMMUNICATIONS S.A. (France)
21. THALES RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY (UK) LIMITED
22. THE UNIVERSITY OF BUCKINGHAM (UK)
23. THOMSON R & D FRANCE SNC (France)
24. UNIVERSITAET SALZBURG (Austria)
25. UNIVERSITATEA TEHNICA CLUJ-NAPOCA (Romania)
26. UNIVERSITE DE LIMOGES (France)

Main objective

BROADWAN has three major goals:

- Develop an economical realistic network architecture to provide true broadband services for all citizens in Europe.
- Bring European industry in the lead for next generation wireless solutions.
- Motivate advanced utilisation of broadband services at all levels of the society by performing wireless demonstrations and trials in rural areas.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/001930>

Publications

not found

MOSAIC
Addressed topics
Rural and digital ; innovation policies

Coordinator:

STICHTING TELEMATICA INSTITUUT

Full name

Mobile worker support environments: Aligning innovation in mobile technologies, applications and workplaces for location-independent cooperation and networking

Funding Scheme

SSA - Specific Support Action

Overall budget

1,244,679.00

Start/Ends

2004-2005

Participants

1. APIF MOVIQUITY S.A. (Spain)
2. BAE SYSTEMS (OPERATIONS) LIMITED (UK)
3. CAS SOFTWARE AG (Germany)
4. ESOCE NET (EUROPEAN SOCIETY OF CONCURRENT ENGINEERING) (Italy)
5. EUCONNECT LTD (UK)
6. FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V.

(Germany)

7. ITTI SP. Z O.O. (Poland)
8. KINGSTON UNIVERSITY (UK)
9. NOKIA OYJ (Finland)
10. OULUN YLIOPISTO (Finland)
11. TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT (Netherlands)
12. TELECOM ITALIA LEARNING SERVICES S.P.A. (Italy)
13. THE UNIVERSITY OF SALFORD (UK)
14. UNIVERSITAT ST GALLEN (Switzerland)
15. UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE (Netherlands)
16. VALTION TEKNILLINEN TUTKIMUSKESKUS (Finland)

Main objective

MOSAIC explores business and societal innovation and prepares Europe for deploying innovative mobile technology in a range of application domains, to support mobile workers in distributed and location-sensitive settings. It focuses on mobile working in three key domains: Healthcare&Wellbeing, Life-Cycle Management sectors (Building Construction, Manufacturing) and Rural and Regional Work Environments.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/004341>

Publications

not found

SEAMLESS

Addressed topics

Policy performance ; innovation policies

Coordinator

WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT

Full name

System for Environmental and Agricultural Modelling; Linking European Science and Society

Funding Scheme

IP - Integrated Project

Overall budget

15,553,272.00

Start/End

2005-2009

Participants:

1. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE (INRA) (France)
2. CENTRE DE COOPERATION INTERNATIONALE EN RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE POUR LE DEVELOPPEMENT (France)
3. HUMBOLDT UNIVERSITAET ZU BERLIN (Germany)

4. LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG (ZALF) E.V. (Germany)
5. CONSIGLIO PER LA RICERCA E SPERIMENTAZIONE IN AGRICOLTURA (Italy)
6. COMMISSION OF THE EUROPEAN COMMUNITIES - DIRECTORATE GENERAL JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE (Belgium)
7. UNIVERSITETET FOR MILJO OG BIOVITENSKAP (Norway)
8. LUNDS UNIVERSITET (Sweden)
9. SCUOLA UNIVERSITARIA PROFESSIONALE DELLA SVIZZERA ITALIANA (SUPSI) (Switzerland)
10. PLANT RESEARCH INTERNATIONAL B.V. (Netherlands)
11. LANDBOUW-ECONOMISCH INSTITUUT B.V. (Netherlands)
12. ALTERRA B.V. (Netherlands)
13. UNIVERSITY OF NEWCASTLE UPON TYNE (UK)
14. SZKOLA GLOWNA GOSPODARSTWA WIEJSKIEGO (Poland)
15. USTAV SYSTE MOVE BIOLOGIE A EKOLOGIE AV CR VEREJNA VYZKUMNA INSTITUTE – USBE (Czechia)
16. RESEARCH INSTITUTE FOR AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS (Czechia)
17. LUND UNIVERSITY EDUCATION AB (Sweden)
18. SIMULISTICS LIMITED (UK)
19. RHEINISCHE FRIEDRICH-WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAET BONN (Germany)
20. CENTER FOR SKOV, LANDSKAB OG PLANRHININ, KVL (Denmark)
21. CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE HAUTES ETUDES AGRONOMIQUES MEDITERRANEENNES (France)
22. UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA. (Portugal)
23. NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, GALWAY (Ireland)
24. ANTOPTIMA SA (Switzerland)
25. INSTITUT D'ECONOMIE RURALE (Mali)
26. UNIVERSITY OF VERMONT (USA)
27. CENTRE NATIONAL DU MACHINISME AGRICOLE, DU GENIE RURAL, DES EAUX ET DES FORETS (France)
28. UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN (UK)
29. THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH (UK)
30. KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET (Denmark)

Main objective

The project will develop an integrated framework (SEAMLESS-IF) which integrates approaches from economic, environmental and social sciences to enable assessment of the impact of policy and behavioural changes and innovations in agriculture and agroforestry. Contributions of agriculture to sustainable development and multifunctionality will be assessed at different spatial scales from farm to global, allowing consideration of both top-down and bottom-up approaches to land management change.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/10036>

Publications

not found

RES-Integration

Addressed topics

Rural and biodiversity

Coordinator

AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS

Full name

Rural sustainable development through integration of renewable energy technologies in poor European regions

Funding Scheme

STIP - Specific Targeted Innovation Project

Overall budget

1,150,000.00

Start/Ends

2004-2007

Participants

1. ETA ENERGIA TRASPORTI AGRICOLTURA S.R.L. (Italy)
2. MASLNSKI FAKULTET - KRAGUJEVAC (FACULTY OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING – KRAGUJEVAC)
3. ZDRUZENIE NA GEOTERMIAARI NA MAKEDONIJA - MAGA (MACEDONIAN GEOTHERMAL ASSOCIATION – MAGA)
4. POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY OF TIRANA (UNIVERSITETI POLITEKNIK, UPT) (Albania)
5. WIP – KG (Germany)

Main objective

The ultimate goal of the present project is to study the implementation of innovative low cost Renewable Energy and Energy Saving Technologies at selected poor regions of the participating countries. Locally available Energy Resources will be used, with a final goal the regional sustainable socio-economic development. Pathways will be invented for maximising Renewable Energy penetration in the region. Ideally, 100 % renewable energy penetration will be pursued for.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/509204>

Publications

not found

SEACASE

Addressed topics

Rural labour; social capital ; rural values and income

Coordinator:

CENTRO DE CIENCIAS DO MAR DO ALGARVE

Full name

Sustainable extensive and semi-intensive coastal aquaculture in Southern Europe

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

2,415,002.00

Start/End

2007-2010

Participants:

1. AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS (Spain)
2. INSTITUT FRANÇAIS DE RECHERCHE POUR L'EXPLOITATION DE LA MER (France)
3. CENTRE RÉGIONAL D'EXPÉRIMENTATION ET D'APPLICATION AQUACOLE (France)
4. SYNDICAT MIXTE "FORUM DES MARAIS ATLANTIQUES" (France)
5. UNIVERSITE DE BRETAGNE OCCIDENTALE (France)
6. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA 'TOR VERGATA' (Italy)
7. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA (Italy)
8. HELLENIC CENTER FOR MARINE RESEARCH (Greece)
9. UNIVERSITY OF CRETE (Greece)
10. INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE RECURSOS BIOLÓGICOS, IP/IPIMAR (Portugal)
11. INSTITUTO SUPERIORE PER LA PROTEZIONE E LA RICERCA AMBIENTE (Italy)

Main objective

Traditional extensive coastal and semi-intensive aquaculture systems in Southern Europe are facing difficulties, especially due to increased competition for coastal areas by other candidate users and market competition, due to low-price products from intensive aquaculture.

The positive effects of extensive and semi-intensive aquaculture in coastal areas - including environmental protection and restoration in areas of particular ecological interest, employment opportunity and development in rural and coastal areas - have been clearly recognised within EU policy.

The final goal of the SEACASE project is to develop effective tools for maintenance of competitiveness, productivity, profitability and thus sustainability of extensive and semi-intensive aquaculture production in Southern Europe, while minimizing its environmental impacts and improving the quality and public image of its products.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44483>

Publications: not found

TERESA

Addressed topics

Territorial approaches and policies / Policy performance evaluation / Characterizing rural - rural diversity

Coordinator

OESTERREICHISCHES INSTITUT FUER RAUMPLANUNG

Full name

Types of interaction between economy, rural society, environment and agricultural activities in European regions

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

1,006,000.00

Start/End

2007-2009

Participants

1. NORWEGIAN INSTITUTE FOR URBAN AND REGIONAL RESEARCH (Norway)
2. UNIVERSITY OF SUSSEX (UK)
3. SERVICE D'UTILITÉ AGRICOLE À COMPÉTENCES INTERDÉPARTEMENTALES MONTAGNE ALPES DU NORD (France)
4. HUMBOLDT UNIVERSITY OF BERLIN (Germany)
5. STANISLAW LESZCZYCKI INSTITUTE OF GEOGRAPHY AND SPATIAL ORGANISATION POLISH ACADEMY OF SCIENCES (Poland)
6. FUNDACIO EMPRESA I CIENCIA - UNIVERSITAT AUTONOMA DE BARCELONA (Spain)
7. CENTRUL DE ASISTENTA RURALA (Romania)
8. BUNDESANSTALT FUER BERGBAUERNFRAGEN (Austria)
9. ACCADEMIA EUROPEA PER LA RICERCA APPLICATA ED IL PERFEZIONAMENTO PROFESSIONALE BOLZANO (Italy)
10. CORVINUS UNIVERSITY OF BUDAPEST (Hungary)
11. UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK (Ireland)

Main objective

Rural development policy and the new CAP increasingly place agriculture in a wider context taking into account the diversification of rural economy, the quality of the environment and food safety to gain higher competitiveness of the farming sector. Combining expertise in agricultural sciences and regional policies TERESA aims to shed light on these interrelations and the impact of policies on it, focusing on three goals: Goal A - identifying interrelationships in rural areas: to identify typical interrelationships between farming activities, rural economy, rural society and the environment. Goal B - modelling: to develop a model demonstrating the typical interrelations between agriculture, the rest of rural economy and the environment in different types of rural areas in Europe and the impact of policies on its development. Goal C - assessing policies: to identify and to assess different integration policies regarding their effectiveness in generating positive externalities for farming activities and rural development.

Website

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44400>

Publications

not found

MULTAGRI

Addressed topics

Rural and biodiversity

Coordinator

CENTRE NATIONAL DU MACHINISME AGRICOLE, DU GÉNIE RURAL, DES EAUX ET DES FORÊTS

Full name

CAPITALISATION OF RESEARCH RESULTS ON THE MULTIFUNCTIONALITY OF AGRICULTURE AND RURAL AREAS

Funding Scheme

SSA - Specific Support Action

Overall budget

1,000,443.00

Start/End

2004-2005

Participants

1. NORWEGIAN INSTITUTE FOR URBAN AND REGIONAL RESEARCH (Norway)
2. UNIVERSITY OF SUSSEX (UK)
3. SERVICE D'UTILITÉ AGRICOLE À COMPÉTENCES INTERDÉPARTEMENTALES MONTAGNE ALPES DU NORD (France)
4. HUMBOLDT UNIVERSITY OF BERLIN (Germany)
5. STANISLAW LESZCZYCKI INSTITUTE OF GEOGRAPHY AND SPATIAL ORGANISATION POLISH ACADEMY OF SCIENCES (Poland)
6. FUNDACIO EMPRESA I CIENCIA - UNIVERSITAT AUTONOMA DE BARCELONA (Spain)
7. CENTRUL DE ASISTENTA RURALA (Romania)
8. BUNDESANSTALT FUER BERGBAUERNFRAGEN (Austria)
9. ACCADEMIA EUROPEA PER LA RICERCA APPLICATA ED IL PERFEZIONAMENTO PROFESSIONALE BOLZANO (Italy)
10. CORVINUS UNIVERSITY OF BUDAPEST (Hungary)
11. UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK (Ireland)

Main objective

One of the guiding principles of Priority 6.3 Global Change and Ecosystems is to promote scientific research to provide support to the EU Strategy for Sustainable Development. The capitalisation process, in the way that it has been conceived in Multigrain SSA, addresses several aspects directly related with the objectives of this Strategy. The aim of this proposal is to provide a complete overview of the research that has been done, particularly in Europe, in the different aspects related to Multifunctionality of agriculture. The essential approach adopted in this initiative is founded on the premise that for agriculture to be sustainable its multifunctional dimension must be acknowledged and promoted.

Website

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/505297>

Publications

not found

AGRINERGY

Addressed topics

Rural and biodiversity

Coordinator

ECOLOGIC - INSTITUTE FOR INTERNATIONAL AND EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY GGBH

Full name

EU bioenergy policies and their effects on rural areas and agriculture policies

Funding Scheme

SSA - Specific Support Action

Overall budget

294,680.00

Start/End

2007-2008

Participants

1. SZKOLA GLOWNA GOSPODARSTWA WIEJSKIEGO (WARSAW AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY) (Poland)
2. CENTRE FOR EUROPEAN POLICY STUDIES (Belgium)
3. BIOMASSE NORMANDIE (France)
4. ECOLOGIC - INSTITUT FÜR INTERNATIONALE UND EUROPÄISCHE UMWELTPOLITIK GEMEINNÜTZIGE GMBH (Austria)
5. LANDBOUW ECONOMISCH INSTITUUT B.V. (Netherlands)

Main objective

Bioenergies are the all-rounders among the renewables, since only biomass is equally suitable for the generation of electricity and heat and the production of fuels. Currently biomass accounts for about two thirds of renewable energy production in the EU. The agricultural and forestry sectors can make a key tribution to meeting these targets. The aim of SSA is firstly to analyse and understand the socio-eomic, environmental and societal issues of EU bioenergy policies and their effects on future Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), and how they fit into the cept of sustainable rural development. Sedly, the aim is to develop cornerstones for future policy-making fostering the production of large volumes of biomass in agriculture and ensuring sustainable (environmentally friendly and socially acceptable) development of rural areas at the same time. AGRINERGY aims to: " bring together policymakers, decision makers, stakeholders, and scientists of the CAP, the development of rural areas and EU bioenergy policies areas to develop a common language and understanding and to establish a co-operation in order to develop cornerstones for future policy-making fostering the production of large volumes of biomass in agriculture and ensuring sustainable (environmental friendly and social acceptable) development of rural areas at the same time; " discuss future needs and options in order to guarantee a sustainable biomass production for energy production; " analyse and understand the socio-eomic, the environmental and the science-society issues related to bioenergy systems use and the development of future rural areas.

Website

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44437>

Publications

not found

REFORLAN
Addressed topics
Rural and biodiversity
Coordinator
BOURNEMOUTH UNIVERSITY HIGHER EDUCATION CORPORATION
Full name
Restoration of forest landscapes for biodiversity conservation and rural development in the dry lands of Latin America
Funding Scheme
STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project
Overall budget
1,862,979.00
Start/End
2007-2009
Participants
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. PONTIFICIA UNIVERSIDAD CATOLICA DE CHILE (Chile) 2. UNIVERSIDAD AUSTRAL DE CHILE (Chile) 3. UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DEL COMAHUE (Argentina) 4. FUNDACION PROYUNGAS (Argentina) 5. EL COLEGIO DE LA FRONTERA SUR (Mexico) 6. INSTITUTO POLITECNICO NACIONAL (Mexico) 7. INSTITUTO DE ECOLOGIA, A.C. (Mexico) 8. UNIVERSIDAD DE ALCALA (Spain) 9. UNIVERSITA' DEGLI STUDI DI TRENTO (Italy)
Main objective
<p>This project aims to identify and promote approaches for the sustainable management of dryland forest ecosystems, by researching ecosystem restoration techniques using native species of economic value. The project will directly address Thematic Issue A.2.3 Managing arid and semi-arid ecosystems, by undertaking a programme of multi-disciplinary research analysing how restoration of degraded lands can be achieved in a way that will mitigate the effects of unsustainable land use practices and contribute to conservation of biodiversity, in ways that support the development of rural livelihoods according to the ecosystem approach.</p>
Website
1) https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/32132
Publications
not found
RURAL ETINET
Addressed topics
Characterizing rural - rural diversity

Coordinator

THE PROVOST FELLOWS AND SCHOLARS OF THE COLLEGE OF THE HOLY AND UNDIVIDED TRINITY OF QUEEN ELIZABETH NEAR DUBLIN HEREINAFTER TRINITY COLLEGE DUBLIN

Full name

A Cognitive Approach to Rural Sustainable Development the dynamics of expert and lay knowledges

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

1 131 033

Start/End

2004-2007

Participants

1. GOETEBORGS UNIVERSITET. (Sweden)
2. HUNGARIAN ACADEMY SCIENCES (Hungary)
3. UNIVERSITAT DE VALENCIA (Spain)
4. JAGIELLONIAN UNIVERSITY (Poland)
5. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI NAPOLI FEDERICO II. (Italy)
6. AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS. (Greece)
7. UNIVERSIDADE TECNICA DE LISBOA (Portugal)
8. UNIVERSITY COURT OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN (United Kingdom)
9. CENTRE FOR RURAL RESEARCH (Norway)
10. LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTS- UND LANDNUTZUNGSFORSCHUNG E.V. (Germany)
11. CESKA ZEMEDELKA UNIVERZITA V PRAZE (Czechia)
12. UNIVERSITY OF NEWCASTLE UPON TYNE (United Kingdom)

Main objective

The CORASON project studied knowledge and knowledge use in European rural sustainable development. Its objective was to identify and explain the dynamics of the variety of knowledge forms (expert and lay, ranging from the scientific, economic, administrative, and managerial to local, practical, and ecological knowledge, traditional repertoires, trial and error or experientially-based discoveries) used in rural projects in relation to rural economic development, rural civil society and the protection of rural nature.

Website

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/506049>

Publications

not found

COCONUT

Addressed topics

Rural and biodiversity / rural and digital / innovation policies

Coordinator

SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET

Full name

Understanding effects of land use changes on ecosystems to halt loss of biodiversity due to habitat destruction, fragmentation and degradation

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

1 057 051

Start/End

2006-2009

Participants

1. CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION ECOLOGICA Y APLICACIONES FORESTALES (Spain)
2. GISAT S.R.O. (Czechia)
3. HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUER UMWELTFORSCHUNG GMBH – UFZ (Germany)
4. PENSOFT PUBLISHERS (Bulgaria)
5. STOCKHOLMS UNIVERSITET (Sweden)
6. SUOMEN YMPARISTOKESKUS (Finland)
7. TARTU UELIKOOL (Estonia)
8. THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH (United Kingdom)
9. THE UNIVERSITY OF READING. (United Kingdom)
10. UNIVERSITAET BAYREUTH. (Germany)
11. UNIVERSITE CATHOLIQUE DE LOUVAIN (Belgium)

Main objective

To stop biodiversity declines and meet future challenges, a better understanding is needed on how biodiversity is affected by historic and current land use changes.

In the COCONUT project we will:

- (1) Gather existing and new data on both historic and current species richness and land use (GIS) across Europe,
- (2) Synthesise these data and perform meta-analyses to assess the extent of biodiversity loss and to understand how land use change affects biodiversity change,
- (3) Use the results to parameterize predictive models to project future land use and biodiversity change in response to socio-economic scenarios,
- (4) Based on these results develop policy options and decision tools for main EU-policy areas mitigating future biodiversity loss.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44346>

Publications

not found

CC NETWORK

Addressed topics

Policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY

Full name

Cross-compliance network

Funding Scheme

SSA - Specific Support Action

Overall budget

300 000

Start/End

2005-2007

Participants

1. BUNDESFORSCHUNGSANSTALT FUR LANDWIRTSCHAFT, INSTITUT FUR LANDLICHE RAUME (Germany)
2. CLM ONDERZOEK EN ADVIES BV (Netherlands)
3. LITHUANIAN INSTITUTE OF AGRARIAN ECONOMICS (Lithuania)
4. APPLICATIONS DES SCIENCES DE L'ACTION (France)
5. THE UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN (Denmark)
6. AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS (Greece)
7. ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI ECONOMIA AGRARIA (Italy)
8. INSTITUTE FOR STRUCTURAL POLICY (Czechia)
9. JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LANDLICHE RAUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI (Germany)

Main objective

The project had two primary objectives:

1. To bring together stakeholders to discuss research to date on cross compliance in the common agricultural policy (CAP).
2. To identify priority areas for future research to support the development of cross compliance in the CAP and its role in the modernisation and sustainability of agriculture.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/22727>

Publications

not found

FARMING ECONOMICALLY**Addressed topics**

Social capital / rural and climate / rural values and income

Coordinator

WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT

Full name

Farming economically, a new path to sustainable rural development in Galicia, Spain

Funding Scheme

EIF - Marie Curie actions-Intra-European Fellowships

Overall budget

not found

Start/End

2004-2006

Participants

not found

Main objective

The overall objective of this research project was to develop a new approach to sustainable rural development, in which sustainability was not only economically defined but social and ecological aspects were also taken into account. In order to do so, this approach combined a multifunctional concept of agriculture with a multidimensional concept of sustainability. Both were integrated into a multilevel analysis that took into account not only the level of individual farms but also the level of the regions, which together built one agro-ecosystem.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/10680/reporting>

Publications

not found

ETUDE

Addressed topics

Social capital / rural values and income / innovation policies / rural and circular and efficient resource use

Coordinator

WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT

Full name

Enlarging the theoretical understanding of rural development

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

713,229.00

Start/End

2007-2009

Participants

1. INSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE STRUKTURFORSCHUNG AN DER JOHANN WOLFGANG GOETHE UNIVERSITAET FRANKFURT (MAIN) (Germany)

2. UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI PERUGIA (Italy)
3. CARDIFF UNIVERSITY (United Kingdom)
4. MTT AGRIFOOD RESEARCH FINLAND (Finland) 5. BALTIC STUDIES CENTRE (Latvia)

Main objective

The ETUDE project will develop an integrated conceptual framework that goes beyond mono-disciplinary and sectoral approaches and integrates several currently emerging theoretical strands like 1) the 'endogeneity' of rural economies, 2) the capacity of rural areas to produce of 'novelties', 3) the institutional capacity to construct new markets, 4) the capacity to create new 'induced' forms of governance, 5) the development of flexible and cost-efficient forms of sustainability and 6) the role of social capital. The conceptual model will be loaded with appr. 100 completed case-studies and tested in regional case studies in contrasting areas.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44245>

Publications

not found

AG2020

Addressed topics

Innovation policies / rural values and income

Coordinator

DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET (TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF DENMARK)

Full name

Foresight analysis for world agricultural markets (2020) and Europe

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

1,996,146.00

Start/End

2007-2010

Participants

1. UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES OF WEIHENSTEPHAN (Germany)
2. DANISH METEOROLOGICAL INSTITUTE (Denmark)
3. STICHTING DIENST LANDBOUWKUNDIG ONDERZOEK (Netherlands)
4. NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS (Greece)
5. UNIVERSITY OF AARHUS (Denmark)
6. UNIVERSITY OF ANTWERP (Belgium)
7. AGROBIOINSTITUTE (Bulgaria)
8. UNIVERSITA' DEGLI STUDI DI FIRENZE - DIP. DI SCIENZE AGRONOMICHE E GESTIONE DEL TERRITORIO AGROFORESTALE (Italy)
9. METROECONOMICA LIMITED (United Kingdom)
10. INTERNATIONAL FOOD POLICY RESEARCH INSTITUTE (United States)

11. VERENIGING VOOR CHRISTELIJK HOGER ONDERWIJS, WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK EN PATIENTENZORG / VERENIGING VU-WINDESHEIM (Netherlands)
 12. MILIEU- EN NATUURPLANBUREAU (Netherlands)

Main objective

AG2020 will use an innovative scenario method to develop a range of policy scenarios that can meet EU targets of sustainability (economic, regional development, environment, and food safety and quality). Key indicators of these targets will be identified and used to assess the influence of world market developments in a range of policy scenarios both at the global level, and specifically for the EU.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44280>

Publications

not found

MEACAP

Addressed topics

innovation policies / policy performance

Coordinator

INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY

Full name

Impact of Environmental Agreements of the CAP

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

1,940,640.00

Start/End

2004-2007

Participants

1. JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LANDLICHE RAUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI (Germany)
2. DEUTSCHES BIOMASSEFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GMBH (Germany)
3. HUMBOLDT UNIVERSITY OF BERLIN (Germany)
4. ALTERRA B.V. (Netherlands) 5. INSTITUTE OF FOREST ECOSYSTEM RESEARCH, LTD. (Czechia) 6. FONDAZIONE ENI ENRICO MATTEI (Italy) 7. SCOTTISH AGRICULTURAL COLLEGE (United Kingdom) 8. EUROPEAN FOREST INSTITUTE (INTERNATIONAL ORGANISATION) (Finland)

Main objective

The study has four primary objectives. 1. To make an assessment of the exact obligations falling on the Community with respect to agriculture in the fulfillment of commitments under the Kyoto Protocol and the CBD, clarifying how agriculture could contribute relative to other sectors of the economy and land users. 2. To undertake an analysis of the most appropriate adaptations and innovations in the

agricultural sector required to meet the new objectives and obligations. This needs to be achieved within a consistent, methodical framework. It will focus on efficiency, particularly in economic terms, effectiveness, concerning different environmental outcomes and compatibility with other objectives and constraints, at the farm and wider national and EU levels. Interactions between CBD and Kyoto Protocol driven measures need to be exposed and analysed. Account will be taken of a wide range of conditions in Europe, both in existing and new Member States. Afforestation and forest management issues need to be considered alongside agricultural adaptations. 3. An assessment of how far these changes at farm level and upwards require alterations in policy, both at the national and EU levels. Policy change may be needed in the environmental, agricultural, forestry, research, regional support or other policy domains. The main focus will be on agricultural and rural development policies, especially those within the CAP. Specific measures of relevance to Candidate Countries need to be identified.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/503604>

Publications

not found

CARERA

Addressed topics

Rural labour / policy performance

Coordinator

ARISTOTLE UNIVERSITY OF THESSALONIKI

Full name

The Impact of CAP Reform on the Employment Levels in Rural Areas

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

1,499,900.00

Start/End

2006-2008

Participants

1. UNIVERSITY OF CRETE (Greece)
2. UNIVERSITA' DEGLI STUDI DI PARMA (Italy)
3. THE UNIVERSITY OF WALES ABERYSTWYTH (United Kingdom)
4. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT (Netherlands)
5. JUSTUS-LIEBIG-UNIVERSITAET GIESSEN (Germany)
6. CORVINUS UNIVERSITY OF BUDAPEST (Hungary)
7. SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET (Sweden)

Main objective

The proposed project will provide EU policy makers with information, data, indicators, quantitative instruments as well as empirical expertise (synthetic reports, briefing notes, etc.) on the analysis of

structural and employment effects of CAP reform and rural development measures. Specifically, the purpose is to offer detailed information (datasets, economic transactions), to provide an objective assessment on key features of rural areas (employment and income levels) and to deliver tools for simulating the effects of changes on both the CAP and the rural development schemes.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/22653>

Publications

not found

SOFAR

Addressed topics

Vulnerable groups in rural communities

Coordinator

UNIVERSITY OF PISA

Full name

Social Services in Multifunctional Farms - Social Farming

Funding Scheme

SSA - Specific Support Action

Overall budget

537,850.00

Start/End

2006-2009

Participants

1. STICHTING DIENST LANDBOUWKUNDIG ONDERZOEK (Netherlands)
2. RESEARCH INSTITUTE OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE (Germany)
3. GHENT UNIVERSITY (Belgium)
4. UNIVERSITY OF LJUBLJANA (Slovenia)
5. QAP DECISION (France)
6. NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN (Ireland)
7. AGENZIA REGIONALE PER LO SVILUPPO E L'INNOVAZIONE NEL SETTORE AGRICOLO-FORESTALE (Italy)

Main objective

Since ever, agricultural and rural world, all over the European countries, has developed experiences promoting diverse practices and forms of solidarity, social assistance and social inclusion. Particularly we may speak of social farming (or "care farming" or "green care") to describe those farming practices that are aimed to concur towards disadvantaged people's rehabilitation and care and/or towards the integration of those people with "low contractual capacity" (i.e.: psychophysical disabilities, convicts, drug addicts, minors, emigrants). Social farming appears as an evolving, dynamic scenario, which is gaining increasing attention from multiple stakeholders in recent times. On one hand, this results from a new, widespread positive perception of agricultural and rural resources, leading to a crescent interest about the effects of natural spaces and agricultural areas on the social,

physical and psychic well-being of people; health institutions are keen on finding alternative practices, more embedded in the social contexts. On the other hand, social farming represents a new chance for farmers to carry out alternative services, broadening the scope of their activities and their role in society.

Website

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/22682>
- 2) <http://sofar.unipi.it/>

Publications

not found

TERA

Addressed topics

Social capital / rural values and income

Coordinator

UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA

Full name

TERRITORIAL ASPECTS OF ENTERPRISE DEVELOPMENT IN REMOTE RURAL AREAS

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

1,500,000.00

Start/End

2005-2008

Participants

1. THE UNIVERSITY COURT OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN (United Kingdom)
2. HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO (Finland)
3. UNIVERSITY OF PATRAS - RESEARCH COMMITTEE (Greece)
4. LATVIAN STATE INSTITUTE OF AGRARIAN ECONOMICS (Latvia)
5. INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS AND INFORMATION (Czechia)

Main objective

The overall objective of TERA is to identify and analyze the territorial (local and spatial) factors that influence the development of enterprises in remote rural areas of Europe. In more detail, TERA aims at:

- Identifying and analyzing territorial economic factors which influence the creation, development and survival of enterprises in peripheral rural areas of Europe and measuring the nature and degree of the influence of these factors;
- Assessing the extent to which current and recent EU development policies and national and regional development programmes and projects take account of these factors, in the context of, especially, parallel support policies such as CAP direct payments and national social welfare support systems;

- Specifying new policy directions which take account of territorial factors and promote the development of remote rural areas in a more targeted and effective manner.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/6469>

Publications

not found

SCARLED

Addressed topics

Social capital / rural values and income / well-being - quality of life and attractiveness / innovation policies

Coordinator

LEIBNIZ INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE (IAMO)

Full name

Structural change in Agriculture and rural livelihoods

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

809,133.00

Start/End

2007-2010

Participants

1. KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN (Belgium)
2. UNIVERSITY OF NATIONAL AND WORLD ECONOMY (Bulgaria)
3. CORVINUS UNIVERSITY OF BUDAPEST (Hungary)
4. AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS RESEARCH INSTITUTE (Hungary)
5. WARSAW UNIVERSITY DEPARTMENT OF ECONOMIC SCIENCES (Poland)
6. BANAT'S UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES AND VETERINARY MEDICINE TIMISOARA (Romania)
7. UNIVERSITY OF LJUBLJANA (Slovenia)
8. THE UNIVERSITY OF KENT (United Kingdom)
9. UNIVERSITY OF NEWCASTLE UPON TYNE (United Kingdom)

Main objective

The objectives of this project are:

- to analyse the agricultural sector restructuring process and rural socio-economic transformation in the NMS12, with a particular focus on five countries;
- to analyse the patterns behind rural "success stories" in the EU15 during previous enlargements to identify and codify best practices and draw recommendations for the NMS.
- supports policy design by providing policy-makers and the scientific community with scientific single- and cross-country analyses and policy recommendations based on up-to-date information;

- realises objectives of the European Research Area by networking and developing common scientific reference and
- stimulates international co-operation and qualification.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44201>

Publications

not found

CRESMED

Addressed topics

Smart villages

Coordinator

TRAMA TECNOAMBIENTAL S.L.

Full name

Cost efficient and reliable rural electrification schemes for South Mediterranean countries based on multi user Solar Hybrid grids

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

1,800,000.00

Start/End

2006-2009

Participants

1. TRANSENERGIE (France)
2. SASSO S.R.L. (Italy)
3. FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FÖRDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V. (Germany)
4. ASSOCIATION POUR LA RECHERCHE ET LE DÉVELOPPEMENT DES MÉTHODES ET PROCESSUS INDUSTRIELS (France)
5. AGENCE DE L'ENVIRONNEMENT ET DE LA MAÎTRISE DE L'ENERGIE (France)
6. CENTRE DE DÉVELOPPEMENT DES ÉNERGIES RENOUVELABLES DE L'ALGÉRIE' (Algeria)
7. CENTRE DE DÉVELOPPEMENT DES ÉNERGIES RENOUVELABLES (Morocco)
8. AFRISOL S.A. (Morocco)
9. LEBANESE SOLAR ENERGY SOCIETY (Lebanon)
10. NATIONAL ENERGY RESEARCH CENTER (Jordan)

Main objective

Based on the successful implementation of multi-user solar hybrid grids (MSG) in Europe, this project deals with the design of rural village electrification technology and schemes for rural communities, schools, or dispensaries in Mediterranean partner countries. For this purpose, this project further develops and adapts an integrated approach, covering all aspects required (social, economic, financial

and technical) for long term sustainable energy service achieved with hybrid systems. This approach is elaborated in a common effort between partners in the EU and Mediterranean partner countries).

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/15286>

Publications

not found

RD-GOVERNANCE

Addressed topics

Territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE

Full name

The structures of civil society governance in promoting rural development (on the example of East Germany and Ukraine)

Funding Scheme

IIF - Marie Curie actions-Incoming International Fellowships

Overall budget

not found

Start/End

2005-2007

Participants

not found

Main objective

The specific objectives of research are:

- theoretical analysis of civil society governance;
- evaluation of the potential of using the civil society governance for rural development purposes in each covered country;
- development of recommendations for action for the key stakeholders of rural development.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/514036>

Publications

not found

FOODIMA

Addressed topics

Territorial approaches and policies / innovation policies / rural values and income / policy performance

Coordinator

ARISTOTLE UNIVERSITY OF THESSALONIKI

Full name

EU food industry dynamics and methodological advances

Funding Scheme

STREP - Specific Targeted Research Project

Overall budget

1,046,133.00

Start/End

2007-2010

Participants

1. UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN (Denmark)
2. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITEIT (Netherlands)
3. UNIVERSITY OF WARWICK (United Kingdom)
4. UNIVERSITY OF CRETE (Greece)
5. CHARLES UNIVERSITY IN PRAGUE (Czechia)
6. MARTIN-LUTHER-UNIVERSITAT HALLE-WITTENBERG (Germany)

Main objective

The expected outputs include:

- an analytical characterisation of the EU food chain, including a review of the influence of agricultural policies;
- a set of microeconomic models for the analysis of strategic interactions in the food chain;
- a set of theoretical models for the evaluation of the impact of technological innovations on the structure of food chain and the incentives created for R&D investments;
- a theoretical model for the analysis of policy instruments like food standards and labelling on firm performance and social welfare;
- a concrete framework for the evaluation of the economic performance of the entire food chain;
- a general equilibrium model for the quantitative analysis of the industry's impact on the socioeconomic development of rural areas.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/44283>

Publications

not found

ARSLAND

Addressed topics

Rural and circular and efficient resource use

Coordinator

INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO AGRARIO DE CASTILLA Y LEÓN

Full name

SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF ARSENIC CONTAMINATED WATER AND SOIL IN RURAL AREAS OF LATIN AMERICA

Funding Scheme

SSA - Specific Support Action

Overall budget

129 964

Start/End

2006-2007

Participants

1. CORNWALL COLLEGE CORPORATION (United Kingdom)
2. UNIVERSIDAD CATÓLICA DEL NORTE (Chile)
3. UNIVERSIDAD DE BUENOS AIRES (Argentina)
4. UNIVERSIDAD DE VALLADOLID (Spain)

Main objective

The rational use of natural resources is of vital importance for sustainability and development of developing countries. New policies must be adopted to guarantee sustainable management and utilisation of the natural resources of soil and water. Safe water for domestic and agrarian uses is a world-wide priority in all countries and for all people. The global impact of arsenic contamination on soils and groundwaters by natural (volcanic) and anthropogenic (mining) activities causes serious health issues which need to be addressed with some urgency in the near future. Nowadays, there are no simple and inexpensive technologies to mitigate arsenic contamination. In isolated and poor rural areas in developing countries this problem is deeply aggravated as they cannot benefit from public water treatment processes. On the other hand, agricultural uses of arsenic polluted soil and water is an important issue for food safety concern. The aim of this project is the design and implementation of arsenic mitigate on programmes to solve the specific problems of these poor and rural areas. A complementary topic of interest is the development of monitoring strategies aimed to assess the risk of arsenic accumulation in the food chain. The present proposal is addressed to connect and feedback mechanisms between all the relevant sectors involved in arsenic pollution in Europe and Latin America (scientific expertise in arsenic mitigation and/or removal in water and soil; health agencies; national and regional Authorities; stakeholders such as communities, NGOs and the private sector. Other aims of the project are the development of effective and sustainable strategies, compiling the right information, preparing emergency and long term programme phases, and coordinating mitigation and monitoring programmes.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/15114>

Publications

not found

FP7 PROJECTS

TUCAN 3G

Addressed topics

Well-being quality of life and attractiveness of rural territories as places to live and work; social capital, social processes, social networks and social innovation

Full name

Wireless technologies for isolated rural communities in developing countries based on cellular 3G femtocell deployments

Funding scheme

FP7-ICT

Overall budget

€ 1,365,123.00

Start/End

2013-2016

Participants

1. UNIVERSIDAD DEL CAUCA (COLOMBIA)
2. CENTRO REGIONAL DE PRODUCTIVIDAD E INNOVACION DEL CAUCA ENTIDAD PRIVADA SIN ANIMO DE LUCRO, (COLOMBIA)
3. TELEFONICA INTERNATIONAL WHOLESAL SERVICES SL (SPAIN)
4. FUNDACION ENLACE HISPANO AMERICANO DE SALUD, (SPAIN)
5. UNIVERSIDAD REY JUAN CARLOS, (SPAIN)
6. KNOWLEDGE & INNOVATION CONSULTANTS SYMVOULEFTIKI MONOPROSOPI EPE, (GREECE)
7. FONDO DE INVERSION EN TELECOMUNICACIONES – FITEL (PERU)
8. TELEFONICA DEL PERU SAA, (PERU)
9. PONTIFICIA UNIVERSIDAD CATOLICA DEL PERU, (PERU)
10. IP.ACCESS LIMITED (UNITED KINGDOM)

Main objective

Technology development, market research and elaboration of business models, and in verification through proofs of concept in platforms installed in basins of the rivers Napo and Putumayo (Peru), which will allow deploying several femtocells in 4 remote rural locations .

No policies are mentioned.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/601102>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/601102/results>

There are 9 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

Not found

SMARTOPENDATA

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas an rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability ; rural and digital; innovation policies and innovation ecosystems for rural communities; rural and biodiversity

Coordinator

EMPRESA DE TRANSFORMACION AGRARIA SA

Full name

Linked Open Data for environment protection in Smart Regions

Funding scheme

FP7-ENVIRONMENT

Overall budget

€ 3,189,042.11

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas an rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability ; rural and digital; innovation policies and innovation ecosystems for rural communities; rural and biodiversity

Start/End

2013-2015

Participants

1. UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID (SPAIN)
2. THE NATIONAL MICROELECTRONICS APPLICATIONS CENTRE LTD (CZECHIA)
3. SINDICE LIMITED, Ireland Mid-West Regional Authority (IRELAND)
4. AGENZIA REGIONALE PER LA PROTEZIONE DELL'AMBIENTE (ITALY)
5. FONDAZIONE BRUNO KESSLER (ITALY)
6. SPAZIODATI SRL (ITALY)
7. HELP SERVICE REMOTE SENSING SRO (CZECHIA)
8. Ústav pro hospodářskou úpravu lesů Brandýs nad Labem (CZECHIA)
9. CESKE CENTRUM PRO VEDU A SPOLECNOST (CZECHIA)
10. STIFTELSEN SINTEF (NORWAY)
11. LATVIJAS UNIVERSITATES MATEMATIKAS UN INFORMATIKAS INSTITUTS (LATVIA)
12. DIRECAO GERAL DO TERRITORIO (PORTUGAL)
13. SLOVENSKA AGENTURA ZIVOTNEHO PROSTREDIA (SLOVAKIA)
14. GEIE ERCIM (FRANCE)
15. LIMERICK CITY AND COUNTY COUNCIL (IRELAND)

Main objective

SmartOpenData aims to define mechanisms for acquiring, adapting and using Open Data provided by existing sources for environment protection in European protected areas. Through target pilots in these areas, the project will harmonise metadata, improve spatial data fusion and visualisation and publish the resulting information according to user requirements and Linked Open Data principles to provide new opportunities for SMEs.

No policies are mentioned.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/603824>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/603824/results>

There is 1 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

Identified the most important or useful tools, models and algorithms used during the project and made those publicly available as well. Using all of these tools, SMARTOPENDATA completed five pilot studies to ensure that the infrastructure works as intended. The work of SMARTOPENDATA is sure to foster innovation within the environmental and conservation industries in the EU.

No policies are mentioned.

ENVIEVAL

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability; rural values and income; policy performance evaluation; rural and biodiversity

Coordinator

JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI

Full name

Development and application of new methodological frameworks for the evaluation of environmental impacts of rural development programmes in the EU

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€ 2,335,877.00

Start/End

2013-2015

Participants

1. THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE, (UNITED KINGDOM)
2. GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON (GRECECE)
3. LUONNONVARAKESKUS (FINLAND)
4. CONSIGLIO PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA E L'ANALISI DELL'ECONOMIA AGRARIA (ITALY)
5. BALTIJOS APLINKOS FORUMAS VSI Lithuania SZENT ISTVAN UNIVERSITY (HUNGARY)

Main objective

i) to review implemented rural development programmes, existing monitoring and indicator systems, and new methodological developments in environmental policy evaluation; ii) to develop new methodological frameworks for the evaluation of net environmental effects of rural development programmes against their counterfactual; iii) to test and validate the selected evaluation tools through public good case study applications in seven partner countries and close collaboration with the European Evaluation Network, national and regional evaluators and managing authorities; iv) to assess the cost-effectiveness of the tested indicators and evaluation methods; and v) to provide a user-friendly methodological handbook for the evaluation of environmental impacts of rural development programmes.

Environmental policy evaluation is mentioned.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/312071>

<https://www.envieval.eu/>

Publications

Not found

Results and recommendations

A handbook has recently been produced on new evaluation approaches to assess the effectiveness of rural development programmes (RDPs) in delivering environmental benefits.

The project results affected in many ways the policies between environment and rural programmes.

FARMPATH

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas an rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability; generation renewal: renewing farming and rural generations; policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE,

Full name

Farming Transitions: Pathways Towards Regional Sustainability of Agriculture in Europe

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€ 2,068,272.80

Start/End

2011-2014

Participants

1. UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN (AUSTRIA)
- 2.AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS (GREECE)
- 3.UNIVERSITY OF NATIONAL AND WORLD ECONOMY (BULGARIA)
- 4.VEREIN FUER LANDLICHE STRUKTURFORSCHUNG EV (GERMANY)

5. CESKA ZEMEDELSKA UNIVERZITA V PRAZE (CZECHIA)
6. UNIVERSITY OF PLYMOUTH (UNITED KINGDOM)
7. UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA (PORTUGAL)
8. INSTITUT SUPERIEUR DES SCIENCES AGRONOMIQUES, AGROALIMENTAIRES, HORTICOLES ET DU PAYSAGE (UNITED KINGDOM)
9. THE MACAULAY LAND USE RESEARCH INSTITUTE (UNITED KINGDOM)

Main objective

1. To improve our understanding of **transition processes in European agriculture**. 2. To provide an in-depth analysis of **seven to ten types of farming models and initiatives**, through twenty-one case studies in seven European states. 3. To assess future transition pathways for sustainable agriculture through the **development and operationalisation of the concept of 'regional sustainability of agriculture'**. 4. To identify **mechanisms to provide viable models for young farmers**, through an analysis of the engagement of young people in initiatives, evaluating the issues, preferences and challenges (including gender) facing young people in agriculture at local, regional, national and European levels. 5. To develop **evidence-based policy recommendations at farming system, regional, national and EU levels** for identifying and pursuing future transition pathways and social and technological innovation needs. 6. To initiate a **network of regional level stakeholders and organizations** involved in transition processes in agriculture and to further equip, enable and consolidate it. 7. To provide **resources for policymakers, academics and other stakeholders** in order to develop their understanding and enable pursuit of transition towards regional sustainability of agriculture in their own efforts and organisations.
2. **Policy recommendations for farming systems and sustainability.**

Websites

- <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/265394>
<https://farmpath.hutton.ac.uk/partners>

Publications

- <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/265394/results>

There are 2 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

Researchers have produced a guide outlining different approaches to achieving sustainable agriculture in Europe.

FARMPATH project helped farmers to adapt to these changing demands. It will help disseminate the knowledge gained during the project to academics, policymakers and farmers.

ARANGE (Not 'rural' is mentioned, but it contains regions)

Addressed topics

Rural and climate; rural values and income; innovation policies and innovation ecosystems for rural communities; policy performance evaluation; rural and biodiversity

Coordinator

UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN

Full name

Advanced multifunctional forest management in European mountain ranges

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€ 3,802,775.79

Start/End

2012-2015

Participants

1. EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH, (SWITZERLAND)
2. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN SCIENCES ET TECHNOLOGIES POUR L'ENVIRONNEMENT ET L'AGRICULTURE (FRANCE)
3. TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN (GERMANY)
4. SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET (SWEDEN)
5. UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI (SLOVENIA)
6. NARODNE LESNICKE CENTRUM (SLOVAKIA)
7. INSTITUT ZA GORATA – BA (BULGARIA)
8. INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACION Y TECNOLOGIA AGRARIA Y ALIMENTARIA OA MP (SPAIN)
9. EUROPEAN FOREST INSTITUTE (FINLAND)
10. UNIVERSITAET GRAZ (AUSTRIA)
11. IFER - Ustav pro vyzkum lesnich ekosystemu, (s.r.o.) (CZECHIA)
12. GEOEXPERT RESEARCH AND PLANNING GMBH (AUSTRIA)
13. STICHTING BIRDLIFE EUROPE (NETHERLANDS)
14. ARANZADA GESTION FORESTAL SLP, (SPAIN)
15. DR. STEPHEN WEBB / RTD SERVICES E U(AUSTRIA)

Main objective

The project builds on seven case study regions in major mountain ranges throughout Europe covering a wide range of forest types, socio-economic conditions and cultural contexts and seeks to develop and evaluate strategies for their multifunctional management considering risks and uncertainty due to changing climatic and socio-economic conditions.

ARANZADA will translate project findings on the efficient provision of multiple ES from mountain forests into decision support for policy makers.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/289437>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/289437/results>

There are 9 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

The project studied the pros and cons of different approaches to mountain forest management, mapping related risks and threats, in order to advance ecosystem services. It investigated cutting-edge knowledge for providing these services to support policymakers and forest experts so that they can enhance decision-making and planning. The project covered seven mountain regions in the continent, integrating different forest types such as continental, Mediterranean and boreal. It worked

on identifying the different ecosystem services from conservation to protection, analysing policy and governance frameworks, and outlining management strategies. To achieve its aims, the project team collected the relevant tree data and baseline climate data for different elevations. It also projected five transient climate change scenarios for each of the seven areas under study, in addition to modelling forest conditions and defining ecosystem service indicators. Specifically, the team identified 22 indicators for different ecosystem services, namely timber and biomass production, carbon sequestration, biodiversity/habitat conservation, protection against landslides, and avalanches or falling rocks. Most importantly, the project developed a decision support toolbox to analyse ecosystem services indicators for different landscapes and made it publicly available to facilitate forest management planning. Among its findings, the project team demonstrated the importance of factoring disturbances to avoid over-optimistic forest projections. It also recommended against a single forest management approach for all European mountain forests. These and many other conclusions, along with the toolbox, will contribute to safeguarding our forests and pre-empting catastrophic changes that could arise from climate change.

An in-depth evaluation of ecosystem services and how they can support forests in Europe could help policymakers and authorities combat climate change.

SmartRuralGrid

Addressed topics

Rural and digital; smart villages/communities

Coordinator

ESTABANELL Y PAHISA ENERGIA SA

Full name

Smart ICT-enabled Rural Grid innovating resilient electricity distribution infrastructures, services and business models

Funding scheme

FP7-ICT

Overall budget

€ 4,944,690.00

Start/End

2014-2017

Participants

1. KISTERS AG (Germany)
2. STADTWERKE ROSENHEIM NETZE GMBH, (Germany)
3. XARXA OBERTA, DE COMUNICACIO I TECNOLOGIA DE CATALUNYA SA (Spain)
4. ZIV COMMUNICATIONS SA (Spain)
5. UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE CATALUNYA (Spain)
6. CG POWER SYSTEMS IRELAND LTD (Ireland)
7. SMART INNOVATION NORWAY AS (Norway)
8. EUS GMBH (Germany)
9. CG AUTOMATION SYSTEMS UK LIMITED (United Kingdom)

Main objective

Med at developing an innovative smart grid approach targeted to the particular conditions of rural electricity distribution networks. The project will devote particular attention to highlight the differentiated specificities of rural electricity distribution and will target the need of gaining substantial improvements in terms of efficiency, quality and network resilience, favouring the introduction of new innovative business models in support of rural DSO's operations and of their future economic and industrial sustainability

No policies are mentioned.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/619610>

<https://smartruralgrid.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/619610/results>

Results and recommendations

Not found

C-BIRD

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability; policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

TRAKIYSKI UNIVERSITET

Full name

Cooperative Business and Innovative Rural Development: Synergies between Commercial and Academic Partners

Funding scheme

FP7-PEOPLE

Overall budget

€ 597,663.91

Start/End

2014-2017

Participants

1. EURICSE (Italy)
2. UNIVERSIDAD DE ALMERIA (Spain)
3. UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK (Ireland)
4. AGROCONSULT-ENGINEERING EOOD (Bulgaria)
5. ASOCIACION DE ORGANIZACIONES DE PRODUCTORES DE FRUTAS Y HORTALIZAS DE ALMERIA (Spain)
6. ZIP CENTAR ZA MLADE BIZNIS INKUBATOR DOO PIROT (Serbia)

Main objective

It Will investigate the innovative role of cooperatives, and related rural actors (including academic institutions, commercial enterprises, NGOs, associations, etc.) in rural development as a useful tool to achieve such objectives (sustainability of rural areas in social, economic and environmental aspects.) and their importance in the "knowledge economy". Quantitative and qualitative and case study analysis will be carried out in exchanges between industry and academic institutions in order to identify successful models and also to investigate rural development strategies in recently incorporated EU countries."

Rural development policy is mentioned.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/611490>

Publications

Not found

Results and recommendations

Not found

RURAL DECISIONS

Addressed topics

Policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

HUMBOLDT-UNIVERSITAET ZU BERLIN

Full name

Development of a framework for managing uncertain decisions in agricultural and environmental policies – Towards an integrated policy for decision-making support in rural areas

Funding scheme

FP7-PEOPLE

Overall budget

€ 232,684.02

Start/End

2009-2012

No participants**Main objective**

Develop a methodological framework integrating uncertain economic and ecological aspects in multiobjective decision-support systems in agricultural and environmental policies for Germany, Poland, and the U.S.

Project is totally mentioned to policy evaluation in rural areas.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/235979/reporting/es>

Publications

Not found

Results and recommendations

Yielded a novel tool that supports **policy evaluation** and decision making in contexts of European rural economics. The work also helped to improve European scientific excellence.

BIR AL-NAS

Addressed topics

Well-being, quality of life and attractiveness of rural territories as places to live and work Social capital, social processes, social networks and social innovation; rural and climate; territorial approaches and policies; rural and Biodiversity

Coordinator

UNIVERSITA CA' FOSCARI VENEZIA, Italy

Full name

Bottom-up IntegRATED Approach for sustainabLe grouNdwater mAnagement in rural areaS

Funding scheme

FP7-PEOPLE

Overall budget

€ 212,532.00

Start/End

2013-2016

No participants**Main objective**

The overall objective is meant to be achieved through an integrated hydrogeochemical and social analysis finalized to obtain robust and reliable information for providing advices and supporting integrated management practices for rural development

No policy is mentioned.**Websites**

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/327287?rcn=182627>

<https://biralnas.wordpress.com/papers-publications/my-publications-map/>

Publications

<https://biralnas.wordpress.com/papers-publications/my-publications-map/>

There is 1 publication via OpeinAire.

Results and recommendations

Not found

GLOBAL-RURAL

Addressed topics

Territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

ABERYSTWYTH UNIVERSITY, United Kingdom

Full name

The Global Countryside: Rural Change and Development in Globalization

Funding scheme

FP7-IDEAS-ERC

Overall budget

€ 2,263,107.00

Start/End

2014-2019

No participants**Main objective**

advance our understanding of the workings and impact of globalization in rural regions through the development and application of new conceptual and methodological approaches. Globalization has a pervasive influence in transforming rural economies and societies, with implications for the major societal challenges of environmental change and resource security.

One work package of this project will identify the policy applications of the research, and disseminate research findings to academic and non-academic users.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/339567>

Publications

Not found

Results and recommendations

Not found

MEMOLA

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability; rural values and income; rural and biodiversity

Coordinator

UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA (Spain)

Full name

MEditerranean MOntainous LAndscapes: an historical approach to cultural heritage based on traditional agrosystems

Funding scheme

FP7-SSH

Overall budget

€ 2,940,722.56

Start/End

2014-2017

Participants

1. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA (Italy)
2. UNIVERSIDAD DE CORDOBA (Spain)
3. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PALERMO (Italy)
4. THE UNIVERSITY OF SHEFFIELD (United Kingdom)
5. EACHTRA ARCHAEOLOGICAL PROJECTS LIMITED (Ireland)
6. ARQUEOANDALUSI ARQUEOLOGIA Y PATRIMONIO SL (Spain)
7. AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS (Spain)
8. CENTRO UNESCO DE ANDALUCIA (Spain)
9. QENDRA E KERKIMEVE DHE PROMOVIMIT TE PEISAZHEVE HISTORIKO-ARKEOLOGJIKE SHQIPTARE (Albania)

Main objective

Interdisciplinary approach to cultural landscapes of Mediterranean mountainous areas, taking as a central axis the historical study of two natural resources essential to generate agro-systems: water and soil. Agricultural traditions and the different ways of exploiting natural resources including management over time are crucial for conservation of the landscape and its ability to adapt to current global changes: globalisation and agrarian industrialisation, loss of peasant knowledge, loss of rural population and climate change.

No policies are mentioned.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/613265?rcn=197932>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/613265/results?rcn=197932>

There are 15 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

Not found

AGFORWARD**Addressed topics**

Innovation policies and innovation ecosystems for rural communities

Coordinator

CRANFIELD UNIVERSITY, United Kingdom

Full name

AGroFORestry that Will Advance Rural Development

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€ 8,009,806.24

Start/End

2014-2017

Participants

1. EUROPEAN FOREST INSTITUTE , Finland
2. Association de Coordination Technique Agricole, France
3. UNIVERSIDAD DE SANTIAGO DE COMPOSTELA, Spain

4. TECHNOLOGIKO EKPEDEFTIKO IDRIMA STEREAS ELLADAS, Greece
5. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France
6. PROGRESSIVE FARMING TRUST LTD LBG, United Kingdom
7. BRANDENBURGISCHE TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT COTTBUS-SENFTENBERG, Germany
8. UNIVERSIDAD DE EXTREMADURA, Spain
9. INSTITUTO SUPERIOR DE AGRONOMIA, Portugal
10. KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET, Denmark
11. EIDGENOESSISCHES DEPARTEMENT FUER WIRTSCHAFT, BILDUNG UND FORSCHUNG, Switzerland
12. WERKGROEP VOOR EEN RECHTVAARDIGE ENVERANTWOORDE LANDBOUW, Belgium
13. AARHUS UNIVERSITET, Denmark
14. AGRIFOOD AND BIOSCIENCES INSTITUTE, United Kingdom
15. CONSIGLIO PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA E L'ANALISI DELL'ECONOMIA AGRARIA, Italy
16. STICHTING LOUIS BOLK INSTITUUT, Netherlands
17. CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE, Italy
18. SOPRONI EGYETEM KOOPERACIOS KUTATASI KOZPONT NONPROFIT KFT, Hungary
19. UNIVERSITATEA BABES BOLYAI, Romania
20. AGENZIA VENETA PER L'INNOVAZIONE NEL SETTORE PRIMARIO, Italy
21. AGROOF, France
22. ASSEMBLEE PERMANENTE DES CHAMBRES D'AGRICULTURE, France
23. ASSOCIATION FRANCAISE D AGROFORESTERIE, DES RACINES ET DES CIMES, France
24. INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR RESEARCH IN AGROFORESTRY, Kenya
25. EUROPEAN AGROFORESTRY FEDERATION ASSOCIATION*EURAFEUROPEAN AGROFORESTRY FEDERATION, France

Main objective

A four-year project, developed by 23 organisations at the forefront of agroforestry research, practice and promotion in Europe, with the goal of promoting appropriate agroforestry practices that advance sustainable rural development. i) increase our understanding of existing, and new extensive and intensive agroforestry systems in Europe; ii) identify, develop and demonstrate innovations to improve the ecosystem service benefits and viability of agroforestry systems in Europe using participatory research, iii) develop better adapted designs and practices for the different soil and climatic conditions of Europe, and iv) promote the wide adoption of sustainable agroforestry systems.

No policies are mentioned.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/613520>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/613520/results>

There are 75 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

Not found.

CLAIM

Addressed topics

Policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

ALMA AMTER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA, Italy

Full name

Supporting the role of the Common agricultural policy in Landscape valorisation: Improving the knowledge base of the contribution of landscape Management to the rural economy

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€ 1,874,220.00

Start/End

2012-2014

Participants

1. LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG (ZALF) (e.V.) (Germany)
2. JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE- EUROPEAN COMMISSION (Belgium)
3. UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN (Austria)
4. VERENIGING VOOR CHRISTELIJK HOGER ONDERWIJS WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK EN PATIENTENZORG (Netherlands)
5. INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACIONY FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA (Spain)
6. SZKOLA GLOWNA GOSPODARSTWA WIEJSKIEGO(Poland)
7. SULEYMAN DEMIREL UNIVERSITY (Turkey)
8. AGRAREN UNIVERSITET - PLOVDIV (Bulgaria)
9. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE (France)
10. STICHTING VU (Netherlands)

Main objective

Provide the knowledge base to support an effective CAP policy design in the direction of improved landscape management, particularly providing insights into the ability of landscape to contribute to the production of added value for society in rural areas.

Project focuses on policies about landscape management from different points of view.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/289578>

<http://www.claimproject.eu/about.aspx>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/289578/results>

There are 9 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

An EU team examined local consequences of Europe's agricultural policies on landscape, contributing to policy evolution. Results indicated that the largest unknown was indirect economic effects of landscape management, and that food supply had the greatest impact on landscape valorisation. The CLAIM project's exploration of socioeconomic issues surrounding management of European rural landscapes helped to revise the CAP.

CAPRI-RD

Addressed topics

Innovation policies and innovation ecosystems for rural communities

Coordinator

RHEINISCHE FRIEDRICH-WILHELMS-UNIVERSITÄT BONN, Germany

Full name

Common Agricultural Policy Regionalised Impact - The Rural Development Dimension"

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€ 3,030,002.00

Start/End

2009-2013

Participants

1. JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE- EUROPEAN COMMISSION (Belgium)
2. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH (Netherlands)
3. MIDDLE EAST TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY (Turkey)
4. JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI (Germany)
5. HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO (Finland)
6. UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI (Slovenia)
7. INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY LONDON (United Kingdom)
8. UNIVERSITY OF GLOUCESTERSHIRE (United Kingdom)
9. SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET (Sweden)

Main objective

Aims to develop and apply an operational, Pan-European tool including all Candidate and Potential Candidate countries to analyse the regional impacts of all policy measures under CAP Pillar I and II across a wide range of economic, social and environmental indicators, aligned with the CMEF. CAPRI-RD's core contains consistently linked economic models at the NUTS 2 level, the CAPRI model for agriculture, and a newly developed layer of regional CGEs. Given the importance of the EU's agricultural trade, CAPRI includes a global agricultural market model.

The tool for regional and spatial policy impact analysis of the CAP with regard to rural development indicators.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/226195>

http://enrd.ec.europa.eu/enrd-static/networks-and-networking/research-initiatives/en/research-projects-capri_rd_en.html

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/226195/results>

There are 9 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

Analysed the regional impact of CAP's pillar I (production support) and pillar II (rural development), employing economic, social and environmental indicators. The CAPRI-RD tool will inform **policymakers** and other stakeholders on the consequences of changes to the **CAP**, thereby aiding future decision making and reforms.

SOLINSA

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability; social capital, social processes, social networks and social innovation; innovation policies and innovation ecosystems for rural communities; policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG, Switzerland

Full name

Agricultural Knowledge Systems in Transition: Towards a more effective and efficient support of Learning and Innovation Networks for Sustainable Agriculture

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€ 3,153,275.00

Start/End

2011-2014

Participants

1. UNIVERSITA DI PISA (Italy)
2. UNIVERSITY OF GLOUCESTERSHIRE (United Kingdom)
3. UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF ENGLAND, BRISTOL (United Kingdom)
4. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY (Netherlands)
5. DEVELOPPEMENT DE L'AGRICULTURE ET DE L'ESPACE RURAL: AGRIDEA (Switzerland)
6. EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH (Switzerland)
7. NODIBINAJUMS BALTIC STUDIES CENTRE (Latvia)
8. INSTITUT DE L'ELEVAGE (France)
9. UNIVERSITAET HOHENHEIM (Germany)
10. MAGYAR TUDOMANYOS AKADEMIA KOZGAZDASAG- ES REGIONALIS TUDOMANYI KUTATOKOZPONT (Hungary)

Main objective

Overall objective of this project is to identify effective and efficient approaches for the support of successful LINSAs (Learning and Innovation Networks for Sustainable Agriculture) as drivers of transition towards Agricultural Innovation Systems for sustainable agriculture and rural development.

A policy framework for innovation in agriculture is one of strategic objectives.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/266306>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/266306/results>

There are 10 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

It studied efficient approaches to support actual Learning and Innovation Networks for Sustainable

Agriculture (LINSA). The project identified factors that promoted or held back existing agricultural knowledge systems and innovation policies.

SUSTAINMED

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability; vulnerable groups in rural communities; policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE HAUTES ETUDES AGRONOMIQUES MEDITERRANEENNES, France

Full name

Sustainable agri-food systems and rural development in the Mediterranean Partner Countries

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€ 2,644.116.60

Start/End

2010-2013

Participants

1. ECOLE NATIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DE MEKNES (Morocco)
2. AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS (Spain)
3. Institut National Agronomique de Tunisie (Tunisia)
4. UNIVERSITY OF KENT (United Kingdom)
5. MEDITERRANEAN AGRONOMIC INSTITUTE OF CHANIA (Greece)
6. PELLERVON TALOUDELLISEN TUTKIMUSLAITOKSEN KANNATUSYHDISTYS RY (Finland)
7. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI NAPOLI FEDERICO II (Italy)
8. Ministry of Agriculture and Agrarian Reform (Syria)
9. UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA (Spain)
10. ZAGAZIG UNIVERSITY (Egypt)
11. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE (France)
12. AKDENIZ UNIVERSITY (Turkey)

Main objective

Overall objective of the SUSTAINMED project is to examine and assess the impacts of EU and national agricultural, rural, environmental and trade policies in the Mediterranean Partner Countries (MPCs). Specific impacts include socio-economic structural changes, income distribution, resource management, trade liberalisation, poverty alleviation, employment and migrations trends, as well as commercial relations with major trade partners (in particular the EU) and competitiveness in international markets. The project will integrate a wide range of complementary methods and analytical tools including quantitative modelling, structured surveying, indicator building and qualitative data analysis, in order to provide (i) orders of magnitude of the impact in MPCs related to changes in important policy parameters, and (ii) qualitative insights into processes which will be important for the future welfare of MPCs but which cannot be fully captured by quantitative indicators. The project results will enable the EU Commission and relevant stakeholders to formulate realistic policies and action plans aimed at supporting sustainable agri-food systems, rural development programmes and capacity building in the Mediterranean region.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/90359-promoting-prosperity-in-the-mediterranean>
<https://sustainmed.iamm.fr/index.php/project-presentation>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/245233/results>
<https://sustainmed.iamm.fr/index.php/publications>

There are 3 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

Project investigated local and EU policies in the fields of agriculture, poverty prevention, sustainability, food security and trade. Determined that policies were generally skewed to cater to economic sustainability concerns, while disregarding resource management, conservation efforts and social aspects.

RURAGRI**Addressed topics**

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability; territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France

Full_name

Facing sustainability: new relationships between rural areas and agriculture in Europe

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€ 1,208,730.00

Start/End

2009-2014

Participants

1. LANDBOUW-ECONOMISCH INSTITUUT B.V. (Netherlands)
2. INSTYTUT SADOWNICTWA I KWIACIARSTWAIM. SZCZEPANA PIENIAZKA (Poland)
3. MINISTERE DE L'AGRICULTURE DE L'AGROALIMENTAIRE ET DE LA FORET (France)
4. BUNDESMINISTERIUM FUER NACHHALTIGKEIT UND TOURISMUS (Austria)
5. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK (Belgium)
6. MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE, RURAL DEVELOPMENT AND ENVIRONMENT OF CYPRUS (Cyprus)
7. BUNDESMINISTERIUM FUER BILDUNG UND FORSCHUNG (Germany)
8. FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JULICH GMBH (Germany)
9. MAGYAR TUDOMANYOS AKADEMIA KOZGAZDASAG- ES REGIONALIS TUDOMANYI KUTATOKOZPONT (Hungary)
10. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY (Ireland)
11. MINISTERO DELLE POLITICHE AGRICOLE ALIMENTARI E FORESTALI (Italy)
12. MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT (Israel)
13. LATVIJAS ZINATNU AKADEMIJA (Latvia)

14. LIETUVOS RESPUBLIKOS ZEMES UKIO MINISTERIJA (Lithuania)

15. INSTYTUT OGRODNICTWA (Poland)

Main objective

Aims to improve coordination between on-going and future European, national and regional research programmes dealing with the new relationships between rural areas and agriculture in Europe and the challenge of sustainability.

In a context of deep modification of agricultural and rural development policies at a European scale, research on such topical issues is crucial to support decision-making processes.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/235175>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/235175/results>

There are 29 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

A synopsis of the three discussions that took place was written up and provided feedback for refining the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA). Another major project outcome was an EU-wide call for project proposals that address one of three core issues: diversity, rural–urban relationships and governance. Five collaborative research projects have been funded. RURAGRI has researched and established an SRA in a key research area. Considered against the backdrop of EU agricultural and rural development policies, an SRA will prove invaluable as support for relevant decision makers and research managers.

SPARD

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability.; territorial approaches and policies; policy performance evaluation)

Coordinator

Leibniz-Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Germany

Full name

Spatial Analysis of Rural Development Measures

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€ 1,900,000.00

Start/End

2010-2013

Participants

1. Stichting Dienst Landbouwkundig Onderzoek (DLO) (Netherlands)
2. Università di Bologna (Italy)
3. Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH (Austria)
4. VU University Amsterdam (Netherlands)
5. Institut national de la recherche agronomique (France)

6. University of Edinburgh (United Kingdom)
7. University of Ljubljana (Slovenia)
8. Institute for Prospective Technological Studies (EU)

Main objective

Develop a modelling tool that will help policy-makers to understand the causal relationships between rural development measures and their results in a spatial dimension.

Webbsites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/244944?fbclid=IwAR2VYbPRX0gJ2RP-q3d2qUnsRoy7uYbWfVi4sCdqZqfNqgJkb0moHfNg7e>
<http://project2.zalf.de/spard/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/244944/results?fbclid=IwAR2VYbPRX0gJ2RP-q3d2qUnsRoy7uYbWfVi4sCdqZqfNqgJkb0moHfNg7eA>

There are 4 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

Researchers developed a conceptual framework establishing coherent links between political aims, RD measures and outcomes. This analytical framework devised theories about the causal relationships between spending, requirements, features and **policy consequences**. It also identified target areas and target groups of RD measures. More efficient RDP and RD instruments will give farmers the flexibility to deal with pressing issues within a given territory that reflect their particular economic, natural and structural circumstances. SPARD will ultimately lead to enhanced competitiveness, as well as rural and environmental sustainability.

RUDI

Addressed topics

Policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

VEREIN FUER LANDLICHE STRUKTURFORSCHUNG EV, Germany

Full name

Assessing the Impact of Rural Development Policies

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€ 3,257,692.00

Start/End

2008-2010

Participants

1. UNIVERSITY OF GLOUCESTERSHIRE (United Kingdom)
2. ISTITUTO NAZIONALE DI ECONOMIA AGRARIA (Italy)
3. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY (Netherlands)
4. ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS (Greece)
5. NSTALT FUER BERGBAUERNFRAGEN (Austria)
6. UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI (Slovenia)
7. NORDREGIO (Sweden)

8. MITTETULUNDUSUHING OKOLOOGILISTE TEHNOLOGIATE KESKUS (Estonia)

9. USTAV ZEMEDELSKE EKONOMIKY A INFORMACI (Czechia)

Main objective

Provide a thorough analysis of the design, delivery and impact of EU **Rural Development Policy** (incl. LEADER). The study combines quantitative and qualitative approaches starting with a critical review of the state-of-the-art in RD theory and the conceptual frameworks and approaches used in **RD policy evaluation**. In the study the Common Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (CMEF) and the underlying intervention and impact logics will be critically examined. The positive and negative effects of rural development policies on institutional, social, economic and environmental level will be identified and described in a set of carefully selected and framed case studies. The impact assessment will also include those impacts that have not been anticipated.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/213034>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/213034/results>

There are 7 publications via OpenAire

Results and recommendations

The project results are set to improve programme design, as well as targeting and implementation of programmes for the funding period 2013–2020. This has the potential to increase the positive impacts of rural development policies in all EU countries. The initiative was supported through direct involvement of key stakeholders and institutions in the research process, as well as cross-country analyses. Conferences, workshops, publications and online dissemination activities ensured that the project's results reached the desired target audience

Project partners analysed the effects of policy processes to develop recommendations for policymakers at EU, national and regional levels.

RUFUS

Addressed topics

Social capital, social processes, social networks and social innovation; rural values and income; policy performance evaluation; territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

GOTTFRIED WILHELM LEIBNIZ UNIVERSITAET HANNOVER, Germany

Full name

Rural Future Networks

Funding scheme

FP7-SSH

Overall budget

€ 1,836,179.20

Start/End

2008-2011

Participants

1. TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT (Netherlands)
2. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE (France)
3. UNIVERSITY OF EAST ANGLIA (United Kingdom)

4. LUNDS UNIVERSITET (Sweden)
5. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY (Netherlands)
6. SPRINT CONSULT GBR WISSENSCHAFT POLITIKBERATUNG (Germany)
7. VERENIGING VOOR CHRISTELIJK HOGER ONDERWIJS WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK EN PATIENTENZORG, (Netherlands)

Main objective

RUFUS will provide policy makers and stakeholders with better theoretical and practical understandings of how CAP measures interact with other forms of public intervention in rural development; and how policy regimes can be combined to ensure more sustainable development. RUFUS will investigate how rural development policy can be targeted at the specific endogenous potential of rural regions to encourage multiple functionality which goes beyond physical landscape potentials to include social and economic activities and opportunities.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/217381>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/217381/results>

There is 1 publication via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

Project members identified policy impact weaknesses due to lack of coordination, studying key issues such as multifunctional potential or diversification, endogenous potential or territorial capital, and territorial impacts of policy. This led to a successful cluster analysis of regional economic, ecological and social characteristics, highlighting comparative advantages of regions and mapping future rural development. It also led to a clear classification of rural areas in Europe, as well as a clearer picture of pressures and potential developments for rural areas, welcome initiative, based on encouraging the emergence of rural networks through enhanced policymaking, is poised to breathe new life into Europe's rural areas.

CAP-IRE

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability; rural values and income; policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA, Italy

Full name

Assessing the multiple Impacts of the Common Agricultural Policies (CAP) on Rural Economies

Funding scheme

FP7-SSH

Overall budget

€ 1,881,354.00

Participants

1. JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE- EUROPEAN COMMISSION (Belgium)
2. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY (Netherlands)
3. LANDBOUW-ECONOMISCH INSTITUUT (B.V.) (Netherlands)

4. ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS (Greece)
5. SZKOLA GLOWNA GOSPODARSTWA WIEJSKIEG (Poland)
6. THE UNIVERSITY COURT OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN (United Kingdom)
7. UNIVERSIDAD DE CORDOBA (Spain)
8. INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS (Bulgaria)
9. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE (France)
10. LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG (ZALF) (e.V.) (Germany)

Main objective

The objective of the project CAP-IRE is to develop concepts and tools to support future CAP design, based on an improved understanding of long term socio-economic mechanisms of change in rural areas.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/216672>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/216672/results>

There are 11 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

Not available

COEXIST This project could not be founded on CORDIS, but the information was collected from its website. There is another one project with this title on CORDIS, but its framework is completely different

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/ rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability; territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

Institute of Marine Research (IMR), Norway

Full name

Interaction in European coastal waters: A roadmap to sustainable integration of aquaculture and fisheries

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€3,777,931.00

Participants

13 partners from 10 countries

Main objective

COEXIST is a broad, multidisciplinary project which will evaluate competing activities and interactions in European coastal areas. The ultimate goal of the COEXIST project is to provide a roadmap to better integration, sustainability and synergies across the diverse activities taking place in the European coastal zone.

No policies are mentioned.

Websites

<https://www.coexistproject.eu/coexist-project/coexist-overview>

Publications

<https://www.coexistproject.eu/coexist-results/publications>

There are 4 articles.

Results and recommendations

Characterisation of relevant European coastal marine ecosystems, their current utilisation and spatial management. Evaluation of spatial management tools for combining coastal fisheries, aquaculture and other uses, both now and in the future

No policies are mentioned.

VOLANTE

Addressed topics

Rural and Biodiversity; policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands

Full name

Visions Of LANd use Transitions in Europe

Funding scheme

FP7-ENVIRONMENT

Overall budget

€ 9,055,946,60

Start/End

2010-2015

Participants

1. THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH (United Kingdom)
2. UNIVERSITAET KLAGENFUR (Austria)
3. VERENIGING VOOR CHRISTELIJK HOGER ONDERWIJS WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK EN PATIENTENZORG (Netherlands)
4. POTSDAM INSTITUT FUER KLIMAFOLGENFORSCHUNG (Germany)
5. KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET (Denmark)
6. EUROPEAN FOREST INSTITUTE (Finland)
7. CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS (France)
8. PANEPITIMIO AIGAIUO (Greece)
9. UNIVERSITATEA DIN BUCURESTI (Romania)
10. JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE- EUROPEAN COMMISSION (Belgium)
11. HUMBOLDT-UNIVERSITAET ZU BERLIN (Germany)
12. AARHUS UNIVERSITET (Denmark)
13. PROSPEX BVBA (Belgium)
14. STICHTING VU (Netherlands)

Main objective

Objective of VOLANTE is to provide European policy and land management with critical pathways defining the band width of possible land management policies for future European land use. Policy options will therefore be identified in time and space and their consequences in terms of states of the land system (provisioning of ecosystem goods and services) will be evaluated, leading to a ROADMAP FOR FUTURE LAND RESOURCES MANAGEMENT IN EUROPE.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/265104>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/265104/results>

There are 78 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

It developed a roadmap to support European land management and decision making. The roadmap proposes three visions of future land use in Europe. The first crosslinks food, feed production, fibre production, rural development and urbanisation, while the second features different scenarios to achieve these visions. The third focuses on implications of these visions and scenarios for society and decision makers, including related trade-offs. Overall the project has deepened our understanding of land-use change in Europe, related policies and vital decision-making processes.

RURALJOBS**Addressed topics**

Well-being, quality of life and attractiveness of rural territories as places to live and work.; rural labour/ jobs; policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

DEBRECENI EGYETEM, Hungary

Full name

New Sources of Employment to Promote the Wealth-Generating Capacity of Rural Communities

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€ 1,400,173.00

Start/End

2008-2010

Participants

1. UNIVERSITATEA BABES BOLYAI , Romania
2. ALEKSANDRO STULGINSKIO UNIVERSITETAS, Lithuania
3. CONSEJERIA DE MEDIO AMBIENTE Y ORDENACION DEL TERRITORIO, Spain
4. LIMOUSIN, France
5. INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS, Bulgaria
6. INIPA - ISTITUTO NAZIONALE ISTRUZIONE PROFESSIONALE AGRICOLA, Italy
7. UNIVERSITY OF PLYMOUTH , United Kingdom

Main objective

Provide a clearer understanding of the factors influencing the employment potentials of different typologies of rural areas to support the future evolution of rural development policies.

The project evaluates the effectiveness of past and current policies in addressing these needs and potentials .The beneficiaries will include policy makers at EU, national and regional levels, rural development practitioners including public sector agencies, SMEs and trade groups, NGOs etc. and academics.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/211605>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/211605/results>

There is 1 publication via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

Several outcomes emerged from the project, including a list of recommendations for public authorities to encourage rural employment. The project team also compiled informative reports on rural development, rural labour markets, labour trends and employment opportunities, thus providing invaluable information about rural areas and key employment issues. It also clearly defined the different typologies of rural areas and articulated a set of indicators that could help further research in this area.

In particular, RURALJOBS looked at the effectiveness of past and current policies in improving competitiveness in sectors such as agriculture, fishing and forestry. It then investigated the harmonisation of regional and rural development policies while the project calls for more analysis to articulate and implement rural policies.

DARDRA

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability; territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

UNIVERSITY OF SOUTHAMPTON, United Kingdom

Full name

Defining and Assessing Rurality/Urbanity and Delineating Rural/Urban Areas in Europe

Funding scheme

FP7-PEOPLE

Overall budget

€ 178,307.05

Start/End

2009-2010

No participants**Main Objective**

Develop methodology for quantification of settlement system morphometric attributes indicating rurality/urbanity based on land cover spatial structure data and population spatial distribution data.

Policies are mentioned at objective's description, but the project does not focus on them.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/220832>

Publications

Not found

Results and recommendations

Not found

DERREG

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability; vulnerable groups in rural communities; territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

ABERYSTWYTH UNIVERSITY, United Kingdom

Funding scheme

FP7-SSH

Overall budget

€ 1,916,222.00

Start/End

2009-2011

Participants

1. LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FÜR LÄNDERKUNDE EV , Germany
2. MENDELOVA UNIVERZITA V BRNE , Czechia NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY , Ireland
3. NORDREGIO, Sweden
4. UNIVERSITÄT DES SAARLANDES, Germany
5. UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI, Slovenia
6. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY, Netherlands
7. ZNANSTVENO RAZISKOVALNI IN IZOBRAZEVALNI ZAVOD NEVORK, Slovenia

Main objective

Produce an interpretative model that will enable regional development actors to better anticipate and respond to the key challenges for disadvantaged regions arising from globalization. In doing so, it will expand scientific knowledge and understanding, inform policy development, and identify examples of best practice

The proposed research will enable policy makers and other stakeholders involved in regional development to better anticipate and respond to the challenges of globalization

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/225204>

<https://www.global-rural.org/about/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/225204/results>

There 25 publications via OpenAire.

Results and recommendations

Firstly, it noted that endogenous rural businesses can benefit more from forming international networks themselves than they can from FDI, something which could be achieved through network brokers. Secondly, it demonstrated that international migrants can contribute significantly to rural regional development, particularly if it is based on initiatives to promote entrepreneurship among migrants. Thirdly, it found that global environmental awareness creates opportunities for the sustainable development of rural environmental capital, although such an eco-economy must first consider regional contexts. Lastly, Derreg found that effective regional development is supported by joint regional learning and innovation that involves knowledge institutes, public administration and grassroots development actions.

All these results can effectively be used by policymakers and local governments to exploit globalisation and make it work for them.

EASTGRAB

Addressed topics

Characterising rural/rural diversity: economic and social analysis tools (including statistics and indicators) to map and describe the situation of rural areas and rural population across the three dimensions of sustainability; social capital, social processes, social networks and social innovation

Coordinator

ERASMUS UNIVERSITEIT ROTTERDAM, Netherlands

Full name

Understanding Land Grabbing in Eastern Europe and Central Asia: an Integrated Assessment of Impacts, Conflicts and Trade-offs

Funding scheme

FP7-PEOPLE

Start/End

Not found

Funding scheme

FP7-PEOPLE

Overall budget

€ 175,974.60

No participants

Main objective

Deepen the existing knowledge of the socio-economic and environmental aspects which characterize the process of agricultural land acquisitions due to commercial purposes, especially in marginalized and poor areas of the world.

The results are expected to provide a better basis for rural development policies to achieve sustainability in rural areas of Eastern Europe in general and of the study area in particular."

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/326781>

Publications

Not available

Results and recommendations

Not found

PRO-AKIS

Addressed topics

Innovation policies and innovation ecosystems for rural communities

Coordinator

UNIVERSITAET HOHENHEIM, Germany

Full name

Prospects for Farmers' Support: Advisory Services in European AKIS

Funding scheme

FP7-KBBE

Overall budget

€ 1,861,524.24

Start/End

2012-2015

Participants

1. THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE, United Kingdom
2. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France
3. UNIVERSIDADE DE TRAS-OS-MONTES E ALTO DOURO, Portugal
4. UNIWERSYTET ROLNICZY IM. HUGONA KOLLATAJA W KRAKOWIE, Poland
5. AGRAREN UNIVERSITET - PLOVDIV, Bulgaria
6. SEGES PS, Denmark
7. LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG (ZALF) (e.V.), Germany

Main objective

Functioning agricultural knowledge and information systems (AKIS) are needed to tackle challenges like (i) giving small-scale farmers access to relevant and reliable knowledge, (ii) bridging scientific research topics and farmers' demands and (iii) offering appropriate support for diverse rural actors that form networks around innovations in agriculture and rural areas .

AKIS stakeholders and policy advisors will accompany PRO AKIS, share interim findings, and participate in workshops and seminars.

On these bases policy recommendations for the strengthening of European agricultural innovation systems will be developed and further research needs will be designated.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/311994>

<https://430a.uni-hohenheim.de/pro-akis>

Publications

Not found

Results and recommendations

Has the potential to enhance linkages between various stakeholders to promote mutual learning and to produce, share and use agriculture-related knowledge, information and technology.

Using all findings as a basis, policy recommendations were produced for strengthening European AKISs.

H2020 PROJECTS

RurInno

Addressed topics

Social capital, social processes/ rural values and income/ innovation policies

Coordinator

LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR RAUMBEZOGENE SOZIALFORSCHUNG (IRS) EV (Germany)

Full name

Social Innovations in Structurally Weak Rural Regions: How Social Entrepreneurs Foster Innovative Solutions to Social Problems

Funding Scheme

MSCA-RISE - Marie Skłodowska-Curie Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE)

Overall budget

225,000

Starts/Ends

2016-2018

Participants

1. UNIVERSITAT LINZ, Austria
2. NIDZICKA FUNDACJA ROZWOJU NIDA, Poland
3. BALLYHOURA DEVELOPMENT CLG, Ireland
4. AGROTIKOS SYNETAIRISMOS STEBIA ELLAS, Greece
5. OTELO EGEN, Austria

Main objective

RurInno acknowledges social enterprises as promising but often neglected drivers of social innovations in structurally weak rural regions that tackle social problems and stabilise and improve the living conditions in these regions. But reports show that social entrepreneurs still lack specialised trainings and education, a supporting infrastructure and recognition. Against this background, RurInno aims at 1) strengthening the skills and the innovative capacity of social entrepreneurs operating in rural regions, 2) improving the knowledge of how social innovations are implemented in rural regions and 3) raising awareness of social entrepreneurship in rural regions in order to foster enabling environments for their activities. We will enhance the knowledge about the innovative capacity of social enterprises in rural regions by field research in the four participating social enterprises and their respective rural regions. We will integrate the social enterprises into the research process as objects of investigation. Thus, we will enhance the perspective from doing research on social entrepreneurs to doing research with social entrepreneurs.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/199946/factsheet/en>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/199946/results/en>

There are 3 peer reviewed articles, 4 reports in regional newspapers and 1 general interest report/broadcast in an EU media.

Results and recommendations

In a world where there is limited awareness regarding rural social enterprises and unfavourable institutional conditions, the EU-funded project *RurInno* (Social Innovations in Structurally Weak Rural Regions) aimed to improve knowledge on how rural social enterprises develop innovative solutions for social challenges. An additional project aim was to strengthen the skills and innovative capacity of rural social enterprise staff members. There were no recommendations for further projects.

SIMRA

Addressed topics

Social capital, social processes/ rural values and incomes/ policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE (United Kingdom)

Full name

Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas

Funding Scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

5,935,828.75

Start/End

2016-2020

Participants

1. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA, Italy
2. UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN, Austria
3. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
4. Perth College, United Kingdom
5. USTAV EKOLOGIE LESA SLOVENSKEJ AKADEMIE VIED, Slovakia
6. EUROPEAN FOREST INSTITUTE, Finland
7. Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Zaragoza / International Centre for Advanced Mediterranean Agronomic Studies, Spain
8. INTERNATIONAL CENTER FOR RESEARCH ON THE ENVIRONMENT AND THE ECONOMY, Greece
9. OULUN YLIOPISTO, Finland
10. BUNDESANSTALT FUR AGRARWIRTSCHAFT UND BERGBAUERNFRAGEN, Austria
11. OSTLANDSFORKNING AS, Norway
12. HOGSKOLEN I INNLANDET, Norway
13. ACCADEMIA EUROPEA DI BOLZANO Italy
14. UNIVERSITY OF LANCASTER, United Kingdom
15. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FOGGIA, Italy
16. CAIRO UNIVERSITY, Egypt
17. FOOD AND AGRICULTURE ORGANIZATION OF THE UNITED NATIONS FAO, Italy
18. Euromontana, France
19. SEEDS-INT, Lebano
20. Foreco Technologies S.L, Spain
21. THE RURAL DEVELOPMENT COMPANY LIMITED, United Kingdom
22. CETIP NETWORK SRO, Czechia
23. OAR GMBH, Austria
24. CONSORCI CENTRE DE CIENCIA I TECNOLOGIA FORESTAL DE CATALUNYA, Spain
25. UNIVERSITAET BERN, Switzerland
26. SCHWEIZERISCHEN ARBEITSGEMEINSCHAFT FUER DIE BERGGEBIETE (SAB), Switzerland

Main objective

SIMRA seeks to advance understanding of social innovation (SI) and innovative governance in agriculture, forestry and rural development (RD), and how to boost them, particularly in marginalised rural areas across Europe, with a focus on the Mediterranean region (including non-EU) where there is limited evidence of outcomes and supporting conditions. These objectives will be achieved by:

1. Developing systematic frameworks: a) theoretical - for improved knowledge of the complexity of SIs and its dimensions, and its impact on unfolding territorial capital; b) operational - based on a trans-disciplinary coalition (researchers and practitioners) to advance understanding of preconditions and success factors (e.g. instruments, incentives etc.) for implementing/operationalizing SI.
2. Creating a categorisation of SIs which encompasses the specificities in terms of social priorities, relationships/collaborations etc. and serves as an instrument to explore reasons why regions with similar conditions display diverging paths and to 'turn diversity into strength'.
3. Creating an integrated set of methods to evaluate SI and its impacts on economic, social, environmental, institutional and policy dimensions of territorial capital.
4. Co-constructed evaluation of SIs in case studies across the spatial variation of European rural areas, considering which components of territorial capital foster and, or mainstream RD.
5. Synthesis and dissemination of new or improved knowledge of SIs and novel governance mechanisms to promote social capital and institutional capacity building and inform effective options/solutions for shaping sustainable development trajectories.
6. Creating collaborative learning and networking opportunities and launching innovative actions at different/multiple scales, with continuous interactions among researchers, 'knowledge brokers' and stakeholders to foster and mainstream SI, leaving a durable legacy.

I thought that this project fits to more than one or two categories so I took the whole objective.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/200385/factsheet/en>

<http://www.simra-h2020.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/200385/results/en>

There are 19 peer reviewed articles, 10 conference proceedings, 2 book chapters and 1 thesis dissertation.

Results and recommendations

At the site we have some deliverables as results and there are no recommendations for further projects. Also, project is ongoing.

COASTAL

Addressed topics

Territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

INSTELLING VOOR TECHNOLOGISCH ONDERZOEK N.V. (Belgium)

Full name

"Collaborative And Sea InTegration pLatform"

Funding Scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

4,999,943.75

Start/End

2018-2022

Participants

1. HELLENIC CENTRE FOR MARINE RESEARCH, Greece
2. STOCKHOLMS UNIVERSITET, Sweden
3. SINTEF OCEAN AS Norway
4. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN SCIENCES ET TECHNOLOGIES POUR L'ENVIRONNEMENT ET L'AGRICULTURE, France
5. INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE-DEZVOLTARE MARINA GRIGORE ANTIPA, Romania
6. INSTITUTUL DE CERCETARE PENTRU ECONOMIA AGRICULTURII SI DEZVOLTARE RURALA BUCURESTI, Romania
7. INTERNATIONAL CENTER FOR RESEARCH ON THE ENVIRONMENT AND THE ECONOMY, Greece
8. AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS, Spain
9. GEONARDO ENVIRONMENTAL TECHNOLOGIES LTD, Hungary
10. GREENBRIDGE INCUBATIE-EN INNOVATIECENTRUM GENT-OOSTENDE, Belgium
11. VLAAMSE LANDMAATSCHAPPIJ, Belgium
12. PROVINCIALE ONTWIKKELINGSMAATSCHAPPIJ WEST-VLAANDEREN, Belgium
13. STIFTELSEN THE STOCKHOLM ENVIRONMENT INSTITUTE, Sweden
14. NIRAS SWEDEN AB, Sweden
15. CAMPUS ROSLAGEN AB, Sweden
16. LUONNONVARAKESKUS, Finland
17. ASOCIATIA GAL DELTA DUNARII, Romania
18. ASOCIATIA GRUPUL DE ACTIUNE LOCALA DOBROGEA CENTRALA, Romania
19. TOURISTIKES EPICHIRISEIS MESSINIAS ANONIMI ETAIREIA, Greece
20. IDRYMA KAPETAN VASILI KAI KARMEN KONSTENTEKOPOULOU, Greece
21. ANAPTYXIAXH MESSINIAS ANAPTYXIAXH AE, Greece
22. CONSEJERIA DE AGUA, AGRICULTURA, GANADERÍA, PESCA Y MEDIO AMBIENTE DE LA REGIÓN DE MURCIA, Spain
23. FEDERACION DE COOPERATIVAS AGRARIAS DE MURCIA S COOP, Spain
24. CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE NOUVELLE –AQUITAINE, France
25. HAVEN OOSTENDE AUTONOOM GEMEENTELIJK HAVENBEDRIJF, Belgium
26. FEDERATION REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE BIOLOGIQUE NOUVELLE AQUITAINE, France
27. VLAAMS INSTITUUT VOOR DE ZEE VZW, Belgium
28. GLOBAL UTMANING, Sweden.

Main objective

The goal of the COASTAL project is to formulate and evaluate business solutions and policy recommendations aimed at improving the coastal-rural synergy to foster rural and coastal development while preserving the environment.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/215939/factsheet/en>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/215939/results/en>

There are 3 peer reviewed articles, project is ongoing.

Results and recommendations

There are no results or recommendations project is ongoing.

SALSA

Addressed topics

Smart villages and communities

Coordinator

UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA (Portugal)

Full name

Small farms, small food businesses and sustainable food security

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

4,958,172.50

Start/End

2016-2020

Participants

1. UNIVERSITA DI PISA, Italy
2. NODIBINAJUMS BALTIC STUDIES CENTRE, Latvia
3. THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE, United Kingdom
4. STIFTELSEN RURALIS INSTITUTT FOR RURAL- OG REGIONALFORSKNING, Norway
5. UNIWERSYTET ROLNICZY IM. HUGONA KOLLATAJA W KRAKOWIE, Poland
6. HIGHCLERE CONSULTING SRL, Romania
7. UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA, Spain
8. International Institute for Environment and Development, United Kingdom
9. AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece
10. UNIVERSIDADE DE CABO VERDE, Cape Verde
11. UNIVERSITY FOR DEVELOPMENT STUDIES, Ghana
12. AFRICAN CENTRE FOR TECHNOLOGY STUDIES, Kenya
13. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE DE TUNISIE, Tunisia
14. INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR RESEARCH IN AGROFORESTRY, Kenya
15. FOOD AND AGRICULTURE ORGANIZATION OF THE UNITED NATIONS FAO, Italy
16. Coldiretti, Italy

Main objective

The overall goal of SALSA "Small Farms, Small Food Businesses and Sustainable Food Security" is to develop a better understanding of the current and potential contribution of small farms to Food and

Nutrition Security (FNS). In addressing this goal, SALSA contributes to tackling research gaps that have become more clearly recognizable in conjunction with the recent global crises which also affected the food distribution and prices. FNS has become a major concern, not only in developing countries but also in Europe.

Policies are not mentioned.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/200242/factsheet/en>

<http://www.salsa.uevora.pt/en/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/200242/results/en>

There are 4 peer reviewed articles, 3 other publications and 5 conference proceedings.

Results and recommendations

The project has some results but because it's ongoing it doesn't have a final summary of them. There are no recommendations.

PROVIDE

Addressed topics

Smart villages and communities

Coordinator

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA (Italy)

Full name

PROVIDing smart DELivery of public goods by EU agriculture and forestry

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

2,991,436.25

Start/End

2015-2018

Participants

1. LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG (ZALF) e. V., Germany
2. UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN, Austria
3. STICHTING VU, Netherlands
4. UNIVERSIDAD DE CORDOBA, Spain
5. THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE, United Kingdom
6. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France
7. LUONNONVARAKESKUS, Finland
8. TALLINN UNIVERSITY, Estonia
9. ISTITUTO DELTA ECOLOGIA APPLICATA SRL, Italy
10. UNIVERSITATEA ALEXANDRU IOAN CUZA DIN IASI, Romania
11. INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS, Bulgaria

12. UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI, Poland

13. TECHNOLOGICKE CENTRUM AKADEMIE VED CESKE REPUBLIKY, Czechia

Main objective

The objective of the project is to provide a conceptual basis, evidence, tools and improved incentive and policy options to support the "smart" provision of public goods (PGs) by the EU agriculture and forestry systems (AFS), in the light of trade-offs and conflicts brought about by prospective intensification scenarios, using a trans-disciplinary approach

Policies are mentioned.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/197077/factsheet/en>

<http://www.provide-project.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/197077/results/en>

There are 8 peer reviewed articles and 1 conference proceeding.

Results and recommendations

The main results of the project are: a renewed ("un-packed") conceptualization of the notion of public goods; an operational framework to support the smart provision of public goods; a toolbox putting together an inventory/mapping of options, operational means for valuation of public goods and for the evaluation of suitable mechanisms for public goods provision; a selection of improved policy/sector mechanisms; a consolidated and long-lasting community of knowledge and practice. There are no recommendations.

NB4WASTE

Addressed topics

Rural and climate/Rural and circular

Coordinator

ALPHA SYLTEC INGENIERIA SL (Spain)

Full name

Narrowband IoT for Waste Collection in Rural Areas

Funding scheme

SME-1 - SME instrument phase 1

Overall budget

71,429

Starts/Ends

1/8/2017-30/11/2017

Participants

There were no participants.

Main objective

The NB4WASTE Project, developed by SYLTEC, will put on the market an integral IoT solution for municipal waste collection management in rural areas using the new NB-IoT communication standard, for the first time in this type of market, including a specific developed low cost unit ultrasonic sensor technology with low energy consumption and 10 years battery life. Thanks to NB4WASTE solution municipalities will increase yield and profit per service (30%) and will save on fuel costs (25%). Additionally waste bin companies business will increase by 40% offering the NB4WASTE solution.

No policies are mentioned.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/211268/factsheet/en>

<http://www.syltec.es/>

The second site doesn't have information for the project it's about the company that developed it.

Publications

There are no publications.

Results and recommendation

The project has finished but there are no results or recommendations.

TRUE

Addressed topics

Rural and climate

Coordinator

THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE (United Kingdom)

Full name

Transition paths to sustainable legume based systems in Europe

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

4,999,927.50

Starts/Ends

2017-2021

Participants

1. COVENTRY UNIVERSITY, United Kingdom
2. STC RESEARCH FOUNDATION, United Kingdom
3. SRUC, United Kingdom
4. KENYA FORESTRY RESEARCH INSTITUTE, Kenya
5. UNIVERSIDADE CATOLICA PORTUGUESA, Portugal
6. UNIVERSITAET HOHENHEIM, Germany

7. AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece
8. IFAU APS, Denmark
9. REGIONALNA RAZVOJNA AGENCIJA MEDIMURJE REDEA DRUSTVO S OGRANICENOM ODGOVORNOSCU ZA REGIONALNI RAZVOJ I POSLOVNE USLUGE, Croatia
10. BANGOR UNIVERSITY, United Kingdom
11. THE PROVOST, FELLOWS, FOUNDATION SCHOLARS & THE OTHER MEMBERS OF BOARD OF THE COLLEGE OF THE HOLY & UNDIVIDED TRINITY OF QUEEN ELIZABETH NEAR DUBLIN, Ireland
12. PROCESSORS & GROWERS RESEARCH ORGANISATION LBG, United Kingdom
13. INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN, Slovenia
14. IGV INSTITUT FUR GETREIDEVERARBEITUNG GMBH, Germany
15. ESSRG KFT, Hungary
16. AGRI KULTI NONPROFIT KORLATOLT FELELOSSEGU TARSASAG, Hungary
17. ALFRED-WEGENER-INSTITUT HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUR POLAR- UND MEERESFORSCHUNG, Germany
18. SLOW FOOD DEUTSCHLAND EV, Germany
19. ARBIKIE DISTILLING LIMITED, United Kingdom
20. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
21. SOCIEDADE AGRICOLA DO FREIXO DO MEIO LDA, Portugal
22. EUREST (PORTUGAL)-SOCIEDADE EUROPEIA DE RESTAURANTES LDA, Portugal
23. SOLINTAGRO SL, Spain
24. JAVNA USTANOVA ZA RAZVOJ MEDIMURSKEZUPANIJE REDEA, Croatia

Main objective

Agriculture accounts for 25% of total (global) greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The production of animals for meat and the application of synthetic nitrogen fertiliser are the largest contributors to agriculture's GHGs budget. Fortunately, legume crops such as beans and clover, are a sustainable source of highly nutritious food and feed and may also be used as a natural nitrogen fertiliser, thanks to their capacity for 'biological nitrogen fixation', that converts atmospheric nitrogen (N₂) to biologically useful nitrogen. The EU-H2020 funded project TRUE (TRansition paths to sUustainable legume-based systems in Europe) was designed from the perspective that the scientific knowledge and societal desire for more-sustainable legume-supported agri-food systems does exist, but that co-innovation among supply chain actors to identify, realise and prioritise transition paths remains to be achieved. TRUE is therefore aimed at working with the full-range of stakeholders across the supply chain, including civil society bodies, to identify and enable routes (transition paths) to help realise more-sustainable legume-supported agri-food systems.

Some policies are mentioned but not as primary goal of the project.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210171/factsheet/en>
<https://www.true-project.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210171/results/en>

There are 2 peer reviewed articles and there are some deliverables.

Results and recommendations

There are no final results yet because the project is ongoing just some deliverables with reports and videos. Also no recommendations have been made so far.

AGRISPIN

Addressed topics

Innovation policies

Coordinator

LANDBRUG & FODEVARER F.M.B.A. (Denmark)

Full name

Space for Agricultural Innovation

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

€ 1,994,306.75

Start/End

2015-2017

Participants

1. ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING, Netherlands
2. UNIVERSITAET HOHENHEIM, Germany
3. VERBAND DER LANDWIRTSCHAFTSKAMMERNEV, German
4. BOERENBONDVERENIGING VOOR INNOVATIEVE PROJECTEN VZW, Belgium
5. LATVIJAS LAUKU KONSULTACIJU UN IZGLITIBAS CENTRS, Latvia
6. Association de Coordination Technique Agricole, France
7. REGIONE TOSCANA, Italy
8. PROAGRIA ETELA-POHJANMAA RY, Finland
9. INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE MOVEMENTS EUROPEAN UNION REGIONAL GROUP, Sweden
10. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
11. CENTRE DE COOPERATION INTERNATIONALE EN RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE POUR LEDEVELOPPEMENT - C.I.R.A.D. EPIC, France
12. FUNDATIA ADEPT TRANSILVANIA, Romania
13. AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece
14. FUNDACION HAZI FUNDAZIOA, Spain/ SEGES PS, Denmark

Main objective

The project name reflects the overall aim of this project: to strengthen support systems in creating space for innovative farmers. There is an EU-wide strategic orientation in policies towards an economic growth that relies on innovation, sustainability and smart knowledge systems. However, innovations are only successful when they have reached a broader acceptance within a social system. The European Innovation Partnership program aims to bridge the perceived gap between research and practice by stimulating multi actor processes from which relevant innovations might emerge. *Policies are mentioned in the project.*

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/194802/factsheet/en>

<https://agrispin.eu/>

Publications

<https://agrispin.eu/books/>

There is 1 book 'Stories From All Corners To Start With'.

Results and recommendations

The project has some results and recommendations at the follow webpage

[`https://agrispin.eu/results/`](https://agrispin.eu/results/).

RURACTION**Addressed topics**

Social capital, social processes/ Characterising rural, rural diversity

Coordinator

LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR RAUMBEZOGENE SOZIALFORSCHUNG (IRS) EV (Germany)

Full name

Social Entrepreneurship in Structurally Weak Rural Regions: Analysing Innovative Troubleshooters in Action

Funding scheme

MSCA-ITN-ETN - European Training Networks

Overall budget

2,529,895.32

Start/End

2016-2020

Participants

1. UNIWERSYTET IM. ADAMA MICKIEWICZA W POZNANIU, Poland
2. ROSKILDE UNIVERSITET, Denmark
3. UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK, Ireland
4. BALLYHOURA DEVELOPMENT CLG, Ireland
5. LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR LANDERKUNDE EV, Germany
6. PANEPISTIMIO AIGAIUO, Greece
7. OTELO EGEN, Austria
8. INSTITUTO UNIVERSITARIO DE LISBOA, Portugal

Main objective

The RURACTION research and training network focuses on problems in structurally weak rural regions in Europe and on the impact of social entrepreneurship regarding the development of innovative solutions to problems in rural regions. Rural regions are faced with major social and economic problems. In comparison to 'predominantly urban' or 'intermediate' regions, 'predominantly rural' regions, and particularly structurally weak rural regions, are economically less productive, which finds expression by a low level of gross domestic product. They provide a less extensive scope of desired goods and services, opportunities for higher education and qualified job offers. Not least, they are faced with recurring negative discourses. Against this background the respective regions experience a considerable loss of inhabitants and especially a brain drain of young and highly skilled people.

Policies are not mentioned in the objective but with the issues that the project is occupied I believe some policies will come up.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/205511/factsheet/en>
<https://ruraction.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/205511/results/en>

There is 1 peer reviewed article.

Results and recommendations

There are no results or recommendations yet the project is ongoing.

ROBUST

Addressed topics

Well-being, quality of life/Territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY (Netherlands)

Full name

Rural-Urban Outlooks: Unlocking Synergies

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

5,999,937.50

Starts/Ends

2017-2021

Participants

1. ABERYSTWYTH UNIVERSITY, United Kingdom
2. NODIBINAJUMS BALTIC STUDIES CENTRE, Latvia
3. TUKUMA NOVADA DOME, Latvia
4. UNIVERSITY OF GLOUCESTERSHIRE, United Kingdom
5. BUNDESANSTALT FUR AGRARWIRTSCHAFT UND BERGBAUERNFRAGEN, Austria
6. BUNDESANSTALT FUER BERGBAUERNFRAGEN, Austria
7. BUNDESANSTALT FUER BERGBAUERNFRAGEN, Austria
8. PLANUNG & FORSCHUNG POLICY RESEARCH & CONSULTANCY BERGS UND ISSA PARTNERSCHAFTSGESELLSCHAFT WIRTSCHAFTS-UND SOZIALWISSENSCHAFTLER, Germany
9. PERI-URBAN REGIONS PLATFORM EUROPE, Belgium
10. UNIVERSITAT DE VALENCIA, Spain
11. OIKOS SVETOVANJE ZA RAZVOJ DOO, Slovenia
12. LUONNONVARAKESKUS, Finland
13. HELSINGIN KAUPUNKI, Finland
14. REGIONALNA RAZVOJNA AGENCIJA - LJUBLJANSKE URBANE REGIJE ZAVOD, Slovenia

15. ICLEI EUROPEAN SECRETARIAT GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH), Germany
16. GEMEENTE EDE, Netherlands
17. COMISSAO DE COORDENACAO E DESENVOLVIMENTO REGIONAL DE LISBOA E VALE DO TEJO, Portugal
18. INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TECNICO, Portugal
19. UNIVERSITA DI PISA, Italy
20. GLOUCESTERSHIRE COUNTY COUNCIL, United Kingdom
21. REGIONALVERBAND FRANKFURTRHEINMAIN, Germany
22. PROVINCIA DI LUCCA, Italy
23. WELSH LOCAL GOVERNMENT ASSOCIATION, United Kingdom
24. REGIONALMANAGEMENT STEIRISCHER ZENTRALRAUM GMBH, Austria
25. FEDERACION VALENCIANA DE MUNICIPIOS Y PROVINCIAS, Spain

Main objective

Mutually beneficial relations along rural–periurban–urban trajectories have been shown to contribute substantially to smart, sustainable and inclusive growth agenda outlined in the EU 2020 strategy. Well-designed multi-level and multi-actor governance systems and processes are key to strengthening beneficial relations between rural, peri-urban and urban areas. A challenge for all involved actors is to contribute to a more balanced, future-oriented, sustainable and spatially integrated place-based development that takes into account synergies across rural–periurban–urban areas. Urbanisation processes can contribute positively to rural development by providing access to markets, services, and knowledge if carefully designed and managed. Rural areas, in turn, can offer urban centres amenities that contribute positively to urban quality of life, regional competitiveness and cultural identity.

Hence, the overall goal of ROBUST is: to advance our understanding of the interactions and dependencies between rural, peri-urban and urban areas, and to identify and promote policies, governance models and practices that foster mutually beneficial relations. Improved governance arrangements and synergies between rural, peri-urban and urban areas will contribute to Europe’s smart, sustainable and inclusive growth, maximizing the creation of rural jobs and value-added.

Policies are mentioned.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210506/factsheet/en>
<http://www.rural-urban.eu/>

Publications

<http://www.rural-urban.eu/publications>

There are 8 reports, 2 article and some newsletters and presentations.

Results and recommendations

The project is ongoing so there are no results or recommendations so far.

AgriLink

Addressed topics

Rural values and income

Coordinator

INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE (France)

Full name

Agricultural Knowledge: Linking farmers, advisors and researchers to boost innovation”

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

4,999,966.49

Starts/Ends:

2017-2021

Participants

1. CENTRUM DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO W BRWINOWIE, Poland
2. AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece
3. BOERENBONDVERENIGING VOOR INNOVATIEVE PROJECTEN VZW, Belgium
4. EKOTOXA SRO, Czechia
5. HIGHCLERE CONSULTING SRL, Romania
6. INRA TRANSFERT (S.A.), France
7. INSTITUTO NAVARRO DE TECNOLOGIAS E INFRAESTRUCTURAS AGROALIMENTARIAS SA, Spain/
8. NODIBINAJUMS BALTIC STUDIES CENTRE, Latvia
9. THE OPEN UNIVERSITY, United Kingdom
10. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
11. STIFTELSEN RURALIS INSTITUTT FOR RURAL- OG REGIONALFORSKNING, Norway
12. THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE, United Kingdom
13. UNIVERSIDADE DE TRAS-OS-MONTES E ALTO DOURO, Portugal
14. USTAV ZEMEDELSKE EKONOMIKY A INFORMACI, Czechia
15. VINIDEA SRL, Italy

Main objective

The aim of AgriLink is to better understand the role of advisory services in farmers’ decisions regarding various innovation areas (technological, process, marketing and social), and to enhance the contribution of advice to sustainable development of agriculture. The political context is characterised by high expectations for the contribution of advice to ecological transitions, as reflected in the various

policy briefs by the Strategic Working Group on Agriculture Knowledge and Innovation Systems, of the Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR-AKIS-SWG).

Policies are mentioned.

Website

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210165/factsheet/en>
- 2) <https://www.agrilink2020.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210165/results/en>

There are no publications just 1 conference proceeding.

Results and recommendations

There are no results or recommendations yet project is ongoing.

SafeWaterAfrica

Addressed topics

Well-being, quality of life

Coordinator

FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG E.V. (Germany)

Full name

Self-Sustaining Cleaning Technology for Safe Water Supply and Management in Rural African Areas

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

2,989,998.13

Starts/Ends

2016-2019

Participants

1. CONDIAS GMBH, Germany
2. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA, Italy
3. UNIVERSIDAD DE CASTILLA - LA MANCHA, Spain
4. ADVANCE CALL PTY LTD, South Africa
5. VIRTUAL CONSULTING ENGINEERS VCE, South Africa
6. TSHWANE UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, South Africa

- 7. STELLENBOSCH UNIVERSITY, South Africa
- 8. COUNCIL FOR SCIENTIFIC AND INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH, South Africa
- 9. SALOMON LDA, Mozambique

Main objective

The overall goal of the SafeWaterAfrica project is to research and develop an autonomous and decentralized "Made in Africa" water treatment system for rural and peri-urban areas which is highly efficient in the degradation of harmful pollutants, and which is accepted by the members of rural communities.

Policies are not mentioned.

Website

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/203389/factsheet/en>
- 2) <https://safewaterafrica.eu/en/home>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/203389/results/en>

There are 5 peer reviewed articles.

Results and recommendations

The project as results has upload 7 work packages at the follow link '<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/203389/reporting/en>'.

There are no recommendations.

RURECO

Addressed topics

Innovation policies/ Rural and circular and efficient resource use

Coordinator

BUREAU DE RECHERCHES GEOLOGIQUES ET MINIERES (France)

Full name

Institutions for Resilient Groundwater Dependent Rural Economies

Funding scheme

MSCA-IF-EF-ST - Standard EF

Overall budget

173,076.00

Starts/Ends

2018-2020

Participants

It's a small project so there are no participants.

Main objective

Groundwater is a strategic resource for modern economies worldwide; yet it is over-exploited at an alarming rate. New forms of governance are sought, in particular in rural areas with intensive agricultural irrigation where authorities lack the means to regulate large numbers of dispersed users. During the Fellowship, I will develop new understanding of strategies and institutional arrangements for increasing the resilience of groundwater dependent rural economies, and develop and test a methodology that support local actors to design collective solutions.

Policies are mentioned.

Website

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/209980/factsheet/en>

Publications

There are no publications project is ongoing.

Results and recommendations

There are no results or recommendations project is ongoing.

WATERPROTECT

Addressed topics

Rural and circular and efficient resource use

Coordinator VLAAMSE INSTELLING VOOR TECHNOLOGISCH ONDERZOEK N.V. (Belgium)

Full name

Innovative tools enabling drinking WATER PROTECTiON in rural and urban environments

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

4,997,006.50

Starts/Ends

2017-2020

Participants:

1. INAGRO, PROVINCIAAL EXTERN VERZELFSTANDIGD AGENTSCHAP IN PRIVAATRECHTELIJKE VORM VZW, Belgium
2. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK, Belgium
3. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
4. Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland, Denmark
5. UNIVERSITA CATTOLICA DEL SACRO CUORE, Italy
6. AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS, Spain
7. ASSOCIAZIONE PIACE CIBO SANO, Italy

8. PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT GEOLOGICZNY - PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY, Poland
9. VLAAMSE MAATSCHAPPIJ VOOR WATERVOORZIENING, Belgium
10. AGENZIA REGIONALE PER LA PREVENZIONE, L'AMBIENTE E L'ENERGIA DELL'EMILIA-ROMAGNA, Italy
11. KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET, Denmark
12. COMUNITAT D'USUARIS D'AIGUES DE LA VALL BAIXA I DELTA DEL LLOBREGAT, Spain
13. LANDBO LIMFJORD, Denmark
14. SKIVE KOMMUNE, Denmark
15. ASOCIATIA ECOLOGIC BAIA MARE, Romania
16. UNIVERSITATEA TEHNICA CLUJ-NAPOCA, Romania
17. THE EUROPEAN WATER PARTNERSHIP AISBL, Belgium
18. AIGUES DE BARCELONA, EMPRESA METROPOLITANA DE GESTIO DEL CICLE INTEGRAL DE L'AIGUA SA, Spain
19. INSTYTUT TECHNOLOGICZNO-PRZYRODNICZY. Poland
20. CONSORCI DEL PARC AGRARI DEL BAIX LLOBREGAT, Spain
21. ZACHODNIOPOMORSKI UNIWERSYTET TECHNOLOGICZNY W SZCZECINIE, Poland
22. GLANBIA IRELAND DESIGNATED ACTIVITY COMPANY, Ireland
23. UNIVERSITY OF ULSTER, United Kingdom
24. WEXFORD COUNTY COUNCIL, Ireland
25. EUROPEAN FEDERATION OF BOTTLED WATERS, Belgium
26. VLAAMSE MILIEUMAATSCHAPPIJ, Belgium

Main objective

The overarching objective of WATERPROTECT is to contribute to effective uptake and realisation of management practices and mitigation measures to protect drinking water resources. Therefore WATERPROTECT will create an integrative multi-actor participatory framework including innovative instruments that enable actors to monitor, to finance and to effectively implement management practices and measures for the protection of water sources. We propose seven case studies involving multiple actors in implementing good practices (land management, farming, product stewardship, point source pollution prevention) to ensure safe drinking water supply.

Policies are mentioned.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210492/factsheet/en>
- 2) <https://water-protect.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210492/results/en>

There are 12 documents and reports.

Results and recommendations

Project is ongoing so results and recommendations are expected.

BOND

Addressed topics

Rural values and income

Coordinator

COVENTRY UNIVERSITY (United Kingdom)

Full name

Bringing Organisations and Network Development to higher levels in the farming sector in Europe

Funding Scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

2,890,691.25

Starts/Ends

2017-2020

Participants

1. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY, Netherlands
2. UNIVERSIDAD DE CORDOBA, Spain
3. FOOD AND AGRICULTURE ORGANIZATION OF THE UNITED NATIONS FAO, Italy
4. ASOCIATA OBSTEASCA PROENTRANSE, Moldova
5. CONFEDERACAO NACIONAL DE AGRICULTURA, Portugal
6. THE LANDWORKERS ALLIANCE, United Kingdom
7. ASOCIATIA ECO RURALIS-IN SPRIJINULFERMIERIL OR ECOLOGICI SI TRADITIONALI, Romania/
8. NORSK LANDBRUKSSAMVIRKE SERVICEKONTOR AS, Norway
9. COORDINADORA DE AGRICULTORES Y GANADEROS DE LA COMUNIDAD VALENCIANA, Spain/
10. SINDICATO LABREGO GALEGO - COMISIONS LABREGAS, Spain/
11. VEDEGYLET EGYESULET, Hungary
12. KISLEPTEKU TERMEKELOALLITOK ES SZOLGALTATOK ORSZAGOS ERDEKKEPVISELETENEK EGYESULETE, Hungary
13. SPOLECZNY INSTYTUT EKOLOGICZNY, Poland
14. ASOCIACE MISTNICH POTRAVINOVYCH INICIATIV OPS, Czechia
15. FEDERATION NATIONALE DES COOPERATIVES D'UTILISATION DE MATERIEL AGRICOLE, France/

16. ASSOCIAZIONE NAZIONALE COOPERATIVE AGROITICOALIMENTARI PER LO SVILUPPO RURALE E COSTIERO, Italy.

Main objective

The aim of this project is to reach higher levels of organisation and networking, and develop a healthier, and more productive and harmonious farming sector in Europe for the long term. Within this perspective, BOND's general objective is to directly contribute to unleash, strengthen, and organise, the great potential for collective action and networking of individuals, groups and entities of farmers and land managers in selected countries across Europe, with a view to creating strong, dynamic and effective organizations that have a voice and a place in policy design.

Policies are mentioned.

Website

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/212218/factsheet/en>
- 2) <https://www.bondproject.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications.

Results and recommendations

Results and recommendations haven't been made yet, project is ongoing

CORE Organic Cofund

Addressed topics

Rural values and income

Coordinator

AARHUS UNIVERSITET (Denmark)

Full name

Coordination of European Transnational Research in Organic Food and Farming Systems Cofund

Funding scheme

ERA-NET-Cofund - ERA-NET Cofund

Overall budget

20,628,860.02

Starts/Ends

2016-2021

Participants

1. Bundesanstalt für Landwirtschaft und Ernährung, Germany
2. BUNDESMINISTERIUM FUER NACHHALTIGKEIT UND TOURISMUS, Austria
3. VLAAMSE GEWEST, Belgium/
4. CENTRE WALLON DE RECHERCHES AGRONOMIQUES, Belgium
5. Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries, Danish AgriFish Agency, Denmark

6. MAAELUMINISTEERIUM, Estonia/ 7. MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE AND FORESTRY, Finland
8. MINISTERE DE L'AGRICULTURE DE L'AGROALIMENTAIRE ET DE LA FORET, France
9. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France
10. Bundesministerium für Ernährung, Landwirtschaft und Verbraucherschutz, Germany
11. MINISTERO DELLE POLITICHE AGRICOLE ALIMENTARI E FORESTALI, Ital
12. MINISTERO DELL'ISTRUZIONE, DELL'UNIVERSITA' E DELLA RICERCA, Italy
13. AGRORESURSU UN EKONOMIKAS INSTITUTS, Latvia
14. MINISTERIE VAN ECONOMISCHE ZAKEN EN KLIMAAT, Netherlands
15. NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR WETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK, Netherlands
16. NORGES FORSKNINGSRAD, Norway
17. NARODOWE CENTRUM BADAN I ROZWOJU, Poland
18. Unitatea Executiva pentru Finantarea Invatamantului Superior, a Cercetarii, Dezvoltarii si Inovarii, Romania
19. MINISTRSTVO ZA KMETIJSTVO GOZDARSTVO IN PREHRANO Slovenia
20. INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACION Y TECNOLOGIA AGRARIA Y ALIMENTARIA OA MP, Spain
21. FORSKNINGSRÅDET FÖR MILJÖ, ARELLA NÄRINGAR OCH SAMHÄLLSBYGGANDE, Sweden/ 22. MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE AND FORESTRY, Turkey
23. EIDGENOESSISCHES DEPARTEMENT FUER WIRTSCHAFT, BILDUNG UND FORSCHUNG, Switzerlan
24. MINISTERIO DE ECONOMIA, INDUSTRIA Y COMPETITIVIDAD, Spain
25. BULGARIAN NATIONAL SCIENCE FUND, Bulgaria

Main objective

The present proposal for a CORE Organic Cofund will continue, to update and consolidate the series of transnational research calls that support a focused and coordinated research and innovation effort covering the most important challenges along the organic value chains, for example: increasing the organic production potentials, enhancing resource efficiency, and improving animal welfare. In addition this research and innovation plays a key role in adapting to the new EU regulations on Organic Farming.

Policies are not mentioned.

Website

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/205973/factsheet/en>
- 2) <https://projects.au.dk/coreorganiccofund/>

Publications

There are no publications yet, project is ongoing.

Results and recommendations

The project is ongoing, results and recommendations.

SUFISA

Addressed topics

Innovation policies/ Rural labour, jobs

Coordinator

KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN (Belgium)

Full name

Sustainable finance for sustainable agriculture and fisheries

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

4,863,662.50

Starts/Ends:

2015-2019

Participants

1. UNIVERSITA DI PISA, Italy
2. UNIVERSITY OF GLOUCESTERSHIRE, United Kingdom
3. FONDATION INSTITUT DE RECHERCHE POUR LE DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE ET LES RELATIONS INTERNATIONALES, France
4. ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA, Italy
5. UNIVERSITEIT HASSELT, Belgium
6. NODIBINAJUMS BALTIC STUDIES CENTRE, Latvia
7. UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA, Portugal
8. AARHUS UNIVERSITET, Denmark
9. AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece
10. HOCHSCHULE FUR NACHHALTIGE ENTWICKLUNG EBERSWALDE, Germany
11. UNIWERSYTET JAGIELLONSKI, Poland
12. EKONOMSKI FAKULTET, UNIVERZITET U BEOGRADU, Serbia
13. SYDDANSK UNIVERSITET, Denmark

Main objective

The purpose of SUFISA is to identify sustainable practices and policies in the agricultural, fish and food sectors that support the sustainability of primary producers in a context of multi-dimensional policy requirements, market uncertainties and globalisation.

Policies are mentioned.

Website

1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/193339/factsheet/en>

2) <https://www.sufisa.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/193339/results/en>

There are 9 peer reviewed articles.

Results and recommendations

Some results and policies briefs are at the follow link '<https://www.sufisa.eu/policybriefs/>'.

There were no recommendations.

PROIntensAfrica

Addressed topics

Rural values and income/ Territorial and policies

Coordinator

STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH (Netherlands)

Full name

Towards a long-term Africa-EU partnership to raise sustainable food and nutrition security in Africa

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

1,777,873.75

Starts/ends

2015-2017

Participants

1. FORUM FOR AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH IN AFRICA, GHANA, Ghana
2. CENTRE DE COOPERATION INTERNATIONALE EN RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE POUR LEDEVELOPPEMENT - C.I.R.A.D. EPIC, France
3. CONF. RESPONS. RECHER. AGRONOM.AFRIQ. DE L'OUEST & DU CENTRE, Senegal
4. UNIVERSITE CATHOLIQUE DE LOUVAIN, Belgium
5. CENTRE FOR COORDINATION OF AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT FOR SOUTHERN AFRICA, Botswana
6. SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET, Sweden
7. COUNCIL FOR SCIENTIFIC AND INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH, Ghana
8. AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH COUNCIL (ARC), South Africa
9. INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACAO CIENTIFICA TROPICAL, Portugal
10. LUONNONVARAKESKUS, Finland

11. AFRICAN FORUM FOR AGRICULTURAL ADVISORY SERVICES, Uganda
12. KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET, Denmark
13. THE REGISTERED TRUSTEES OF THE ASSOCIATION FOR STRENGTHENING AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH IN EASTERN AND CENTRAL AFRICA, Uganda
14. RHEINISCHE FRIEDRICH-WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAT BONN, Germany
15. UNIVERSITY OF GREENWICH, United Kingdom
16. CESKA ZEMEDELKA UNIVERZITA V PRAZE, Czechia
17. INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE INVESTIGACION Y TECNOLOGIA AGRARIA Y ALIMENTARIA OA MP, Spain
18. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
19. UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN, Austria
20. SZENT ISTVAN UNIVERSITY, Hungary
21. NIBIO - NORSK INSTITUTT FOR BIOKONOMI, Norway
22. INSTITUT DE L'ENVIRONNEMENT ET DE RECHERCHES AGRICOLES, Burkina Faso
23. INSTITUTO SUPERIOR DE AGRONOMIA, Portugal

Main objective

PROIntensAfrica intends to develop a proposal for a long term research and innovation partnership between Europe and Africa, focusing on the improvement of the food and nutrition security and the livelihoods of African farmers by exploring and exploiting the diversity of pathways to sustainable intensification of African agro-food systems. The exploration will include environmental, economic and social externalities along the whole value chains. PROIntensAfrica has the ambition to formulate a research and innovation agenda, identifying the domains in need for further research to realize the potential of African food systems.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/194806/factsheet/en>
- 2) <http://www.intensafrica.org/>

Publications

There are no publications just 18 articles and documents.

Results and recommendations

The PROIntensAfrica project was a CSA project and not a research project which could show, on the basis of the research results, socio-economic results and positive impact on livelihoods of the rural population in Africa. These results and impacts can be only expected if the partnership proposed will materialize and operational in the near future.

There are no recommendations.

SURE-Farm

Addressed topics

Policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY (Netherlands)

Full name

Towards SUsustainable and REsilient EU FARMing systems

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget:

4,875,616.25

Starts/Ends

2017-2021

Participants

1. KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN, Belgium
2. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK, Belgium
3. UNIVERSITY OF GLOUCESTERSHIRE, United Kingdom
4. ABERYSTWYTH UNIVERSITY, United Kingdom
5. ABERYSTWYTH UNIVERSITY, United Kingdom
6. SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET, Sweden
7. UNIVERSITETET I BERGEN, Norway
8. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France
9. UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID, Spain
10. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DELLA TUSCIA, Italy
11. EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZUERICH, Switzerland
12. LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUER AGRARENTWICKLUNG IN TRANSFORMATIONSOEKONOMIEN (IAMO), Germany
13. INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS, Romania
14. UNIVERSITY OF NATIONAL AND WORLD ECONOMY, Bulgaria
15. INSTYTUT ROZWOJU WSI I ROLNICTWA POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK, Poland
16. GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITAT GOTTINGENSTIFTUNG OFFENTLICHEN RECHTS, Germany

Main objective

Sure-Farm objectives are to: measure the determinants of resilience; improve farmers' risk-related decisions and management; assess farm demographic changes and their links to labour markets; evaluate the current policy framework and develop resilience enhancing policy options; make integrated long-term projections of farming system resilience; and identify pathways to implement a resilience enhancing environment.

Website

1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210494/factsheet/en>

2) <http://www.surefarmproject.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210494/results/en>

There is 1 peer reviewed article.

Results and recommendations

Key results at this stage of the project are (i) we created a framework which enables to provide an 'elaborated diagnosis' of the resilience of a farming system, e.g. eventually simultaneously finding a resilience-constraining environment for social and economic challenges and a resilience-enhancing environment for environmental challenges, or vice versa; (ii) five scenarios have been elaborated in the context of resilience; (iii) we found that most CS perceive generational renewal as a future challenge for the resilience of farming systems; (iv) we concluded that current policies and strategies mostly contribute to robustness and adaptability, but less to transformability; and (v) we found that modelling tools are available to assess robustness and adaptability, but less for transformability.

There are no recommendations.

SUPREMA

Addressed topics

Innovation policies

Coordinator

STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH (Netherlands)

Full name

SUpport for Policy RElevant Modelling of Agriculture

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget:

999,823.75

Starts/Ends

2018-2020

Participants

1. EUROPEAN CENTER FOR AGRICULTURAL, REGIONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY RESEARCH, EURO CARE, Germany
2. JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI, Germany
3. SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET, Swede
4. JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE- EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Belgium
5. INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FUER ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE, Austria

6. UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID, Spain

Main objective

The project has four coherent objectives: 1) A SUPREMA roadmap of future directions for modelling will be developed. 2) An enhanced and strengthened SUPREMA model family will be created. 3) Future directions of modelling in agriculture will be explored and tested. 4) A SUPREMA meta-platform will be established, to share and discuss the findings of the work with existing model platforms, research communities, and policy makers.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/212216/factsheet/en>
- 2) <https://www.suprema-project.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications just some deliverables
'<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/212216/results/en>'.

Results and recommendations

SUPREMA defined the needs for future model development and also prioritised model improvements and model related actions. An early stock-taking in SUPREMA identified challenges which might be covered during the project, including (i) coverage of future global food demand (trade, generation of income and its distribution across different income groups; (ii) environmental constraints, like future water and land availability and quality, and climate mitigation and adaptation; (iii) strategies towards a more bio-based economy; and (iv) increasing concentration and the ongoing structural change in the food value chain are also determining income at farm level. There were no further recommendations.

LANDSUPPORT

Addressed topics

Territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI NAPOLI FEDERICO II (Italy)

Full name

Development of Integrated Web-Based Land Decision Support System Aiming towards the Implementation of Policies for Agriculture and Environment

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

6,999,771.25

Starts/Ends

2018-2021

Participants

1. ARIESPACE SRL, Italy

2. BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER - CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION, Spain
3. UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN, Austria
4. CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE, Italy
5. CROPS FOR THE FUTURE RESEARCH CENTRE, Malaysia
6. INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH IN THE DRY AREAS, Lebanon
7. FELSÖBBOKU TANULMANYOK INTEZETE, Hungary
8. ISTITUTO SUPERIORE PER LA PROTEZIONE E LA RICERCA AMBIENTALE, Italy
9. RASDAMAN GMBH, Germany
10. JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE- EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Belgium
11. REGIONE CAMPANIA, Italy
12. PANNON EGYETEM, Hungary
13. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI MILANO, Italy
14. ZALA MEGYEI ONKORMANYZATA, Hungary
15. CMAST, Belgium
16. ACTEON SARL, France
17. UMWELTBUNDESAMT GESELLSCHAFT MIT BESCHRANKTER HAFTUNG (UBA GMBH), Austria
18. GOZDARSKI INSTITUT SLOVENIJE, Slovenia

Main objective

The objective of LANDSUPPORT is the construction of a web-based smart geoSpatial Decision Support System (S-DSS), which shall provide a powerful set of tools devoted to (i) support sustainable agriculture/forestry, (ii) evaluate trade-off between land uses (including spatial planning) and (iii) contribute to implementation, impact and delivery of about 20 European land policies and also selected 2030 UN Sustainable Development Goals including climate change resilience goals and the key SDG 15.3 "achieving a land degradation-neutral world".

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/215938/factsheet/en>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/215938/results/en>

There is 1 peer reviewed article.

Results and recommendations

There are no results or recommendations so far project is ongoing.

AGRICORE

Addressed topics

Territorial approaches and policies/ Rural and digital

Coordinator

OPTIMIZACION ORIENTADA A LA SOSTENIBILIDAD SL (Spain)

Full name

Agent-based support tool for the development of agriculture policies

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

3,937,248.75

Starts/Ends

2019-2023

Participants

1. ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS, Greece
2. AXIA INNOVATION UG, Germany
3. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PARMA, Italy
4. STAM SRL, Italy
5. INSTYTUT AGROFIZYKI POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK, Poland
6. AYESA ADVANCED TECHNOLOGIES SA, Spain
7. COOPERATIVAS AGRO-ALIMENTARIAS DE ANDALUCIA, Spain
8. AKDENIZ UNIVERSITY, Turkey
9. UNIWERSYTET TECHNOLOGICZNO PRZYRODNICZY IM JANA I JEDRZEJA SNIADKICH W BYDGOSZCZY, Poland

Main objective

The AGRICORE project proposes a novel tool for improving the current capacity to model policies dealing with agriculture by taking advantage of latest progresses in modelling approaches and ICT. Specifically, the AGRICORE tool will be built as an agent-based approach where each farm is to be modelled as an autonomous decision-making entity which individually assesses its own context and makes decisions on the basis of its current situation and expectations.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223202/factsheet/en>

Publications

There are no publications yet project is ongoing.

Results and recommendation

There are no results or recommendations.

BESTMAP

Addressed topics

Policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS (United Kingdom)

Full name

Behavioral, Ecological and Socio-economic Tools for Modelling Agricultural Policy

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

3,995,811.25

Starts/Ends

2019-2023

Participants

1. HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUR UMWELTFORSCHUNG GMBH – UFZ, Germany
2. UNIVERZITA PALACKEHO V OLOMOUCI, Czechia
3. INSTITUT FUER WELTWIRTSCHAFT, Germany
4. CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION ECOLOGICA Y APLICACIONES FORESTALES, Spain
5. UNITED KINGDOM RESEARCH AND INNOVATION, United Kingdom
6. THE RURAL INVESTMENT SUPPORT FOR EUROPE FOUNDATION, Belgium
7. BIOSENSE INSTITUTE - RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN BIOSYSTEMS, Serbia
8. PENSOFT PUBLISHERS, Bulgaria
9. DEPARTAMENT D'AGRICULTURA, RAMADERIA, PESCA I ALIMENTACIO, Spain
10. MUNDIALIS GMBH & CO KG, Germany
11. CAMBRIDGE ECONOMETRICS LIMITED, United Kingdom

Main objective:

BESTMAP will develop a new modelling framework using insights from behavioral theory, linking existing economic modelling with individual-farm Agent-Based Models. Using these new modular and customizable tools BESTMAP will quantitatively model, map and monitor co-designed policy scenarios' impacts on the environment, climate system, delivery of ESS, as well as socio-economic metrics (e.g. jobs).

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223207/factsheet/en>

Publications

There are no publications yet project is ongoing.

Results and recommendation

There are no results or recommendations project is ongoing.

MIND-STEP

Addressed topics

Innovation policies

Coordinator

STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH (Netherlands)

Full name

Modelling Individual Decisions to Support The European Policies related to agriculture

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

4,000,000.00

Starts/Ends

2019-2023

Participants

1. RHEINISCHE FRIEDRICH-WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAT BONN, Germany
2. INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FUER ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE, Austria
3. LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUER AGRARENTWICKLUNG IN TRANSFORMATIONSOEKONOMIEN (IAMO), Germany
4. JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI, Germany
5. UNIVERSITA CATTOLICA DEL SACRO CUORE, Italy
6. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY, Netherlands
7. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France
8. NIBIO - NORSK INSTITUTT FOR BIOKONOMI, Norway
9. JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE- EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Belgium
10. GEONARDO ENVIRONMENTAL TECHNOLOGIES LTD, Hungary

Main objective

MIND STEP will improve exploitation of available agricultural and biophysical data and will include the individual decision making (IDM) unit in policy models. Based on a common data framework MIND STEP will develop IDM models, including agent-based models, focusing on different topics in an integrated manner in different regional case studies.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223209/factsheet/en>

Publications

There are no publications project is ongoing.

Results and recommendation

There are no results and recommendations project is ongoing.

SiEUGreen

Addressed topics

Smart villages, communities/ Rural and circular and efficient resource use

Coordinator

NORGES MILJO-OG BIOVITENSKAPLIGE UNIVERSITET (Norway)

Full name

Sino-European innovative green and smart cities”

Funding scheme

IA - Innovation action

Overall budget

8,377,867.50

Starts/Ends

2018-2021

Participants

1. NIBIO - NORSK INSTITUTT FOR BIOKONOMI, Norway
2. THE INSTITUTE OF VEGETABLES AND FLOWERS CHINESE ACADEMY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES, China
3. CREVIS SPRL, Belgium
4. NORDREGIO, Sweden
5. EMETRIS SYMVOULOI ANAPTYXIS ORGANOSIS KAI PLIROFORIKIS AE, Greece
6. AARHUS KOMMUNE, Denmark
7. VILABS (CY) LTD, Cyprus
8. OKYS LTD, Bulgaria
9. BEIJING ECO-CREATIVE AGRICULTURAL SERVICE ALLIANCE, China
10. BEIJING GREEN VALLEY SPROUTS CO LTD, China
11. SCANDINAVIAN WATER TECHNOLOGY AS, Norway
12. HATAY METROPOLITAN MUNICIPALITY, Turkey
13. RURAL DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE CHINESE ACADEMY OF SOCIAL SCIENCES, China
14. Sampas Bilisim Ve Iletisim Sistemleri Sanayi Ve Ticaret A.S., Turkey
15. HUNAN HENGKAI ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY INVESTMENT CO.LTD, China
16. SEECON INTERNATIONAL GMBH, Switzerland
17. LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR GEMUSE- UND ZIERPFLANZENBAU GROSSBEEREN/ERFURT EV, Germany
18. BEIJING PHOTON SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY CO., LTD, China

Main objective

SiEUGreen aspires to enhance the EU-China cooperation in promoting urban agriculture for food security, resource efficiency and smart, resilient cities. Building on the model of zero-waste and circular economy, it will demonstrate how technological and societal innovation in urban agriculture can have a positive impact on society and economy, by applying novel resource-efficient agricultural

techniques in urban and peri-urban areas, developing innovative approaches for social engagement and empowerment and investigating the economic, environmental and social benefits of urban agriculture.

Websites

1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/212412/factsheet/en>

Publications

There are no publications yet.

Results and recommendation

There are no results or recommendations.

NEWBIE

Addressed topics

Well-being, quality of life/ Rural labour rural jobs

Coordinator

STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH (Netherlands)

Full name

New Entrant netWork: Business models for Innovation, entrepreneurship and resilience in European agriculture

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

1,995,040.75

Starts/Ends

2018-2021

Participants

1. THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE, United Kingdom
2. KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN, Belgium
3. UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA, Portugal
4. FACHHOCHSCHULE SUDWESTFALEN, Germany
5. UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI, Slovenia
6. RENETA (RESEAU NATIONAL DES ESPACES-TEST AGRICOLES), France
7. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
8. SDRUJENIE-BISNES INKUBATOR-GOTSE DELCHEV, TSENTAR ZA PODPOMAGANE NA PREDPRIEMACHESTVOTO, Bulgaria
9. BUND DER DEUTSCHEN LANDJUGEND E.V. (BDL), Germany

Main objective

The NEWBIE Network has been designed to address the significant challenge of enabling new entrants to successfully establish sustainable farm businesses in Europe. The NEWBIE network will facilitate the development and dissemination of new business models, including new entry models, to the full range of new entrants - from successors to complete newcomers to the agricultural sector.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/212394/factsheet/en>
- 2) <http://www.newbie-academy.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/212394/results/en>

There is 1 non peer reviewed article.

Results and recommendation

There are no results and recommendations project is ongoing.

LIVERUR
Addressed topics
Rural values and income/ Innovation policies

Coordinator

FUNDACION UNIVERSITARIA SAN ANTONIO (Spain)

Full name

Living Lab research concept in Rural Areas

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

4,107,005.00

Starts/Ends

2018-2021

Participants

1. FUNDO REGIONAL PARA A CIENCIA E TECNOLOGIA, Portugal
2. INSTITUTE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT, Greece
3. UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI, Slovenia
4. SOGESCA (s.r.l.), Italy
5. WIRELESSINFO, Czechia
6. ASOCIACION PARA EL DESARROLLO RURAL INTEGRADO DE LOS MUNICIPIOS DE LA VEGA DEL SEGURA, Spain
7. CESIE, Italy
8. BUNDESANSTALT FUR AGRARWIRTSCHAFT UND BERGBAUERNFRAGEN, Austria

9. TR ASSOCIATES LTD, Malta
10. ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA, Latvia
11. ZAFER KALKINMA AJANSI, Turkey
12. DAR MARGOUM OUEDHREF, Tunisia
13. UNIONE DEI COMUNI DEL TRASIMENO, Italy
14. COMMISSARIAT A L'ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVES, France
15. E35 FONDAZIONE PER LA PROGETTAZIONE INTERNAZIONALE, Italy
16. CLEOPA GMBH, Germany
17. CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE PROVENCE ALPES COTE AZUR, France
18. CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DES PAYS DE LA LOIRE, France
19. WELLNESS TELECOM SL, Spain
20. UHLAVA OPS, Czechia
21. ZENTRUM FUR SOZIALE INNOVATION GMBH, Austria
22. REGIONALMANAGEMENT BURGENLAND GMBH, Austria
23. CHAMBRE REGIONALE D'AGRICULTURE DE BRETAGNE, France

Main objective

LIVERUR identifies Living Labs as innovative business models that are currently developing in 13 rural piloting areas across Europe, Africa and Asia. The project undertakes a socio-economic analysis to describe and benchmark differences between the new Living Lab methodologies and more traditional entrepreneurial approaches. The basis for the strategic development of a rural Living Lab is to establish an association of stakeholders, users, policy makers, businesses and researchers to ensure sustainability.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/214746/factsheet/en>
- 2) <https://liverur.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/214746/results/en>

There is 1 peer reviewed article.

Results and recommendation

There are no results and recommendations project is ongoing.

RUBIZMO
Addressed topics
Rural values and income

Coordinator

RISE RESEARCH INSTITUTES OF SWEDEN AB (Sweden)

Full name

Replicable business models for modern rural economies

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

3,928,852.04

Starts/Ends

2018-2021

Participants

1. GREENOVATE EUROPE, Belgium
2. IFAU APS, Denmark
3. INVESTORNET-GATE2GROWTH APS, Denmark
4. LEIBNIZ INSTITUT FUER AGRARTECHNIK UND BIOOEKONOMIE E V, Germany
5. ASOCIATIA ROMANA PENTRU AGRICULTURA DURABILA, Romania
6. CLUSTER VIOOIKONOMIAS KAI PERIVALLONTOS DYTIKIS MAKEDONIAS, Greece
7. ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA, Italy
8. UNIWERSYTET PRZYRODNICZY WE WROCLAWIU, Poland
9. IRISH RURAL LINK CO-OPERATIVE SOCIETY LIMITED, Ireland
10. ZABALA INNOVATION CONSULTING (S.A.), Spain
11. EUROPEAN SCIENCE COMMUNICATION INSTITUTE (ESCI) GGMBH, Germany
12. COOPERATIVAS AGRO-ALIMENTARIAS DE ESPANA U DE COOP SOCIEDAD COOPERATIVA, Spain
13. SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET, Sweden/ 14. GREENFLEX, France

Main objective

RUBIZMO will identify business models with high potential for empowering rural communities to take advantage of the opportunities arising from improved value chain optimisation. It will directly support the creation of sustainable jobs and growth in rural economies, supporting a multi-actor approach for generation of shared-value. Ultimately, the project looks to contribute to rural development in Europe, supporting the Europe 2020 Strategy for Smart, Sustainable and Inclusive Growth, as well as supporting Regional and Rural Development policy

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/214741/factsheet/en>
- 2) <https://rubizmo.eu/>

Publications

<https://rubizmo.eu/publications>

As publications there are policy recommendations.

Results and recommendation

There are no results. Policy recommendation have been made '<https://rubizmo.eu/publications>'.

RURALIZATION**Addressed topics**

Generations/ Social capital, social processes

Coordinator

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT (Netherlands)

Full name

The opening of rural areas to renew rural generations, jobs and farms

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

5,995,904.00

Starts/Ends

2019-2023

Participants

1. TERRE DE LIENS, France
2. ILS - INSTITUT FUR LANDES- UND STADTENTWICKLUNGSFORSCHUNG gGMBH, Germany
3. XARXA PER A LA CONSERVACIO DE LA NATURA, Spain
4. UNIWERSYTET WROCLAWSKI, Poland
5. SHARED ASSETS LIMITED, United Kingdom
6. MAGYAR TUDOMANYOS AKADEMIA TARSADALOMTUDOMANYI KUTATOKOZPONT, Hungary
7. KULTURLAND EG, Germany
8. UNIVERSITA DELLA CALABRIA, Italy
9. CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL, Spain
10. CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS, France
11. PRO VERTES ZARTKORUEN MUKODONONPROFIT RESZVENYTARSASAG, Hungary
12. DEBRECENI EGYETEM, Hungary
13. DE LANDGENOTEN, Belgium
14. TURUN YLIOPISTO, Finland
15. NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY, Ireland
16. ASOCIATIA ECO RURALIS-IN SPRIJINULFERMIERIL OR ECOLOGICI SI TRADITIONALI, Romania
17. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland

Main objective

RURALIZATION will develop a novel perspective for rural areas to trigger a process of ruralisation as counterforce to urbanisation, that is, a development towards a new rural frontier offering new rural generations stimulating economic and social opportunities. The project will identify rural areas that do better than others and explore the rural dreams of new generations through foresight. Innovations will focus on facilitating generation renewal in farming and rural communities.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223213/factsheet/en>
- 2) <http://www.ruralization.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications project is ongoing.

Results and recommendation

There are no results and recommendations yet project is ongoing.

PoliRural

Addressed topics

Policy performance evaluation/ Well-being, quality of life

Coordinator

CESKA ZEMEDELSKA UNIVERZITA V PRAZE (Czechia)

Full name

Future Oriented Collaborative Policy Development for Rural Areas and People

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

5,999,875.28

Starts/Ends

2019-2022

Participants

1. CESKE CENTRUM PRO VEDU A SPOLECNOST, Czechia
2. PLAN4ALL ZS, Czechia
3. NUVIT, (Z.U.), Czechia
4. SLOVENSKA POLNOHOSPODARSKA UNIVERZITA V NITRE, Slovakia
5. AGROINSTITUT NITRA STATNY PODNIK, Slovakia
7. MESTO NITRA, Slovakia
8. KAJO SRO, Slovakia

9. OBCIANSKE ZDRUZENIE VIDIECKY PARLAMENT, Slovakia
10. BALTIC OPEN SOLUTIONS CENTER, Latvia
11. VIDZEMES PLANOSANAS REGIONS, Latvia
12. AGRORESURSU UN EKONOMIKAS INSTITUTS, Latvia
13. LATVIJAS LAUKU FORUMS, Latvia
14. NEUROPUBLIC AE PLIROFORIKIS & EPIKOINONION, Greece
15. GAIA EPICHEIREIN ANONYMI ETAIREIA PSIFIAKON YPIRESION, Greece
16. AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS, Greece
17. PERIFEREIA STEREAS ELLADAS, Greece
18. SOCIEDADE PORTUGUESA DE INOVACAO CONSULTADORIA EMPRESARIAL E FOMENTO DA INOVACAO SA, Portugal
19. MIGAL GALILEE RESEARCH INSTITUTE LTD, Israel
20. 21C CONSULTANCY LIMITED, United Kingdom
21. INNOVAGRITECH SRL, Italy
22. ASPLAN VIAK INTERNET AS, Norway
23. CREHAN, KUSANO & ASSOCIATES, Belgium
24. THE JOINT INSTITUTE FOR INNOVATION POLICY AISBL, Belgium
25. VLAAMSE INSTELLING VOOR TECHNOLOGISCH ONDERZOEK (N.V.), Belgium
26. AG FUTURA TECHNOLOGII DOOEL SKOPJE, North Macedonia
27. CLUB OF OSSIACH, Austria
28. EMPRESA DE TRANSFORMACION AGRARIA SA, Spain
29. FUNDACION SOCIALINNOVLABS, Spain
30. OLIVA QUESADA ANTONIO, Spain
31. LOYTTY TUULA-MAIJA, Finland
32. HAMEEN AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY, Finland
33. EUROPEAN RURAL DEVELOPMENT NETWORK, Poland
34. THE NATIONAL MICROELECTRONICS APPLICATIONS CENTRE LTD, Ireland
35. MURGIA PIU - SOCIETA CONSORTILE ARL, Italy
36. CONFAGRICOLTURA FOGGIA - UNIONE PROV. AGRICOLTORI DI FOGGIA, Italy
37. ZDRUZENIE PLATFORMA ZA ZELEN RAZVOJSKOPJE, North Macedonia

Main objective

Changes in rural areas, such as depopulation, land abandonment and the loss of biodiversity, may proceed very slowly yet are often irreversible. Policymakers can steer these developments in order to reduce their negative impacts but this requires knowing whether current policy instruments are effective, who is benefiting from them and in what measure, what driving forces will be most

influential and how they will affect people, planet, profits and land-use. PoliRur will leave decision makers at different levels of government better equipped to tackle existing and emerging rural challenges, rural populations more empowered and rural areas more resilient.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223230/factsheet/en>
- 2) <https://polirural.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications yet, project has just started.

Results and recommendation

There are no results or recommendations yet, project has just started.

DESIRA
Addressed topics
Rural and digital/ Social capital, social processes

Coordinator

UNIVERSITA DI PISA (Italy)

Full name

Digitisation: Economic and Social Impacts in Rural Areas

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

4,994,156.25

Starts/Ends

2019-2023

Participants

1. THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE, United Kingdom
2. FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG, Switzerland
3. SISTEMA GMBH, Austria
4. UNIVERSIDAD DE CORDOBA, Spain
5. CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE, Italy
6. SUSTAINABLE IRELAND CO-OPERATIVE SOCIETY LTD, Ireland
7. SOCIEDAD ARAGONESA DE GESTION AGROAMBIENTAL SL, Spain
8. ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE POUR L'INFORMATION SUR LE DEVELOPPEMENT LOCAL, Belgium
9. ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA, Latvia
10. KARLSRUHER INSTITUT FUER TECHNOLOGIE, Germany

11. AMIGO SRL, Italy
12. UNIVERSITEIT GENT, Belgium
13. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
14. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY, Netherlands
15. NODIBINAJUMS BALTIC STUDIES CENTRE, Latvia
16. HRVATSKA POLJOPRIVREDNO-SUMARSKA SAVJETODAVNA SLUZBA, Croatia
17. MINISTARSTVO POLJOPRIVREDE, Croatia
18. UNIWERSYTET LODZKI, Poland
19. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK, Belgium
20. JYVASKYLAN YLIOPISTO, Finland
21. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France
22. ATHINA-EREVNITIKO KENTRO KAINOTOMIAS STIS TECHNOLOGIES TIS PLIROFORIAS, TON EPIKOINONION KAI TIS GNOSIS, Greece
23. DEBRECENI EGYETEM, Hungary
24. PROGRAMME FOR THE ENDORSEMENT OF FOREST CERTIFICATION SCHEMES ITALIA, Italy
25. FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG (E.V.), Germany

Main objective

DESIRA will develop the concept of Socio-Cyber-Physical Systems to advance understanding of the impact of digitisation in rural areas, linking analysis directly to the United Nation’s Sustainable Development Goals. Operationalising the Responsible Research and Innovation approach, DESIRA will enrol agriculture, forestry and rural stakeholders in co-developing scenarios and policies in Living Labs established in 20 European Regions, and a Rural Digitization Forum gathering 250 stakeholders from all Europe. A Virtual Research Environment tailored to the purposes of the project will connect all participants and allow to increase substantially the interaction within the network.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223227/factsheet/en>

Publications

There are no publications, yet project has just started.

Results and recommendation

There are no results and recommendations yet, project has just started.

PEGASUS

Addressed topics

Territorial approaches and policies/ Policy performance evaluation

Coordinator

INSTITUTE FOR EUROPEAN ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY, LONDON (United Kingdom)

Full name

Public Ecosystem Goods And Services from land management - Unlocking the Synergies

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

3,007,800.00

Starts/Ends

2015-2018

Participants

1. UNIVERSITY OF GLOUCESTERSHIRE, United Kingdom
2. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
3. VEREIN FUER LANDLICHE STRUKTURFORSCHUNG EV, Germany
4. CONSIGLIO PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA E L'ANALISI DELL'ECONOMIA AGRARIA, Italy
5. USTAV ZEMEDELSKE EKONOMIKY A INFORMACI, Czechia
6. JRC -JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE- EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Belgium
7. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France
8. BUNDESANSTALT FUR AGRARWIRTSCHAFT UND BERGBAUERNFRAGEN, Austria
9. BUNDESANSTALT FUER BERGBAUERNFRAGEN Austria
10. UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA, Portugal
11. UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI, Slovenia
12. MITTETULUNDUSUHING OKOLOOGILISTE TEHNOLOGIATE KESKUS, Estonia
13. Euromontana, France
14. STICHTING BIRDLIFE EUROPE, Netherlands

Main objective

PEGASUS will develop innovative, practical ways of making PG and ESS concepts accessible and operational: it will identify how, where and when cost-effective mechanisms and tools for policy, business and practice can most effectively be applied, increasing the sustainability of primary production in pursuit of the EU2020 vision of 'smart, sustainable and inclusive growth'.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/193257/factsheet/en>
- 2) <http://pegasus.ieep.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/193257/results/en>

There are 3 peer reviewed articles 8 conference proceedings and 11 other publications.

Results and recommendation:

The PEGASUS policy recommendations highlight the importance of providing support to and encouraging a variety of actors, institutions and value chains to agree on priorities and then cooperate on joint actions across a territory or along a supply chain.

PROVIDE

Addressed topics

Well-being, quality of life

Coordinator

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA (Italy)

Full name

PROVIDing smart DELivery of public goods by EU agriculture and forestry

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

2,991,436.25

Starts/Ends

2015-2018

Participants

1. LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG (ZALF) (e. V.), Germany
2. UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN, Austria
3. STICHTING VU, Netherlands
4. UNIVERSIDAD DE CORDOBA, Spain
5. THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE, United Kingdom
6. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France
7. LUONNONVARAKESKUS, Finland
8. TALLINN UNIVERSITY, Estonia
9. ISTITUTO DELTA ECOLOGIA APPLICATA SRL, Italy
10. UNIVERSITATEA ALEXANDRU IOAN CUZA DIN IASI, Romania
11. INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS, Bulgaria
12. UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI, Poland
13. TECHNOLOGICKE CENTRUM AKADEMIE VED CESKE REPUBLIKY, Czechia

Main objective

The objective of the project is to provide a conceptual basis, evidence, tools and improved incentive and policy options to support the ""smart"" provision of public goods by the EU agriculture and forestry ecosystems, in the light of trade-offs and conflicts brought about by prospective intensification scenarios, using a transdisciplinary approach.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/197077/factsheet/en>
- 2) <http://www.provide-project.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/197077/results/en>

There are 8 peer reviewed articles and 1 conference proceeding.

Results and recommendation

The results confirm the positive willingness to pay by citizens for public goods produced by the European agriculture and forestry. The amount that citizens are willing to pay for public goods provision very much differs depending on the public good, but also across areas and groups, showing the importance of segmentation of different demand components. The result also show that the current amount of money devoted by the CAP to public good provision is generally considered as acceptable by EU households (with more than 60% of citizens agreeing with the current expenditure devoted to that aim).

Bottom-up approaches, such as collective actions, can have high potential, but they are strongly dependent on the commitment of the partners united under the approach and therefore only recommendable if compliance to the fundamental principles of collaboration are guaranteed.

CONSOLE**Addressed topics**

Well-being, quality of life/ Rural and climate

Coordinator

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA (Italy)

Full name

CONtract SOLutions for Effective and lasting delivery of agri-environmental-climate public goods by EU agriculture and forestry

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

4,999,998.75

Starts/Ends

2019-2022

Participants:

1. REGIONE EMILIA ROMAGNA, Italy
2. CONSORZIO DI BONIFICA DELLA ROMAGNA OCCIDENTALE, Italy
3. UNIVERSITAET FUER BODENKULTUR WIEN, Austria
4. ECORYS BRUSSELS NV, Belgium

5. EUROPEAN LANDOWNERS ORGANIZATION, Belgium
6. SDRUZHENIE ASOTSIATSIYA NA AGROEKOLOGICHNITE ZEMEDELSKI PROIZVODITEL, Bulgaria
7. INSTITUTE OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS, Bulgaria
8. JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI, Germany
9. EVENOR TECH SL, Spain
10. ASOCIACION AGRARIA JOVENES AGRICULTORES DE SEVILLA, Spain
11. UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID, Spain
12. LUONNONVARAKESKUS, Finland
13. ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONS EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES, France
14. ASSOCIATION TRAME, France
15. CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS, France
16. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France
17. UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK, Ireland
18. UNIVERSITA DI PISA, Italy
19. ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA, Latvia
20. STICHTING VU, Netherlands
21. STICHTING HET WERELD NATUUR FONDS-NEDERLAND, Netherlands
22. SZKOLA GLOWNA GOSPODARSTWA WIEJSKIEGO, Poland
23. UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS, United Kingdom

Main objective

The objective of CONSOLE is to boost innovation in the lasting delivery of agri-environmental-climate public goods (AECPGs) by EU agriculture and forestry. The CONSOLE framework includes: a) a catalogue showcasing successful experiences and good practices in AECPGs contracting and cooperation models; b) improved AECPGs contracts solutions and their assessment for different levels of governance; c) a comprehensive guide to the process for the design of AECPGs contracts; d) documentation, training and supporting materials.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/223126/factsheet/en>

Publications

There are no publications yet project is ongoing.

Results and recommendation

There are no publications yet project is ongoing.

Contracts2.0

Addressed topics

Territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG (ZALF) e.V. (Germany)

Full name

Co-design of novel contract models for innovative agri-environmental-climate measures and for valorisation of environmental public goods

Funding scheme:

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

4,998,188,75

Starts/Ends

2019-2023

Participants:

1. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR NATUUR- EN BOSONDERZOEK, Belgium
2. ESSRG KFT, Hungary
3. THE UNIVERSITY COURT OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ABERDEEN, United Kingdom
4. CENTRE DE COOPERATION INTERNATIONALE EN RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE POUR LEDEVELOPPEMENT - C.I.R.A.D. EPIC, France
5. UNIVERSITA DI PISA, Italy
6. UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI, Slovenia
7. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY, Netherlands
8. UNIWERSYTET WARSZAWSKI, Poland
9. DEUTSCHE UMWELTHILFE EV, Germany
10. GROUPEMENT D'INTERET PUBLIQUE CENTRE DE RESSOURCES SUR LE PASTORALISME ET LA GESTION DE L'ESPACE, France
11. ORSEGI NEMZETI PARK IGAZGATOSAG, Hungary
12. BOERENNATUUR.NL, Netherlands
13. GOTTFRIED WILHELM LEIBNIZ UNIVERSITAET HANNOVER, Germany
14. NATURAL ENGLAND, United Kingdom
15. SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET, Sweden
16. COMUNIDAD DE MADRID, Spain
17. AGROBEHEERCENTRUM ECOKWADRAAT, Belgium
18. DEUTSCHER BAUERNVERBAND (E.V.), Germany
19. KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET, Denmark
20. UNIONE COMUNI GARFAGNANA, Italy
21. STIFTUNG RHEINISCHE KULTURLANDSCHAFT, Germany
22. BORNHOLMS REGIONSKOMMUNE, Denmark
23. BORNHOLMS LANDBRUG & FODEVARER, Denmark
24. HELICONIA S. COOP. MAD, Spain
25. STIFTUNG WESTFÄLISCHE KULTURLANDSCHAFT, Germany
26. UNIVERSIDAD AUTONOMA DE MADRID, Spain

Main objective

The overall objective of Contracts2.0 is to develop novel contract-based approaches to incentivise farmers for the increased provision of environmental public goods along with private goods using result-based, collective, land tenure and value chain approaches. Newly developed contract-based approaches are environmentally more effective, economically viable for farmers and support the longevity of contractual arrangements. Moreover, they enlarge farmers' entrepreneurial freedom and responsibility, and are better adapted to the relevant temporal and spatial scales of specific environmental goods.

Websites

1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/222534/factsheet/en>

Publications

There are no publications yet project is ongoing.

Results and recommendation

No results or recommendations have been made yet project is ongoing.

FAirWAY

Addressed topics

Policy performance evaluation/ Well-being, quality of life

Coordinator

STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH (Netherlands)

Full name

Farm systems that produce good Water quality for drinking water supplies

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget 4,999,865.00

Starts/Ends

2017-2021

Participants

1. HASKONINGDHV NEDERLAND BV, Netherlands
2. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY, Netherlands
3. BUREAU DE RECHERCHES GEOLOGIQUES ET MINIERES, France
4. LANDBRUG & FODEVARER (F.M.B.A.), Denmark
5. NORSK INSTITUTT FOR VANNFORSKNING, Norway
6. UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI, Slovenia
7. FONDAZIONE PER LO SVILUPPO SOSTENIBILE DEL MEDITERRANEO, Italy/
8. CLM ONDERZOEK EN ADVIES BV, Netherlands
9. JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI, Germany
10. INSTITUTO POLITECNICO DE COIMBRA, Portugal
11. UNIVERSITY OF LINCOLN, United Kingdom
12. INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE-DEZVOLTARE PENTRU PEDOLOGIE, AGROCHIMIE SI

- PROTECTIA MEDIULUI, Romania
 13. ARISTOTELIO PANEPHISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS, Greece
 14. AGRIFOOD AND BIOSCIENCES INSTITUTE, United Kingdom
 15. AARHUS UNIVERSITET, Denmark
 16. Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland, Denmark
 17. RIJKSINSTITUUT VOOR VOLKSGEZONDHEID EN MILIEU, Netherlands
 18. KMETIJSKO GOZDARSKA ZBORNICA SLOVENIJE KMETIJSKO GOZDARSKI ZAVOD MARIBOR, Slovenia
 19. RSK ADAS LIMITED, United Kingdom
 20. LANDWIRTSCHAFTSKAMMER NIEDERSACHSEN, Germany
 21. SCIENCEVIEW MEDIA BV, Netherlands

Main objective

The objective of FAIRWAY is to review policy, governance and farm water management approaches to protect drinking water resources in the EU and to identify and further develop innovative measures and governance approaches which will simultaneously increase the sustainability of agriculture.

Websites

- <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210505/factsheet/en>
<https://www.fairway-project.eu/>

Publications

- <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210505/results/en>

There are 3 peer reviewed articles.

Results and recommendation

The expected results of FAIRWAY are: i) increase the scientific understanding of the relationship between agriculture and drinking water protection, ii) increase the understanding for the barriers to practical implementing of measures and deliver innovative measures, tools and instruments to solve these barriers, iii) develop harmonized monitoring protocols and data-sets for monitoring of key farming practices and water quality, iv) develop effective governance approaches, and v) increase awareness and involvement of farmers and other citizens.

There are no recommendations so far, project is ongoing.

HNV-Link
Addressed topics
Rural labour, rural jobs/ Well-being quality of life/ Innovation policies

Coordinator

CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE HAUTES ETUDES AGRONOMIQUES MEDITERRANEENNES (France)

Full name

High Nature Value Farming: Learning, Innovation and Knowledge.

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

2,230,218.38

Starts/Ends

2016-2019

Participants

1. THE EUROPEAN FORUM ON NATURE CONSERVATION AND PASTORALISM, United Kingdom
2. UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA, Portugal
3. LOKALNA AKCIJSKA GRUPA LAG 5, Croatia
4. UNIVERSITATEA DE STIINTE AGRICOLE SI MEDICINA VETERINARA CLUJ NAPOCA, Romania
5. SOCIETY FOR TERRITORIAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROSPERITY, Bulgaria
6. LANSSTYRELSEN I VASTRA GOTALANDS LAN, Sweden
7. APPLICATIONS DES SCIENCES DE L'ACTION, France
8. INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY SLIGO – ITS, Ireland
9. PANEPISTIMIO THESSALIAS, Greece
10. HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO, Finland
11. CONSERVATOIRE DES ESPACES NATURELS DU LANGUEDOC ROUSSILLON ASSOCIATION, France
12. FUNDACION ENTRE TANTOS, Spain

Main objective

High nature value (HNV) farmland designates “those areas in Europe where agriculture is a major land use and where that agriculture supports, or is associated with, either a high species and habitat diversity or the presence of species of European conservation concern, or both”. They are an important component of European agriculture, notably in terms of biodiversity, cultural landscape, territorial cohesion, quality products and employment. However, abandonment, degradation, economic and social marginalisation are long-standing challenges for the associated farming systems which are still under considerable pressure. For national and local authorities, the European Union and the Common Agricultural Policy, and for stakeholders, the challenge is twofold: 1) to avoid further degradation and disappearance of HNV farming and increase their socio-economic viability: this could be done by collating, evaluating and disseminating innovations as tools for their development; 2) to maintain their “natural value”, i.e. the environmental services they provide to the society.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/200197/factsheet/en>

<http://www.hnmlink.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/200197/results/en>

There are 2 peer reviewed articles 3 conference proceedings and 2 other publications.

Results and recommendation

Creating an operational Atlas of our ten Learning Areas and an extensive Compendium of innovations for HNV farming were the targets of this Framing phase of the project, and are done! The network added value was important with open and vivid discussions and merging processes on the common methodology, participative meetings and cross-reading and commenting of outputs. Confronting local situations, common features and specific problems was a way to approach the European added value of this networking action. We have also put in place a multiscale dissemination and communication process - at the local level, national (in direction of the AKIs and the public) and also at the European level as such.

They are about to begin the second phase of the project, they may not have recommendations but the project is expected to be continued so the previous results, they came up with, will be used to the next phase.

Addressed topics

Rural values and income

Coordinator

STEINBEIS 2I GMBH (Germany)

Full name

Bringing added value to agriculture and forest sectors by closing the research and innovation divide

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

1,997,416.25

Start/End

2016-2018

Participants

1. INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY TRALEE, Ireland
2. UNIVERSITEIT GENT, Belgium
3. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
4. AGENCIA ANDALUZA DEL CONOCIMIENTO, Spain
5. BAY ZOLTAN ALKALMAZOTT KUTATASI KOZHASZNU NONPROFIT KFT, Hungary
6. GROWABRIC, Belgium
7. COOPERATIVAS AGRO-ALIMENTARIAS DE ANDALUCIA, Spain
8. ASOCIACION DE EMPRESAS FORESTALES Y PAISAJISTICAS DE ANDALUCIA, Spain
9. GABINETE DE INICIATIVAS EUROPEAS SA, Spain
10. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
11. FEIRMEOIRI AONTUITHE NA H-EIREANN IONTAOBIATHE TEORANTA LBG, Ireland
12. IBEC LIMITED*IRISH BUSINESS AND EMPLOYERS CONFEDERATION, Ireland
13. NEMZETI AGRARKUTATASI ES INNOVACIOS KOZPONT, Hungary
14. LENDULETBEN AZ AGRO-BIOTECH VALLALKOZAS-FEJLESZTESERT INNOVATIV NON-PROFIT ALAPITVANY, Hungary
15. PILZE-NAGY KERESKEDELMI ES SZOLGALTATO KFT, Hungary
16. STEINBEIS INNOVATION GGMBH, Germany

Main objective

AGRIFORVALOR will close the research and innovation divide by connecting practitioners from agriculture and forestry to research and academia as well as with associations and clusters, bio - industry, policy makers; business support organisations, innovation agencies and technology transfer intermediaries in multi-actor innovation partnership networks.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/200220/factsheet/en>

<http://www.agriforvalor.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/200220/results/en>

There are 4 other publications.

Results and recommendation

In the AGRIFORVALOR project an overview of valorisation techniques and good practice cases is

made facilitated through the sidestream value tool ([www. agriforvalor.eu/sidestreams](http://www.agriforvalor.eu/sidestreams)) making this information easily available for stakeholders such as foresters, farmers, the biomass processing industries, the bio-energy sector but also for the research sector. This tool will be made publically available 2 years after the project's end.

AgroCycle

Addressed topics

Rural and circular and efficient resource use

Coordinator

UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN (Ireland)

Full name

Sustainable techno-economic solutions for the agricultural value chain"

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

7,650,049.75

Start/End

2016-2019

Participants

1. UNIVERSITEIT GENT, Belgium
2. HARPER ADAMS UNIVERSITY, United Kingdom
3. FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG (E.V.), Germany
4. CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE, Italy
5. ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS, Greece
6. MEDUNARODNI CENTAR ZA ODRZIVI RAZVOJ ENERGETIKE VODA I OKOLISA, Croatia/
7. ELLINIKOS GEORGIKOS ORGANISMOS – DIMITRA, Greece
8. CONSIGLIO PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA E L'ANALISI DELL'ECONOMIA AGRARIA Italy
9. The National Non-Food Crops Centre, United Kingdom
10. CHINA AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY, China
11. NANJING UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, China
12. IRIS TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS, SOCIEDAD LIMITADA, Spain
13. TOMSA DESTIL SL, Spain
14. EXERGY LTD, United Kingdom
15. AXEB BIOTHECH SL, Spain
16. MASSTOCK ARABLE UK LIMITED, United Kingdom
17. RESET CARBON LIMITED, Hong Kong
18. CARTON BROS, Ireland
19. NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND MAYNOOTH, Ireland
20. EUROPEAN BIOMASS INDUSTRY ASSOCIATION, Belgium
21. COMITE EUROPEEN DES GROUPEMENTS DE CONSTRUCTEURS DU MACHINISME AGRICOLE, Belgium
22. CONFEDERATION INTERNATIONALE DES BETTERAVIERS EUROPEENS, Belgium

23. EKO KVARNER ORGANIZATION, Croatia
24. INSTITUTO TECNOLOGICO AGRARIO DE CASTILLA Y LEON, Spain
25. INNOVATION FOR AGRICULTURE, United Kingdom

Main objective

AgroCycle will convert low value agricultural waste into highly valuable products, achieving a 10% increase in waste recycling and valorisation by 2020.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/203391/factsheet/en>
<http://www.agrocycle.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/203391/results/en>
There are 9 peer reviewed articles.

Results and recommendation

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/203391/reporting/en>

AGROinLOG

Addressed topics

Rural and circular and efficient resource use

Coordinator

FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS
(Spain)

Full name

Demonstration of innovative integrated biomass logistics centres for the Agro-industry sector in Europe"

Funding scheme

IA - Innovation action

Overall budget

6,385,661.25

Start/End

2016-2020

Participants

1. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
2. FUNDACION ZARAGOZA LOGISTICS CENTER, Spain
3. ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS, Greece
4. JTI - Institutet för jordbruks- och miljöteknik AB, Sweden
5. CONSIGLIO PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA E L'ANALISI DELL'ECONOMIA AGRARIA, Italy
6. AGROINDUSTRIAL PASCUAL SANZ SL, Spain
7. NUTRIA ANONYMI BIOMICHANIKI ETAIRIA TYPOPIISIS KAI EMPORIAS AGROTIKON PROIONTON, Greece

8. LANTMANNEN EKONOMISK FORENING, Sweden
9. RISE PROCESSUM AB, Sweden
10. COOPERATIVAS AGRO-ALIMENTARIAS DE ESPANA U DE COOP SOCIEDAD COOPERATIVA, Spain
11. INSTITOUTO AGROTIKIS KAI SYNETAIRISTIKIS OIKONOMIAS INASO PASEGES, Greece
12. AGRICONSULTING EUROPE (S.A.), Belgium
13. ASSOCIATION UKRAINIAN AGRIBUSINESSCLUB, Ukraine
14. University of Belgrade - Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Serbia
15. RISE RESEARCH INSTITUTES OF SWEDEN AB, Sweden

Main objective

The main goal of AGROinLOG is the demonstration of Integrated Biomass Logistic Centres (IBLC) for food and non-food products, evaluating their technical, environmental and economic feasibility. The project is based on three agro-industries in the fodder (Spain), olive oil production (Greece) and cereal processing (Sweden) sectors that are willing to deploy new business lines in their facilities to open new markets in bio-commodities (energy, transport and manufacturing purposes) and intermediate bio-products (transport and biochemicals).

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/205975/factsheet/en>
<http://agroinlog-h2020.eu/en/home/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/205975/results/en>

There is 1 monographic book 2 other publications and 9 conference proceedings.

Results and recommendation

AGROinLOG will finish in April 2020 having implemented and demonstrated the technical, economic and environmental feasibility of integrated biomass logistics centers (IBLCs) for food and non-food products. As a result of the measures applied, the project agro-industries will be able to create a new activity with lower investment, achieving between 1-2 million euros of savings during the first decade. It is expected that their incomes will be increased by more than 12 %, stabilizing their annual activity (avoiding idle periods) and maintaining or creating new jobs.

DiverIMPACTS

Addressed topics

Rural values and income

Coordinator

INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE (France)

Full name

Diversification through Rotation, Intercropping, Multiple cropping, Promoted with Actors and value-Chains Towards Sustainability

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

11,192,323.50

Start/End

2017-2022

Participants

1. ASOCIATIA AIDER AGRICULTURA INTEGRATA DURABIL ECONOMIC RENTABIL, Romania
2. ASSEMBLEE PERMANENTE DES CHAMBRES D'AGRICULTURE, France
3. Association de Coordination Technique Agricole, France
4. ASS GROUPE ECOLE SUPERIEURE AGRICULTURE, France
5. ASSOCIAZIONE SVILUPPO RURALE, Italy
6. B.V. EXPLOITATIE RESERVEGRONDEN FLEVOLAND, Netherlands
7. BAERTSCHI AGRARTECNIC AG, Switzerland
8. OBSZANSKI TOMASZ, Poland
9. BIOFORUM VLAANDEREN, Belgium/
10. CENTRE WALLON DE RECHERCHES AGRONOMIQUES, Belgium
11. CONSIGLIO PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA E L'ANALISI DELL'ECONOMIA AGRARIA, Italy
12. FONDAZIONE ITALIANA PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA BIOLOGICA E BIODINAMICA, Italy
13. FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG, Switzerland
14. HUSHALLNINGSSALLSKAPET SKANE, Sweden
15. INAGRO, PROVINCIAAL EXTERN VERZELFSTANDIGD AGENTSCHAP IN PRIVAATRECHTELIJKE VORM VZW, Belgium
16. INRA TRANSFERT (S.A.), France/
17. INSTYTUT UPRAWY NAWOZENIA I GLEBOZNAWSTWA, PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY, Poland
18. AGROSOLUTIONS, France
19. LANDWIRTSCHAFTSKAMMER NIEDERSACHSEN, Germany
20. LINKING ENVIRONMENT AND FARMING LBG, United Kingdom
21. MUHLE RYTZ AG, Switzerland
22. OKOLOGIAI MEZOGAZDASAGI KUTATOINTEZET KOZHASZNU NONPROFIT KFT, Hungary
23. PROGRESSIVE FARMING TRUST LTD LBG, United Kingdom
24. QUALITY RESPONSIBLE R SRL, Romania
25. SERVICES OPERATIONNELS DU COLLEGE DES PRODUCTEURS, Belgium
26. STICHTING BIONEXT, Netherlands
27. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
28. SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET, Sweden
29. JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI, Germany
30. UNIVERSITE CATHOLIQUE DE LOUVAIN, Belgium
31. UNIVERSITEIT VAN AMSTERDAM, Netherlands
32. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY, Netherlands
33. WALAGRI, Belgium

Main objective

The overall goal of DiverIMPACTS is to achieve the full potential of diversification of cropping systems for improved productivity, delivery of ecosystem services and resource-efficient and sustainable value chains by (i) assessing performances of crop diversification through rotation, intercropping and multiple cropping, (ii) providing rural areas actors with those key enablers and innovations that would remove existing barriers and ensure actual uptake of benefits of crop diversification at farm, value chain and territory levels and (iii) make recommendations to policy-makers to facilitate the coordination of all relevant actors within the value chain.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210493/factsheet/en>
<https://www.diverimpacts.net/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210493/results/en>

There are 3 conference proceedings.

Results and recommendation

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210493/reporting/en>

There are some results achieved so far but project is ongoing.

MAGIC

Addressed topics

Rural and circular and efficient resource use; territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

CENTRE FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND SAVING FONDATION (Greece)

Full name

Marginal lands for Growing Industrial Crops: Turning a burden into an opportunity

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

€ 5,999,987.50

Start/End

2017-2021

Participants

1. ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA, Italy
2. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
3. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY, Netherlands
4. UNIVERSITAET HOHENHEIM, Germany
5. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France
6. IFEU - INSTITUT FUR ENERGIE UND UMWELTFORSCHUNG HEIDELBERG GMBH, German
7. IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE, United Kingdom
8. NOVA-INSTITUT FUR POLITISCHE UND OKOLOGISCHE INNOVATION GMBH, Germany
9. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI CATANIA, Italy
10. FACULDADE DE CIENCIAS E TECNOLOGIADA UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA, Portugal
11. UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA, Portugal
12. ARKEMA FRANCE SA, France
13. CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIONES ENERGETICAS, MEDIOAMBIENTALES Y TECNOLOGICAS-CIEMAT, Spain
14. COOPERATIVAS AGRO-ALIMENTARIAS DE ESPANA U DE COOP SOCIEDAD COOPERATIVA, Spain
15. KRZYZANIAK MICHAL, Poland
16. CONSIGLIO PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA E L'ANALISI DELL'ECONOMIA AGRARIA, Italy
17. INSTYTUT WLOKIEN NATURALNYCH I ROSLIN ZIELARSKICH, Poland
18. B.T.G. BIOMASS TECHNOLOGY GROUP BV, Netherlands
19. GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON, Greece
20. INSTITUTE OF BIOENERGY CROPS AND SUGAR BEET NATIONAL ACADEMY OF AGRARIAN

SCIENCES OF UKRAINE, Ukraine

21. LATVIJAS VALSTS MEZZINATNES INSTITUTS SILAVA, Latvia
22. INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FUER ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE, Austria
23. NOVABIOM, France
24. VANDINTER SEMO BV, Netherlands/ 25. BIOS AGROSYSTEMS SA, Greece.

Main objective

Industrial Crops can provide valuable resources for high added value products and bioenergy. MAGIC aims to promote the sustainable development of resource-efficient and economically profitable industrial crops grown on marginal lands.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210499/factsheet/en>
<http://magic-h2020.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210499/results/en>

There is 1 other publication.

Results and recommendations

The main advances of MAGIC are: a) development of three tools (MAGIC CROPS database, MAGIC MAPS & MAGIC-DSS), b) breeding and agricultural practices of resource use efficient industrial crops. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/210499/reporting/en> this link show us the progress of the project so far.

Further results and recommendations are not yet exist, project is ongoing.

RURITAGE

Addressed topics

Social capital, social processes

Coordinator

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA (Italy)

Full name

Rural regeneration through systemic heritage-led strategies"

Funding scheme

IA - Innovation action

Overall budget

€ 10,276,187.50

Start/End

2018-2022

Participants

1. CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL, Spain
2. FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION, Spain
3. FUNDACION CARTIF, Spain
4. UNITED NATIONS EDUCATIONAL, SCIENTIFIC AND CULTURAL ORGANIZATION –UNESCO, France
5. UNIVERSITY OF PLYMOUTH, United Kingdom
6. ICLEI EUROPEAN SECRETARIAT GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH)*, Germany
7. AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA, Italy
8. SAVONIA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY, Finland

9. POLITECNICO DI TORINO, Italy
10. NORGES MILJO-OG BIOVITENSKAPLIGE UNIVERSITET, Norway
11. STOWARZYSZENIE CENTRUM ROZWIAZAN SYSTEMOWYCH, Poland
12. AGENCE DE COOPERATION INTERREGIONALE - RESEAU CHEMINS DE SAINT-JACQUES DE COMPOSTELLE, France
13. BORGHI ITALIA TOUR NETWORK SRL, Italy/
14. INNOVATION AND MANAGEMENT CENTRE LIMITED, Ireland
15. ALMENDE BV, Netherlands
16. FEDERACION COLOMBIANA DE MUNICIPIOS, Colombia
17. MAGMA GEOPARK AS, Norway
18. DISTRETTO AGROALIMENTARE REGIONALE SCRL, Italy
19. CA PROVENCE-ALPES-AGGLOMERATION, France
20. VISEGRAD VAROS ONKORMANYZATA, Hungary
21. EMI EPITESUGYI MINOSEGELLENORZO INNOVACIOS NONPROFIT KFT, Hungary
22. KULTURNO IZOBRAZEVALNO DRUSTVO KIBLA, Slovenia
23. ZAVOD ZA KULTURO, TURIZEM IN PROMOCIJO GORNJA RADGONA, Slovenia
24. PIAM ONLUS ASTI, Italy
25. MOUSEIO FISIKIS ISTORIAS APOLITHOMENOU DASOUS LESVOU, Greece
26. GEO NATURPARK BERGSTRASSE-ODENWALDEV, Germany
27. PANEPISTIMIO KRITIS, Greece
28. KATLA GEOPARK, Iceland
29. COMUNE DI APPIGNANO DEL TRONTO, Italy
30. FUNDACION SANTA MARIA LA REAL DEL PATRIMONIO HISTORICO, Spain
31. JUDETUL HARGHITA, Romania
32. ASOCIATIA INSTITUTIO PRO EDUCATIONEM TRANSILVANIENSIS, Romania
33. ARBEITSGEMEINSCHAFT GEOPARK KARAWANKEN-KARAVANKE, Austria
34. AGRUPACION EMPRESARIAL INNOVADORA PARA LA CONSTRUCCION EFICIENTE, Spain
35. IZMIR BUYUKSEHIR BELEDIYESI, Turkey
36. DE SURDURULEBILIR ENERJI VE INSAAT SANAYI TICARET LIMITED SIRKETI, Turkey
37. IZMIR INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, Turkey
38. TAKE ART LIMITED, United Kingdom.

Main objective

European rural areas embody outstanding examples of Cultural and Natural Heritage (CNH) that need not only to be safeguarded, but also promoted as a driver for competitiveness, sustainable and inclusive growth and development. RURITAGE establishes a new heritage-led rural regeneration paradigm able to turn rural areas in sustainable development demonstration laboratories, through the enhancement of their unique CNH potential. RURITAGE has identified 6 Systemic Innovation Areas (pilgrimages; sustainable local food production; migration; art and festivals; resilience; and integrated landscape management) which, integrated with cross-cutting themes, showcase heritage potential as a powerful engine for economic, social and environmental development of rural areas.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/776465>

Publications

There are no publications yet, project is ongoing.

Results and recommendations

there are no results or recommendations yet, project is ongoing.

BE-RURAL

Addressed topics

Social capital, social processes / well-being, quality of life

Coordinator

ECOLOGIC INSTITUT gemeinnützige GmbH (Germany)

Full name

Bio-based strategies and roadmaps for enhanced rural and regional development in the EU

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

2,996,288.75

Start/End

2019-2022

Participants

1. UNIVERSITY OF STRATHCLYDE, United Kingdom
2. WIRTSCHAFT UND INFRASTRUKTUR GMBH & CO PLANUNGS KG, Germany
3. BIOCOM, Germany
4. BALGARSKA STOPANSKA KAMARA - SAYUZ NA BALGARSKIA BIZNES, Bulgaria
5. MEDUNARODNI CENTAR ZA ODRZIVI RAZVOJ ENERGETIKE VODA I OKOLISA, Croatia
6. ROMANIAN ACADEMY NATIONAL INSTITUTE FOR ECONOMIC RESEARCH, Romania
7. LATVIJAS VALSTS MEZZINATNES INSTITUTS SILAVA, Latvia
8. MORSKI INSTYTUT RYBACKI - PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY, Poland.

Main objective

The overall goal of BE-Rural is to realise the potential of regional and local bio-based economies by supporting relevant actors in the participatory development of bioeconomy strategies and roadmaps. BE-Rural will investigate the particular characteristics of the selected regions at a macro level, as well as existing best practices and business models geared towards the bioeconomy. This higher-level analysis will aid in the assessment of the 'bioeconomy potential' of the selected regions.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/818478>

<https://be-rural.eu/region/about/>

Publications

There are no publications, yet project is ongoing.

Results and recommendation

There are results and recommendations yet, project is ongoing.

SMARTCHAIN

Addressed topics

Smart villages, communities / rural values and income

Coordinator

UNIVERSITAET HOHENHEIM (Germany)

Full name

Towards Innovation - driven and smart solutions in short food supply chains

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

5,998,373.75

Start/End

2018-2021

Participants

1. ORGANIC SERVICES GMBH, Germany
2. ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA, Italy
3. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO, Italy
4. CENTRO INTERNAZIONALE DI ALTISTUDI AGRONOMICI MEDITERRANEI, Italy
5. LEGA REGIONALE DELLE COOPERATIVE E MUTUE, Italy
6. CONFEDERAZIONE GENERALE DELL AGRICOLTURA ITALIANA, Italy
7. UNIVERSITEIT UTRECHT, Netherlands
8. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY, Netherlands
9. STICHTING NEDERLANDS BAKKERIJ CENTRUM, Netherlands
10. ASSOCIATION DE COORDINATION TECHNIQUE POUR L'INDUSTRIE AGROALIMENTAIRE, France
11. PANEPISTIMIO KRITIS, Greece
12. Campden BRI Magyarorszag Nonprofit Korlatolt Felelossegu Tarsasag, Hungary
13. KISLEPTEKU TERMEKELOALLITOK ES SZOLGALTATOK ORSZAGOS ERDEKKEPVISELETENEK EGYESULETE, Hungary
14. FACULTY OF AGRICULTURE - UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE, Serbia
15. INSTITUT ZA FIZIKU, Serbia
16. FUNDACION AZTI - AZTI FUNDAZIOA, Spain
17. FUNDACION CITOLIVA, CENTRO DE INNOVACION Y TECNOLOGIA DEL OLIVAR Y DEL ACEITE, Spain
18. GABINETE DE GESTION INTEGRAL DE RECURSOS SL, Spain
19. EIDGENOESSISCHES DEPARTEMENT FUER WIRTSCHAFT, BILDUNG UND FORSCHUNG, Switzerland
20. ISEKI-Food Association, Austria
21. FOODDRINKEUROPE AISBL, Belgium
21. FRUITVEGETABLES EUROPE, Belgium
22. COMITE DES ORGANISATIONS PROFESSIONNELLES AGRICOLE DE L'UNION EUROPEENNE COPA ASSOCIATION DE FAIT, Belgium
23. EUROPEAN FOOD INFORMATION COUNCIL, Belgium/ SOLIDARISCHE LANDWIRTSCHAFT EV, Germany
24. LANDWIRTSCHAFTSKAMMER NIEDERSACHSEN, Germany
25. ALCE NERO SPA, Italy
26. ARVAIA SOCIETA COOPERATIVA AGRICOLA, Italy
27. AMPED CONCEPTS BV, Netherlands
28. BRANDT & LEVIE BV, Netherlands/
28. CENTRE TECHNIQUE DE LA CONSERVATIONES DES PRODUITS AGRICOLES*CTCPA, France

29. A LA FERME, France
30. ASTIKOS PROMITHEUTIKOS SYNETAIRISMOS PERIORISMENIS EUTHYNIS ALLOTROPON, Greece
31. SINETERISMOS PARAGOGON - KATANALOTON OIKOLOGIKON PROIONTON GAIA PE, Greece
32. FOODHUB.HU TERMELOI AGRAR SZOLGALTATO NONPROFIT ZARTKORUEN MUKODO RESZVENYTARSASAG, Hungary
33. ZALA TERMALVOLGYE EGYESULET, Hungary
34. PROMETNO PROMETNO DRUSTVO SA OGRANICENOM ODGOVORNOSCU POLO CACAK, Serbia
35. UDRUZENJE KOMPANIJA ZA PRERADU VOCAI POVRCA KRALJEVO, Serbia
36. LA TRUFA DE ALAVA - ARABAKO BOILURRA KOOP E, Spain
37. FUNDACION LANTEGI BATUAK, Spain
38. BIOFRUITS SA, Switzerland
38. JEAN-MICHEL BESSON, Switzerland.

Main objective

SMARTCHAIN is an ambitious, 3 year project with 43 partners from 11 European countries including key stakeholders from the domain of short food supply chain as actors in the project. The central objective is to foster and accelerate the shift towards collaborative short food supply chains and, through concrete actions and recommendations, to introduce new robust business models and innovative practical solutions that enhance the competitiveness and sustainability of the European agri-food system.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773785>

<https://www.smartchain-h2020.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications yet, project is ongoing.

Results and recommendations

There are no results and recommendations yet, project is ongoing.

FOX

Addressed topics

Rural and digital

Coordinator

DIL DEUTSCHES INSTITUT FUR LEBENSMITTELTECHNIK EV (Germany)

Full name

Innovative down-scaled FOOd processing in a bOX

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

7 065 223, 75

Start/End

2019-2023

Participants

1. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
2. KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN, Belgium

3. FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG (E.V.)Germany
4. AARHUS UNIVERSITET, Denmark
5. AINIA, Spain
6. VYZKUMNY USTAV POTRAVINARSKY PRAHA, Czechia
7. SZKOLA GLOWNA GOSPODARSTWA WIEJSKIEGO, Poland
8. INSTITUT ZA NUTRICIONISTIKO LJUBLJANA, Slovenia
9. STICHTING EFFOST, Netherlands
10. ELEA VERTRIEBS- UND VERMARKTUNGSGESELLSCHAFT MBH, Germany
11. EUROPEAN FOOD INFORMATION COUNCIL, Belgium
12. CENTRE TECHNIQUE DE LA CONSERVATION DES PRODUITS AGRICOLES*CTCPA, France
13. KOMPETENZENTRUM OBSTBAU BODENSEE, Germany
14. STICHTING FOOD TECH PARK BRAINPORT, Netherlands
15. FALKENSTEIN PROJEKTMANAGEMENT GMBH, Germany
16. LINPAC PACKAGING PRAVIA, SA, Spain
17. TERRA I XUFA SOCIEDAD LIMITADA, Spain
18. Tomas Ignac Fenix Czechia
19. AGRARNI KOMORA CESKE REPUBLIKY, Czechia
20. CEDRUS SPOLKA Z OGRANICZONA ODPOWIEDZIALNOSCIA SPOLKA KOMANDYTOWA, Poland
21. SPOLECNOST MLADYCH AGRARNIKU CESKERE PUBLIKY ZS, Czechia
22. SADY TUCHORAZ (SPOL.S.R.O.), Czechia
23. VANRIJSINGEN INGREDIENTS (B.V.), Netherlands
24. HUTTEN CATERING (B.V.), Netherlands.

Main objective

The unique FOX approach will research and develop innovative, small scale technologies in mobile or flexible processing units for different applications for small and medium enterprises and farmers in the fruit and vegetable sector in Europe.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/817683>

Publications

There are no publications, project just started.

Results and recommendation

There are no results or recommendations yet, project is ongoing.

Smart-Akis
Addressed topics
Rural and digital

Coordinator

GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON (Greece)

Full name

European Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) towards innovation-driven research in Smart Farming Technology

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

1,997,756.15

Start/End

2016-2018

Participants

1. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
2. LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG (ZALF) (e.V.), Germany
3. BIOSENSE INSTITUTE - RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN BIOSYSTEMS, Serbia
4. Association de Coordination Technique Agricole, France
5. INSTITUTO NAVARRO DE TECNOLOGIAS E INFRAESTRUCTURAS AGROALIMENTARIAS SA, Spain
6. Deutsche Landwirtschafts-Gesellschaft (e.V.)Germany
7. DELPHY BV, Netherlands
8. PROVINCIAL SECRETARIAT OF AGRICULTURE, WATER ECONOMY AND FORESTRY, VOJVODINA, Serbia
9. INICIATIVAS INNOVADORAS SAL, Spain
10. COMITE EUROPEEN DES GROUPEMENTS DE CONSTRUCTEURS DU MACHINISME AGRICOLE, Belgium
11. FEDERATION REGIONALE DES COOPERATIVES D'UTILISATION DE MATERIEL AGRICOLE DE L'OUEST DE LA FRANCE, France
12. DAVID TINKER & ASSOCIATES LIMITED, United Kingdom
13. ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS, Greece.

Main objective

The project aims at setting up a self-sustainable Thematic Network on Smart Farming Technology designed for the effective exchange between research, industry, extension and the farming community in order to disseminate direct applicable research and commercial solutions and capture grassroots level needs and innovative ideas. Smart Farming Technology (SFT) encompasses Farm Management Information Systems, Precision Agriculture and Agriculture automation and robotics.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/696294>

<https://www.smart-akis.com/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/696294/results>

There is 1 conference proceeding.

Results and recommendation

At the following link there are the results of the project. <https://www.smart-akis.com/index.php/network/results/>

4D4f

Addressed topics

Rural and digital

Coordinator

INNOVATION FOR AGRICULTURE (United Kingdom)

Full name

Data Driven Dairy Decisions 4 Farmers

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

2,105,796.25

Start/End

2016-2019

Participants

1. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK, Belgium
2. EESTI MAAULIKOOL, Estonia
3. ACHTEN BVBA, Belgium
4. WIM GOVAERTS & CO, Belgium
5. LATVIJAS ZINATNU AKADEMIJA, Latvia
6. UNIVERSITATEA DE STIINTE AGRONOMICE SI MEDICINA VETERINARA DIN BUCURESTI, Romania
7. KNOWLEDGE INNOVATION MARKET (S.L.), Spain
8. KUNGL. SKOGS- OCH LANTBRUKSAKADEMIEN KSLA, Sweden
9. ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING, Netherlands
10. STICHTING VAN HALL LARENSTEIN, Netherlands
11. PARAGON LIMITED, Malta
12. INSTITUT DE RECERCA I TECNOLOGIA AGROALIMENTARIES, Spain
13. EVONIK PORPHYRIO, Belgium
14. KATHOLIEKE UNIVERSITEIT LEUVEN, Belgium
15. DeLaval International AB Sweden.

Main objective

Data Driven Dairy Decision For Farmers (4D4F) aims at developing a network for dairy farmers, dairy technology suppliers, data companies, dairy advisors, veterinarians and researchers to improve the decision making on dairy farms based on data generated by sensors. It will focus on the role which dairy animal and environmental sensors can play in collecting real time information to help make more informed decisions in dairy farming.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/696367>

<https://4d4f.eu/>

Publications

There were no publications.

Results and recommendation

Events and workshops have been held which demonstrate the cutting edge of available technology, and bring together interested parties to extend best practice and develop standard operating procedures.

There were no recommendations.

IOF2020

Addressed topics

Rural and digital

Coordinator

STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH (Netherlands)

Full name

Internet of Food and Farm 2020

Funding scheme

IA - Innovation action

Overall budget

34,234,990.42

Start/End

2017-2020

Participants

1. INSTITUT FÜR ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMTECHNIK BREMEN GMBH, Germany
2. BIOSENSE INSTITUTE - RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN BIOSYSTEMS, Serbia
3. SCHUTTELAAR & PARTNERS, CONSULTANCY FOR FOOD AND LIFESCIENCES NV, Belgium
4. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK, Belgium
5. TELEFONICA INVESTIGACION Y DESARROLLO SA, Spain
6. COOPERATIVAS AGRO-ALIMENTARIAS DE ESPANA U DE COOP SOCIEDAD COOPERATIVA, Spain
7. INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE MOVEMENTS EUROPEAN UNION REGIONAL GROUP, Sweden
8. COMITE EUROPEEN DES GROUPEMENTS DE CONSTRUCTEURS DU MACHINISME AGRICOLE, Belgium
9. KUHNE LOGISTICS UNIVERSITY GGMBH, Germany
10. GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON, Greece
11. FUNDACION TEKNIKER, Spain
12. UNIVERSIDAD DE ALMERIA, Spain
13. 365FARMNET GROUP GMBH & CO KG, Germany
14. NXP SEMICONDUCTORS GERMANY GMBH, Germany
15. STMICROELECTRONICS SRL, Italy
16. UNPARALLEL INNOVATION LDA, Portugal
17. CORIZON (B.V.), Netherlands
18. ORANGE SA, France
19. GS1 GERMANY GMBH, Germany
20. WAGENINGEN UNIVERSITY, Netherlands
21. WIRELESSINFO, Czechia
22. SYNELIXIS LYSEIS PLIROFORIKIS AUTOMATISMOU & TILEPIKOINONION ANONIMI ETAIRIA, Greece
23. KVERNELAND GROUP MECHATRONICS BV, Netherlands
24. SIGNIFY NETHERLANDS BV, Netherlands
25. CONNECTERRA BV, Netherlands
26. EVONIK PORPHYRIO, Belgium
27. ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING, Netherlands
28. BAYER CROPSCIENCE AG, Germany
29. KONINKLIJKE KPN NV, Netherlands/
29. UNIVERSITY OF STRATHCLYDE, United Kingdom
30. CONTEXTWISE, Belgium

31. AGROTIKOS SYNETAIRISMOS POLISEOS XIRON KAI NOPON STAFYLION KIATOY KORINTHIAS PIGASOS, Greece
32. GRUPO HISPATEC INFORMATICA EMPRESARIAL SA, Spain
33. DCOOP SOCIEDAD COOPERATIVA ANDALUZA, Spain
34. NILEAS - SYNETAIRISMOS PISTOPOIIMENON AGROTIKON PROIONTON DIMOU NESTOROS MESSINIAS, Greece
35. DUBOURDIEU DENIS ET FLORENCE, France
36. EARL DENIS DUBOURDIEU DOMAINES, France
37. FRESH-CARE CONVENIENCE BV, Netherlands
38. STICHTING HAS OPLEIDINGEN, Netherlands
39. VION GmbH, Germany
40. ARVALIS INSTITUT DU VEGETAL, France
41. VEREIN ZUR FORDERUNG DER EUROPAISCHEN SOJAPRODUKTION DONAU SOJA, Austria
42. STMICROELECTRONICS GRENOBLE 2 SAS, France
43. EURO POOL SYSTEM INTERNATIONAL DEUTSCHLAND GMBH, Germany
44. MIELOO & ALEXANDER BV, Netherlands
45. GRUPO SADA P A SA, Spain
46. EXAFAN SA, Spain
47. FONDAZIONE LINKS - LEADING INNOVATION & KNOWLEDGE FOR SOCIETY, Italy
48. ISTITUTO SUPERIORE MARIO BOELLA SULLE TECNOLOGIE DELL'INFORMAZIONE E DELLE TELECOMUNICAZIONI ASSOCIAZIONE, Italy
49. European EPC Competence Center GmbH, Germany
50. VALORITALIA SOCIETA PER LA CERTIFICAZIONE DELLE QUALITA'E DELLE PRODUZIONI VITIVINICOLE ITALIANE SRL, Italy
51. ISVEA SRL, Italy
52. VINIDEA SRL, Italy
53. QLIP BV, Netherlands
54. AGRO INTELLIGENCE APS, Denmark
55. AARHUS UNIVERSITET, Denmark
56. INAGRO, PROVINCIAAL EXTERN VERZELFSTANDIGD AGENTSCHAP IN PRIVAATRECHTELIJKE VORM VZW, Belgium
57. CENTRO INTERNAZIONALE DI ALTISTUDI AGRONOMICI MEDITERRANEI, Italy
58. INSTITUT POLYTECHNIQUE DE BORDEAUX, France
59. SYSMAN PROGETTI & SERVIZI SRL, Italy
60. ASOCIACION DE ORGANIZACIONES DE PRODUCTORES DE FRUTAS Y HORTALIZAS DE ALMERIA, Spain
61. APOFRUIT ITALIA - SOC. COOP. AGRICOLA, Italy
62. COMMISSARIAT A L'ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVES, France
63. CNH INDUSTRIAL BELGIUM, Belgium
64. GRIMME LANDMASCHINENFABRIK GMBH COKG, Germany
65. NEWAYS TECHNOLOGIES BV, Netherlands
66. AGROM KG, Austria
67. MACHINEFABRIEK STEKETEE BV, Netherlands
68. IHUB.EU EEIG, Belgium
69. STIFTELSEN SINTEF, Norway
70. KOREA ADVANCED INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, South Korea
71. AGCO AS, Denmark
72. SOIA ITALIA, Italy

73. ETVENTURE STARTUP HUB GMBH, Germany
74. BOLT MANAGEMENT SL, Spain
75. FIWARE FOUNDATION EV, Germany
76. FUTURE INTERNET CONSULTING AND DEVELOPMENT SOLUTIONS SL, Spain
77. DONAU SOJA GEMEINNUTZIGE GESELLSCHAFT MIT BESCHRANKTER HAFTUNG, Austria
78. SINTEF AS, Norway.

Main objective

The IoF2020 project is dedicated to accelerate adoption of IoT for securing sufficient, safe and healthy food and to strengthen competitiveness of farming and food chains in Europe. It will consolidate Europe's leading position in the global IoT industry by fostering a symbiotic ecosystem of farmers, food industry, technology providers and research institutes. The IoF2020 consortium of 73 partners, led by Wageningen UR and other core partners of previous key projects such as FIWARE and IoT-A, will leverage the ecosystem and architecture that was established in those projects.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/731884>
- 2) <https://www.iof2020.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/731884/results>

There are 4 conference proceedings, 1 thesis dissertation, 7 peer reviewed articles, 1 book chapter.

Results and recommendation

Results and recommendations are expected, project is ongoing.

PANTHEON

Addressed topics

Rural and digital

Coordinator

UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI ROMA TRE (Italy)

Full name

Precision Farming of Hazelnut Orchards

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

3,144,452.50

Start/End

2017-2021

Participants

1. FERRERO TRADING LUX SA, Luxembourg
2. UNIVERSITE LIBRE DE BRUXELLES, Belgium
3. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DELLA TUSCIA, Italy
4. UNIVERSITAT TRIER, Germany
5. SIGMA CONSULTING SRL, Italy.

Main objective

The goal of PANtHEOn is to develop the agricultural equivalent of an industrial Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA) system to be used for the precision farming of large orchards of hazelnut (*Corylus avellana* L.). By taking advantage of the technological advancements in the fields of robotics, remote sensing and big-data management, our objective is to design an integrated system where a relatively limited number of heterogeneous unmanned robotics components (including terrestrial and aerial robots) move within the orchards to collect data and perform some of the most common farming operations.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/774571>
- 2) <http://www.project-pantheon.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/774571/results>

There is 1 conference proceeding and 4 other publications.

Results and recommendation

The project has some deliverables but the final results and recommendations are expected.

ROMI

Addressed topics

Rural and digital

Coordinator

INSTITUT D'ARQUITECTURA AVANÇADA DE CATALUNYA (Spain)

Full name

RObotics for MIcrofarms

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

3,868,186.25

Start/End

2017-2021

Participants

1. SONY EUROPE LIMITED, United Kingdom
2. SONY EUROPE BV, Netherlands
3. FRANCE EUROPE INNOVATION, France
4. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE ET AUTOMATIQUE, France
5. CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS, France
6. HUMBOLDT-UNIVERSITÄT ZU BERLIN, Germany
7. SCEA PEPINIÈRES CHATELAIN, France.

Main objective

ROMI will develop an open and lightweight robotics platform for these microfarms. We will assist these farms in weed reduction and crop monitoring. This will reduce manual labour and increase the productivity. Thanks to ROMI's weeding robot, farmers will save 25% of their time. This land robot

will also acquire detailed information on sample plants and will be coupled with a drone that acquires more global information at crop level.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773875>
- 2) <https://romi-project.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773875/results>

There are 2 conference proceedings.

Results and recommendation

The project is ongoing so it may have some deliverables but the results and the recommendations are expected.

AfriCultuReS

Addressed topics

Rural and digital

Coordinator

GMV AEROSPACE AND DEFENCE SA (Spain)

Full name

Enhancing Food Security in AFRICan AgriCULTUral Systems with the Support of REMote Sensing

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

8,531,533.20

Start/End

2017-2021

Participants

1. ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS, Greece
2. CENTRE FOR REMOTE SENSING AND GEOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SERVICES LBG, Ghana/ 3. CENTRE REGIONAL AGRHYMET, Niger
4. DRAXIS ENVIRONMENTAL (S.A.), Greece
5. UNIVERSIDADE EDUARDO MONDLANE, Mozambique
6. GEOSAS CONSULTING SERVICE PLC, Ethiopia
7. NOORT HARMANNUS, CONRADUS PIETER, Netherlands
8. LOCATE IT LIMITED, Kenya
9. OBSERVATOIRE DU SAHARA ET DU SAHEL, Tunisia
10. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA LA SAPIENZA, Italy
11. SOUTH AFRICA NATIONAL SPACE AGENCY, South Africa
12. SVERIGES METEOROLOGISKA OCH HYDROLOGISKA INSTITUT, Sweden
13. UNIVERSIDAD DE CANTABRIA, Spain
14. UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS, United Kingdom
15. THE UNIVERSITY OF SHEFFIELD, United Kingdom
16. UNIVERSITY OF RWANDA, Rwanda.

Main objective

AfriCultuReS – Enhancing Food Security in AFRIcan AgriCULTUral Systems with the Support of REmote Sensing - aims to design, implement and demonstrate an integrated agricultural monitoring and early warning system that will support decision making in the field of food security. AfriCultuReS will deliver a broad range of climatic, production, biophysical and economic information, for various regions in Africa. AfriCultuReS will apply geospatial science to sustainable agricultural development, natural resource management, biodiversity conservation, and poverty alleviation in Africa.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/774652>
- 2) <http://www.africultures.eu/project>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/774652/results>

There is 1 peer reviewed article.

Results and recommendation

<http://www.africultures.eu/project>

The project is ongoing so results and recommendations are expected but there are some work packages showing us the progress of the project so far.

SmartAgriHubs

Addressed topics

Rural and digital

Coordinator

STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH (Netherlands)

Full name

Connecting the dots to unleash the innovation potential for digital transformation of the European agri-food sector

Funding scheme

IA - Innovation action

Overall budget

22,423,146

Start/End

2018-2022

Participants

1. BIOSENSE INSTITUTE - RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN BIOSYSTEMS, Serbia
2. SCHUTTELAAR & PARTNERS, CONSULTANCY FOR FOOD AND LIFESCIENCES NV, Belgium
3. ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING, Netherlands
4. INSTITUT FÜR ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMTECHNIK BREMEN GMBH, Germany
5. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK, Belgium
6. NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR TOEGEPAST NATUURWETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK TNO, Netherlands
7. CONSEJERIA DE AGRICULTURA, GANADERÍA, PESCA Y DESARROLLO SOSTENIBLE, Spain
8. UNIVERSIDAD DE ALMERIA, Spain

9. FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG (E.V.), Germany
10. CONSULAI, CONSULTORIA AGROINDUSTRIAL LDA, Portugal
11. WATERFORD INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, Ireland
12. INNOVATION FOR AGRICULTURE, United Kingdom
13. Région des Pays de la Loire, France
14. Association de Coordination Technique Agricole, France
15. ASTER - SOCIETA CONSORTILE PER AZIONI, Italy
16. ART-ER-SOCIETA CONSORTILE PER AZIONI, Italy
17. CONFEDERAZIONE NAZIONALE COLDIRETTI, Italy
18. PRASIDENTENKONFERENZ DER LANDWIRTSCHAFTSKAMMERN OSTERREICHS, Austria
19. WIRELESSINFO, Czechia
20. GERHARDY HUBERT ERICH, Germany
21. GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON, Greece
22. FEDERATIA NATIONALA A PRODUCATORILOR DIN AGRICULTURA INDUSTRIA ALIMENTARA SI SERVICII CONEXE DIN PRO AGRO, Romania
23. LANDBRUG & FODEVARER (F.M.B.A.), Denmark
24. LUONNONVARAKESKUS, Finland
25. ZEMNIEKU SAEIMA, Latvia
26. INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK, Poland
27. NEMZETI AGRARKUTATASI ES INNOVACIOS KOZPONT, Hungary
28. AGRARGAZDASAGI KUTATO INTEZET, Hungary
29. COMITE DES ORGANISATIONS PROFESSIONNELLES AGRICOLE DE L'UNION EUROPEENNE COPA ASSOCIATION DE FAIT, Belgium
30. INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE MOVEMENTS EUROPEAN UNION REGIONAL GROUP, Sweden
31. COMITE EUROPEEN DES GROUPEMENTS DE CONSTRUCTEURS DU MACHINISME AGRICOLE, Belgium
32. FUNDACION CENTRO TECNOLOGICO DE TELECOMUNICACIONES DE GALICIA, Spain
33. SDRUZENIE BULGARSKA ASOCIACIA NA SOFTUERNITE KOMPANII BASCOM, Bulgaria
34. FARMHACKNL, Netherlands
35. EUROPEAN BUSINESS AND INNOVATION CENTRE NETWORK AISBL, Belgium
36. FIWARE FOUNDATION EV, Germany
37. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
38. CODE PLUS LIMITED, Ireland
39. INGENERA SA, Switzerland
40. GROUPE PROVENCE SERVICES, France
41. IRISH CATTLE BREEDING FEDERATION SOCIETY LTD, Ireland
42. ENERGY MONITORING IRELAND LIMITED, Ireland
43. CFS CROSS FARM SOLUTION GMBH, Austria
44. SCHRENK HUBERT, Austria
45. HOEHERE BUNDESLEHR- UND FORSCHUNGSANSTALT FUER LANDWIRTSCHAFT, LANDTECHNIK UND LEBENSMITTELTECHNOLOGIE, Austria
46. FARMDOK GMBH, Austria
47. ROBOVISION BVBA, Belgium
48. EXOBOTIC TECHNOLOGIES, Belgium
48. AGRI-DATASERVICES BIOSCOPE BV, Netherlands
49. AUREA IMAGING BVBA, Belgium

50. AVR BVBA, Belgium
51. SYNTESA PARTNERS AND ASSOCIATES SL, Spain
52. STIENEN BEDRIJFSELEKTRONIKA BV, Netherlands
53. VAN MIERLO INGENIEURSBUREAU (B.V.), Netherlands
54. NEUROPUBLIC AE PLIROFORIKIS & EPIKOINONION, Greece
55. TEKEVER II AUTONOMOUS SYSTEMS LDA, Portugal
56. EASYTOSEE AGTECH, SOCIEDAD LIMITADA, Spain
57. INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE INVESTIGAÇÃO AGRARIA E VETERINARIA, Portugal
58. GRUPO HISPATEC INFORMATICA EMPRESARIAL SA, Spain
59. EDIA-EMPRESA DE DESENVOLVIMIENTO E INTRA-ESTRUTURAS DO ALQUEVA (S.A.)Portugal
60. UNPARALLEL INNOVATION LDA, Portugal
61. PNO INNOVATION, Belgium
62. NORDI GIUSEPPINO, Italy
63. DNAPHONE SRL, Italy
64. CASELLA MACCHINE AGRICOLE SRL, Italy
65. VSAFE SOCIETA' A RESPONSABILITA' LIMITATA, Italy
66. UNIVERSITA CATTOLICA DEL SACRO CUORE, Italy
67. GRAINSENSE OY, Finland
68. AGRO INTELLIGENCE APS, Denmark
69. AGROVAST LIVSMEDEL AKTIEBOLAG, Sweden
70. CYBERNETIC TECHNOLOGIES NETICTECH SPOLKA AKCYJNA, Poland
71. WIELKOPOLSKI OSRODEK DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO W POZNANIU, Poland
72. UNIWERSYTET PRZYRODNICZY W POZNANIU, Poland
73. AGRIWATCH BV, Netherlands
74. FREEDOMGROW - SISTEMAS DE INFORMACAO SA, Portugal
75. PRZEMYSLOWY INSTYTUT MASZYN ROLNICZYCH W POZNANIU, Poland/ 76. BALTIC OPEN SOLUTIONS CENTER, Latvia
77. SABIEDRIBA AR IEROBEZOTU ATBILDIBU SUNGIS, Latvia
78. LESPROJEKT SLUZBY SRO, Czechia
79. INF AGRI 85, AGRI 85, VENDEE AGRICOLE, RACINES, France
80. IQ MANAGEMENT SRL, Romania
81. SMARTRDI - SMART RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INTERNATIONAL SRL, Romania
82. PROSPEH, POSLOVNE STORITVE IN DIGITALNE RESITVE DOO, Slovenia/ 83. VEREIN ZUR FORDERUNG DER BAUERLICHEN VEREDELUNGSWIRTSCHAFT (E.V.), Germany
84. MITTELDEUTSCHE AGENTUR FUR INFORMATIONSSERVICE GMBH, Germany
85. LANDWIRTSCHAFTSKAMMER NIEDERSACHSEN, Germany
86. INNOSEP GMBH, Germany
87. DANFOIL A/S, Denmark
88. GOTHIA REDSKAP & EKOVAXT AB, Sweden
89. AGRO BUSINESS PARK AS, Denmark
90. SMART AGRITECH SOLUTION OF SWEDEN AB, Sweden
91. FOREST ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH AND SERVICES LIMITED, Ireland
92. SERAGRO S. COOP. GALEGA, Spain
93. API AGRO, France
94. ELMEGA SL Spain
95. MONET TECNOLOGIA E INNOVACION SL, Spain
96. SOUNDTALKS, Belgium
97. AGENCIA GALLEGA DE LA CALIDAD ALIMENTARIA, Spain

- 98. TERRASOLIS, France
- 99. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA, Italy
- 100. POLYAGROKTIMA GAIA MAS IKE, Greece
- 101. METEOBLUE AG, Switzerland
- 102. CONSULTORES DE AUTOMATIZACION YROBOTICA SA, Spain
- 103. VERVAEKE, Belgium
- 104. CAJAMAR CAJA RURAL SOCIEDAD COOPERATIVA DE CREDITO, Spain.

Main objective

SmartAgriHubs is dedicated to accelerate the digital transformation of the European agri-food sector. It will consolidate, activate and extend the current ecosystem by building a network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) that will boost the uptake of digital solutions by the farming sector. This will be achieved by integrating technology and business support in a local one-stop-shop approach involving all regions and all relevant players in Europe.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/818182>
- 2) <https://smartagrihubs.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications yet, project is ongoing

Results and recommendation

There are no results or recommendations yet, project is ongoing.

NIVA

Addressed topics

Digital and rural / innovation policies

Coordinator

STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH (Netherlands)

Full name

A New IACS Vision in Action

Funding scheme

IA - Innovation action

Overall budget

10,677,810.00

Start/End

2019-2022

Participants

- 1. MINISTERIE VAN ECONOMISCHE ZAKEN EN KLIMAAT, Netherlands
- 2. Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries, Danish AgriFish Agency, Denmark
- 3. POLLUMAJANDUSE REGISTRITE JA INFORMATSIOONI AMET, Estonia
- 4. AGENCE DE SERVICE ET DE PAIEMENT, France
- 5. ORGANISMOS PLIROMON KE ELEGHOU KINOTIKON ENISHYSEON PROSANATOLISMOU KEEGGYISEON, Greece
- 6. DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURE, FOOD AND THE MARINE, Ireland
- 7. AGENZIA PER LE EROGAZIONI IN AGRICOLTURA AGEA, Italy

8. NATIONAL PAYING AGENCY, Lithuania
9. FONDO ESPANOL DE GARANTIA AGRARIA, Spain
10. NEUROPUBLIC AE PLIROFORIKIS & EPIKOINONION, Greece
11. ABACO SPA, Italy
12. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE L'INFORMATION GEOGRAPHIQUE ET FORESTIERE, France
13. E-GEOS SPA, Italy
14. BUREAU EUROPEEN DE L'ENVIRONNEMENT AISBL, Belgium
15. ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING, Netherlands
16. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France
17. EMPRESA DE TRANSFORMACION AGRARIA SA, Spain
18. WATERFORD INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY, Ireland
19. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
20. TARTU ULIKOOL, Estonia
21. CONSIGLIO PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA E L'ANALISI DELL'ECONOMIA AGRARIA, Italy
22. ITREE LIETUVA UAB, Lithuania
23. LANDBRUG & FODEVARER (F.M.B.A.), Denmark
24. SINERGISE LABORATORIJ ZA GEOGRAFSKEINFORMACIJSKE SISTEME DOO, Slovenia
25. INSTITUTO TECNOLOGICO AGRARIO DE CASTILLA Y LEON, Spain
26. CONSEJERIA DE AGRICULTURA, GANADERÍA, PESCA Y DESARROLLO SOSTENIBLE, Spain.

Main objective

NIVA delivers a suite of digital solutions, e-tools and good practices for e-governance and initiates an innovation ecosystem to support further development of Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) for CAP monitoring. It will explore the use of IACS data for purposes and develop relevant standards for information flows. The project's results promote a transparent, simpler administrative process that contributes to a future CAP that increases environmental performance.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/842009>

Publications

There are n publications yet, project has just started.

Results and recommendation

There are no results and recommendations yet, project has just started.

DEMETER

Addressed topics

Rural and digital

Coordinator

WATERFORD INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY (Ireland)

Full name

Building an Interoperable, Data-Driven, Innovative and Sustainable European Agri-Food Sector

Funding scheme

IA - Innovation action

Overall budget

17,704,191.25

Start/End

2019-2023

Participants

1. ENGINEERING - INGEGNERIA INFORMATICA SPA, Italy
2. INTRASOFT INTERNATIONAL SA, Luxembourg
3. EMPRESA DE TRANSFORMACION AGRARIA SA, Spain
4. JOHN DEERE GMBH & CO. KG*JD, Germany
5. ORGANIZZAZIONE MONDIALE DEGLI AGRICOLTORI, Italy
6. INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS, Greece
7. OPEN GEOSPATIAL CONSORTIUM (EUROPE) LIMITED LBG, United Kingdom
8. ATOS SPAIN SA, Spain
9. FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG (E.V.)Germany
10. SINTEF AS, Norway
11. CONFEDERAZIONE NAZIONALE COLDIRETTI, Italy
12. LESPROJEKT SLUZBY SRO, Czechia
13. CODAN SA, Spain
14. UNIVERSIDAD DE MURCIA, Spain
15. 13 JUL PLANTAZE AD PODGORICA, Montenegro
16. AVR BVBA, Belgium
17. SIVECO ROMANIA SA, Romania
18. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
19. AGRICOLUS (S.R.L.), Italy
20. ASPLAN VIAK INTERNET AS, Norway
21. MACCARESE SPA SOCIETA AGRICOLA, Italy
22. CENTRIA AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY, Finland
23. LANDBRUKETS DATAFLYT SA, Norway
24. DNET LABS DOO NOVI SAD, Serbia
25. F6S NETWORK LIMITED, United Kingdom
26. FENADEGAS FEDERACAO NACIONALDAS ADEGAS COOPS FCRL, Portugal
27. AGROPRODUKT-SINKOVIC DOO, Serbia
28. INFORMATION CATALYST FOR ENTERPRISE LTD, United Kingdom
29. IDEATRONIK SPOLKA Z OGRANICZONA ODPOWIEDZIALNOSCIA, Poland
30. ARIETE FATTORIA LATTE SANO SPA, Italy
31. INDATA LLC, Georgia
31. INESC TEC - INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIADE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES, TECNOLOGIA E CIENCIA, Portugal
32. UBIWHERE LDA, Portugal
33. ELLINIKOS GEORGIKOS ORGANISMOS – DIMITRA, Greece
34. M2XPERT GMBH & CO KG, Germany
35. MIMIRO AS, Norway
36. PULVERIZADORES FEDE SL, Spain
37. ODIN SOLUTIONS (S.L.), Spain
37. PROSPEH, POSLOVNE STORITVE IN DIGITALNE RESITVE DOO, Slovenia/
38. FEIRMEOIRI AONTUITHE NA H-EIREANN IONTAOBIATHE TEORANTA LBG, Ireland
39. PROBOT OY, Finland
40. INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK, Poland/
41. INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE INVESTIGAÇÃO AGRARIA E VETERINARIA, Portugal

42. ITC - INOVACIJSKO TEHNOLOSKI GROZD MURSKA SOBOTA, Slovenia
43. RO TECHNOLOGY SRL, Italy
44. GEORGIAN FARMERS ASSOCIATION, Georgia
45. FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION, Spain
46. UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK, Ireland
47. UDRUZENJE PROIZVODJACA GROZDJA I VINA SA OZNAKOM GEOGRAFSKOG POREKLA SREM - FRUSKA GORA, Serbia
48. UNIVERZITET DONJA GORICA PODGORICA, Montenegro
49. WIELKOPOLSKI OSRODEK DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO W POZNANIU, Poland
50. ASOCIATIA PRODUCATORILOR DE PORUMB DIN ROMANIA, Romania
52. UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID, Spain
53. FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH, Spain
54. VLAAMSE INSTELLING VOOR TECHNOLOGISCH ONDERZOEK (N.V.), Belgium
55. TRONDELAG FORSKNING OG UTVIKLING AS, Norway
57. NAPIERALA RYSZARD, Poland
58. FRACKOWIAK MACIEJ, Poland
59. ZOETIS BELGIUM SA, Belgium.

Main objective

DEMETER will deploy interoperable smart farming-IoT based platforms delivered through a series of 20 pilots across 18 countries. The potential of advanced standards-based interoperability between IoT technologies will be demonstrated by adapting and extending existing standards into an over-arching Agricultural Information Model, ensuring security, privacy and business confidentiality across the full value chain in multiple agri-food operational environments.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/857202>

Publications

There are no publications yet, project has just started.

Results and recommendation

There are no results or recommendations yet, project has just started.

ATLAS

Addressed topics

Rural and digital

Coordinator

FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG (E.V.),
(Germany)

Full name

Agricultural Interoperability and Analysis System

Funding scheme

IA - Innovation action

Overall budget

15,406,420.00

Start/End

2019-2022

Participants

1. AGRICIRCLE AG, Switzerland
2. ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS, Greece
3. AGRO APPS (I.K.E.), Greece
4. UNIVERSITA DEL SALENTO, Italy
5. CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE, Italy
6. AGRICULTURAL INDUSTRY ELECTRONICS FOUNDATION AEF, German
7. NATIONAL OBSERVATORY OF ATHENS, Greece
8. FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JULICH GMBH, Germany
9. ELLINIKOS GEORGIKOS ORGANISMOS – DIMITRA, Greece
10. TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE KOLN, Germany
11. STATIUNEA DE CERCETARE DEZVOLTARE PENTRU VITICULTURA SI VINIFICATIE MURFATLAR, Romania
12. Deutsche Landwirtschafts-Gesellschaft (e.V.), Germany
13. ROBOT MAKERS GMBH, Germany
14. METEOMATICS AG, Switzerland
15. LIBELIUM COMUNICACIONES DISTRIBUIDAS SL, Spain
16. SEELMEYER & WOLTERING KG, Germany
17. LATVIJAS AUGLKOPJU ASOCIACIJA, Latvia
18. CREVIS SPRL, Belgium
19. KUNNE STEPHAN, Germany
20. LIEDER FALK, Germany
21. MUNCHHOFF FRIEDRICH-CHRISTIAN, Germany
22. LATVIJAS BIOLOGISKAS LAUKSAIMNIECIBAS ASOCIACIJA, Latvia
23. FODJAN GMBH, Germany
24. FROHLICH PETER, Switzerland
25. OIKONOMOU STAMATIS, Greece
26. AGROTIKOS SYNETAIRISMOS PROIONTON AGIAS O KISSAVOS, Greece
27. ANWENDUNGSZENTRUM GMBH OBERPFAFFENHOFEN, Germany
28. DARZKOPIBAS INSTITUTS, Latvia
29. KTIMA GEROVASSILIOU OINOPOIIA ANONYMI ETARIA, Greece.

Main objective

ATLAS will develop an open digital service platform for agricultural applications to build a sustainable ecosystem for innovative data-driven agriculture. The platform will allow the flexible combination of agricultural machinery, sensor systems and data analysis tools to overcome the problem of lacking interoperability and to enable farmers to increase their productivity in a sustainable way by making use of the most advanced digital technology and data.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/857125>

Publications

The project has just started so there are no publications yet.

Results and recommendation

The project has just started so there are no results or recommendations yet.

NUTRIMAN

Addressed topics

Rural and circular and efficient resource use / rural and digital

Coordinator

TERRA HUMANA TISZTA TECHNOLOGIAKATFEJLESZTO TERVEZO ES KIVITELEZO KFT (Hungary)

Full name

Nutrient Management and Nutrient Recovery Thematic Network

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

1,999,927.50

Start/End

2018-2021

Participants

1. STICHTING EFFOST, Netherlands
2. ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING, Netherlands
3. ASSEMBLEE PERMANENTE DES CHAMBRES D'AGRICULTURE, France
4. UNIVERSITEIT GENT, Belgium
5. INAGRO, PROVINCIAAL EXTERN VERZELFSTANDIGD AGENTSCHAP IN PRIVAATRECHTELIJKE VORM VZW, Belgium
6. ASSEMBLEE DES REGIONS EUROPEENNES FRUITIERES LEGUMIERES ET HORTICOLES, France
7. VLACO VZW, Belgium
8. FUNDACION CARTIF, Spain
9. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO, Italy
10. INSTITUT FUR BAUSTOFF-FORSCHUNG EV, Germany
11. INSTYTUT UPRAWY NAWOZENIA I GLEBOZNAWSTWA, PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY, Poland
12. DEPURACION DE AGUAS DE MEDITERRANEO SL, Spain
13. MAGYAR AGRAR-, ELELMISZERGAZDASAGI ES VIDEKFEJLESZTESI KAMARA, Hungary.

Main objective

Agriculture and food industry having a high dependence on resources in their production and striving for long-term sustainability. In this context there is an urgent need to optimise resource use and smooth the transition to a knowledge driven agriculture. The NUTRIMAN is a Nitrogen and Phosphorus thematic network compiling knowledge "ready for practice" for such recovered product applications, practices and technologies, interconnecting applied science and industrial practice, for the user interest and benefits of the agricultural practitioners.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/818470>

Publications

The project has just started, there are no publications yet.

Results and recommendation

The project has just started, there are no recommendations or results yet.

FERTINNOWA

Addressed topics

Rural and digital / rural values and income

Coordinator

PROEFSTATION VOOR DE GROENTETEELT (Belgium)

Full name

Transfer of INNOvative techniques for sustainable WATER use in FERTigated crops

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

2,999,273.40

Start/End

2016-2018

Participants

1. PROEFCENTRUM VOOR SIERTEELT - PCS VZW, Belgium
2. ASSOCIATION PROVENCALE DE RECHERCHE ET D'EXPERIMENTATION LEGUMIERE, France
3. CENTRO DI SPERIMENTAZIONE ED ASSISTENZA AGRICOLA, Italy
4. NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR TOEGEPAST NATUURWETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK TNO, Netherlands
5. STICHTING PROEFTUIN ZWAAGDIJK, Netherlands
6. INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACIONY FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA, Spain
7. EAST MALLING RESEARCH, United Kingdom
8. FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG (E.V.), Germany
9. CENTRUM DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO W BRWINOWIE, Poland
10. INSTYTUT OGRODNICTWA, Poland
11. UNIVERSIDAD DE ALMERIA, Spain
12. THE AGRICULTURE AND HORTICULTURE DEVELOPMENT BOARD (AHDB), United Kingdom
13. FUNDACION CAJAMAR, Spain
14. CENTRO DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS Y TECNOLOGICAS DE EXTREMADURA, Spain
15. INSTITUTO VALENCIANO DE INVESTIGACIONES AGRARIAS, Spain
16. INSTITUTO NAVARRO DE TECNOLOGIAS E INFRAESTRUCTURAS AGROALIMENTARIAS SA, Spain
17. PRIVA BV, Netherlands
18. COMITE D'ACTION TECHNIQUE ET ECONOMIQUE, France
19. KMETIJSKO GOZDARSKA ZBORNICA SLOVENIJE KMETIJSKO GOZDARSKI ZAVOD MARIBOR, Slovenia
20. PROVINCIAAL PROEFCENTRUM VOOR DE GROENTETEELT OOST-VLAANDEREN VZW, Belgium
21. PROEFCENTRUM HOOGSTRATEN, Belgium
22. OPTIMA AGRIC PTY LTD, South Africa
23. NIAB EMR, United Kingdom/ 24. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands.

Main objective

The main objective of the FERTINNOWA thematic network is to create a meta-knowledge database on innovative technologies and practices for fertigation of horticultural crops. FERTINNOWA will also build a knowledge exchange platform to evaluate existing and novel technologies (innovation

potential, synergies, gaps, barriers) for fertigated crops and ensure wide dissemination to all stakeholders involved of the most promising technologies and best practices.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/689687>
- 2) <https://www.fertinnowa.com/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/689687/results>

There are 3 other publications, 6 conference proceedings and 1 peer reviewed article.

Results and recommendation

Despite the wide range of available technologies, only a few growers were satisfied with the achieved results. Furthermore, growers were aware of only some alternative technologies. The survey led to the identification of a significant number of bottlenecks and problems. All of them were listed and categorised. There were no recommendations for further projects.

PANACEA

Addressed topics

Rural and digital

Coordinator

CENTRE FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND SAVING FONDATION (Greece)

Full name

A thematic network to design the penetration PAth of Non-food Agricultural Crops into European Agriculture

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

1 999 500

Start/End

2017-2020

Participants

1. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
2. ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA, Italy
3. IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE, United Kingdom
4. GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON, Greece
5. UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA, Portugal
6. INICIATIVAS INNOVADORAS SAL, Spain
7. Association de Coordination Technique Agricole, France
8. INSTITUTO NAVARRO DE TECNOLOGIAS E INFRAESTRUCTURAS AGROALIMENTARIAS SA, Spain
9. ASOCIATIA CLUSTERUL AGRO-FOOD-IND NAPOCA, Romania
10. BIOS AGROSYSTEMS SA, Greece
11. COOPERATIVAS AGRO-ALIMENTARIAS DE ESPANA U DE COOP SOCIEDAD COOPERATIVA, Spain
12. CONSIGLIO PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA E L'ANALISI DELL'ECONOMIA AGRARIA, Italy
13. LIETUVOS AGRARINIU IR MISKU MOKSLU CENTRAS, Lithuania

14. KRZYZANIAK MICHAL, Poland

15. ARKEMA FRANCE SA, France.

Main objective

PANACEA aims to set up a thematic network that will foster the effective exchange between research, industry, and the farming community, so that direct applicable solutions are widely disseminated and grassroots level needs and innovative ideas are thoroughly captured, in order to design the penetration path of non-food crops into European agriculture.

Websites

1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773501>

2) <http://www.panacea-h2020.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications.

Results and recommendation

PANACEA has been established direct communication with the European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP AGRI) and its structures (Focus Groups, Service Point, Operational Groups, and National Clusters) in order to maximise stakeholders' mobilization and enhance the impact of the project activities and outcomes for closing the research and innovation gap in the area of NFC for the bio-based economy. PANACEA is connected with some of the existing operational groups and has been proposed the establishment of a new Operational Group "Non-food crops and bio-based products". Additionally, a dissemination plan has been established including: project's events, social media, promotional material, lin.

LEGUMES TRANSLATED

Addressed topics

Rural values and income

Coordinator

JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI, (Germany)

Full name

Translating knowledge for legume-based farming for feed and food systems

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

2,159,043.75

Start/End

2018-2021

Participants

1. SRUC, United Kingdom
2. HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO, Finland/ 3. MURPHY BOKERN DONAL, Germany
4. THE CIRCA GROUP EUROPE LIMITED, Ireland
5. MINISTERIUM FUER LAENDLICHEN RAUM, ERNAEHRUNG UND VERBRAUCHERSCHUTZ BADEN-WUERTTEMBERG, Germany
6. FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG, Switzerland

7. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
8. LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG (ZALF) (e. V.), Germany
9. NIREFS ICHTHIOKALLIERGEIES ANONYMI ETAIRIA, Greece
10. SYNETAIRISMOS AGROTON THESSALIAS, Greece
11. AGROBIOINSTITUTE, Bulgaria
12. BAEUERLICHE ERZEUGERGEMEINSCHAFT SCHWABISCH HALL WV, Germany
13. HESSISCHES MINISTERIUM FÜR UMWELT, KLIMASCHUTZ, LANDWIRTSCHAFT UND VERBRAUCHERSCHUTZ, Germany
14. DONAU SOJA GEMEINNUTZIGE GESELLSCHAFT MIT BESCHRANKTER HAFTUNG, Austria
15. STONEGATE FARMERS LIMITED, United Kingdom
16. SEED TECHNOLOGY LIMITED, Ireland
17. INSTITUT ZA RATARSTVO I POVRTARSTVO, Serbia.

Main objective

The project addresses an urgent need and cross-sector challenges by building on technical opportunities. The urgent need is due to the imbalance in cropping systems now dominated by cereal crops with adverse agronomic and environmental effects.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/817634>

Publications

The project has just started so there are no publications yet.

Results and recommendation

The project has just started so there are no results or recommendations so far.

INNOSETA

Addressed topics

Rural and circular and efficient resource / rural and digital

Coordinator

UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE CATALUNYA (Spain)

Full name

Accelerating Innovative practices for Spraying Equipment, Training and Advising in European agriculture through the mobilization of Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

1,998,562.50

Start/End

2018-2021

Participants

1. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO, Italy
2. GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON, Greece
3. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK, Belgium
4. INSTITUT FRANCAIS DE LA VIGNE ET DU VIN, France
5. COMITE EUROPEEN DES GROUPEMENTS DE CONSTRUCTEURS DU MACHINISME AGRICOLE, Belgium

6. ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE POUR LA PROTECTION DES CULTURES - EUROPEAN CROP PROTECTION ASSOCIATION - EUROPAISCHER PFLANZENSCHUTZVERBAND, Belgium
7. UNION DE PEQUENOS AGRICULTORES Y GANADEROS, Spain
8. CONFEDERAZIONE GENERALE DELL AGRICOLTURA ITALIANA, Italy
9. AGRICULTURAL & ENVIRONMENTAL SOLUTIONS, Greece
10. ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING, Netherlands
11. VISAVI - GOD LANTMANNASED AB, Sweden
12. ZACHODNIOPOMORSKI OSRODEK DORADZTWAROLNICZEGO W BARZKOWICACE, Poland
13. COMITE DES ORGANISATIONS PROFESSIONNELLES AGRICOLE DE L'UNION EUROPEENNE COPA ASSOCIATION DE FAIT, Belgium
14. ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS, Greece.

Main objective

The aim of this network is to set-up a self-sustainable Thematic Network on Spraying Equipment, Training and Advising designed for the effective exchange between researchers, industry, extension services and farming community. This network will link directly applicable research and commercial solutions and grassroots level needs and innovative ideas thoroughly captured, thus contributing to close the research and innovation divide in this area.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773864>

Publications

There are no publications yet, project as just started.

Results and recommendation

There are no results or recommendations yet, project has just started.

HENNOVATION

Addressed topics

Rural values and income / innovation policies

Coordinator

UNIVERSITY OF BRISTOL (United Kingdom)

Full name

Practice-led innovation supported by science and market-driven actors in the laying hen and other livestock sectors

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

2 094 055

Start/End

2015-2017

Participants

1. THE UNIVERSITY OF EXETER, United Kingdom
2. SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET, Sweden
3. VETERINARNI A FARMACEUTICKA UNIVERZITA BRNO, Czechia
4. UNIVERSIDAD AUTONOMA DE BARCELONA, Spain
5. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands

6. ADAS UK LIMITED, United Kingdom
7. RSK ADAS LIMITED, United Kingdom.

Main objective

The HENNOVATION project is a thematic network funded under the topic 'Closing the research and innovation divide: the crucial role of innovation support services and knowledge exchange' of the Horizon 2020 EU Research and Innovation programme.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/652638>
- 2) <http://hennovation.eu/results/index.html>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/652638/results>

There are 4 conference proceedings and 1 peer reviewed article.

Results and recommendation

The project has demonstrated that this practice-led approach can be a major stimulus for innovation with several networks generating novel ideas and testing them in their commercial context. The complexity and the novelty of the innovations is significant, especially considering concurrent outbreaks of Avian Influenza and relatively limited timescale. The farmers and processors involved in the project were often very enthusiastic committing significant time to the group's activities. Working with social scientists during the project, we have concluded that successful multi-actor, practice-led innovation networks depend upon the following key factors: active participation from relevant actors, professional facilitation, moderate resource support and access to relevant expertise.

Given the enthusiasm and engagement shown from innovation network participants, the project team and advisory board recommend that the agricultural research community and funding agencies should place greater value on Hennovation style practice-led innovation networks alongside technology and advisor focused initiatives. We, therefore, encourage government, industry and other organisations to work collaboratively to realise the potential of this approach, particularly focussing on the critical role of the professional facilitator.

SHEEPNET

Addressed topics

Rural and digital

Coordinator

INSTITUT DE L'ELEVAGE (France)

Full name

Sharing Expertise and Experience towards sheep Productivity through NETworking

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

1,995,289.38

Start/End

2016-2019

Participants

1. UNIVERSITATEA DE STIINTE AGRICOLE SI MEDICINA VETERINARA A BANATULUI REGELE MIHAI I AL ROMANIEI DIN TIMISOARA, Romania
2. NEIKER-INSTITUTO VASCO DE INVESTIGACION Y DESARROLLO AGRARIO SA, Spain
3. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
4. AGRIS SARDEGNA - AGENZIA PER LA RICERCA IN AGRICOLTURA, Italy
5. SRUC, United Kingdom
6. EFFICIENT INNOVATION SAS, France
7. INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE, France
8. TOGEN DANISMANLIK TARIM VE HAYVANCILIK ZIRAAT GIDA BIOTEKNOLOJI ITHALAT IHRACAT SAN VE TIC LTD, Turkey.

Main objective

"SheepNet is a thematic network project about practice-driven innovation to improve sheep productivity (number of lambs weaned/ewe mated): a critical component of farmers' income and therefore of the sustainability and attractiveness of sheep farming.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/727895>
- 2) <http://www.sheepnet.network/>

Publications

There were no publications.

Results and recommendation

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/727895/reporting>

EuroDairy

Addressed topics

Rural values and income / rural and circular and efficient resource use

Coordinator

THE AGRICULTURE AND HORTICULTURE DEVELOPMENT BOARD (AHDB) (United Kingdom)

Full name

A Europe-wide thematic network supporting a sustainable future for EU dairy farmers

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

1,997,237.75

Start/End

2016-2019

Participants

1. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
2. BOERENBONDVERENIGING VOOR INNOVATIEVE PROJECTEN VZW, Belgium
3. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK, Belgium
4. SEGES PS, Denmark
5. LUONNONVARAKESKUS, Finland
6. INSTITUT DE L'ELEVAGE, France

7. CENTRE NATIONAL INTERPROFESSIONNELLE L'ECONOMIE LAITIERE, France
8. CHRISTIAN-ALBRECHTS-UNIVERSITAET ZU KIEL, Germany
9. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
10. CENTRO RICERCA PRODUZIONI ANIMALI- C.R.P.A. SPA, Italy
11. ZUIVELNL, Netherlands
12. ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING, Netherlands
13. SZKOLA GLOWNA GOSPODARSTWA WIEJSKIEGO, Poland
14. UNIVERSIDADE DE TRAS-OS-MONTES E ALTO DOURO, Portugal
15. UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI, Slovenia
16. UNION DE COOPERATIVAS ASOCIACION GALEGA DE COOPERATIVAS AGRARIAS, Spain
17. NEIKER-INSTITUTO VASCO DE INVESTIGACION Y DESARROLLO AGRARIO SA, Spain
18. LANTBRUKARNAS EKONOMI-AB, Sweden
19. THE NOTHERN IRELAND AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT COUNCIL, United Kingdom
20. LANDBRUG & FODEVARER (F.M.B.A.), Denmark.

Main objective

EuroDairy is a thematic network to increase the economic, social and environmental sustainability of dairy farming in Europe. Funded by the EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (ISIB-2015-1 program under grant agreement No 696364), EuroDairy fosters the development and dissemination of practice-based innovations in dairy farming, targeting key sustainability issues following the abolition of milk quotas: socio economic resilience, resource efficiency, animal care, and the integration of milk production with biodiversity objectives.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/696364>
- 2) <https://eurodairy.eu/>

Publications

There were no publications.

Results and recommendation

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/696364/reporting>

There are no recommendations just results which are on the link above.

EuPiG

Addressed topics

Rural values and income

Coordinator

THE AGRICULTURE AND HORTICULTURE DEVELOPMENT BOARD (AHDB) (United Kingdom)

Full name

EU Pig Innovation Group

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

2,000,000.00

Start/End

2016-2020

Participants

1. BETA TECHNOLOGY LTD, United Kingdom
2. ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING, Netherlands
3. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
4. INSTITUT DE RECERCA I TECNOLOGIA AGROALIMENTARIES, Spain
5. CENTRO RICERCHE PRODUZIONI ANIMALI- C.R.P.A. SPA, Italy
6. BOERENBONDVERENIGING VOOR INNOVATIEVE PROJECTEN VZW, Belgium
7. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
8. AGRIFOOD AND BIOSCIENCES INSTITUTE, United Kingdom
9. VETERINAERMEDIZINISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN, Austria
10. INTERPROFESSION NATIONALE PORCINE, France
11. SEGES PS, Denmark
12. DEUTSCHER RAIFFEISENVERBAND EV, Germany
13. VAGOALLAT- ES HUS SZAKMAKOZI SZERVEZET ES TERMEKTANACS, Hungary
14. IFIP-INSTITUT DU PORC ASSOCIATION, France
15. GRAN SUINO ITALIANO, Italy
16. SZKOLA GLOWNA GOSPODARSTWA WIEJSKIEGO, Poland
17. POLSKI ZWIAZEK HODOWCOW I PRODUCENTOW TRZODY CHLEWNEJ POLSUS Poland
18. ELAINTEN TERVEYS ETT RY, Finland
19. LANDBRUG & FODEVARER (F.M.B.A.), Denmark.

Main objective

EU PiG specifically aims to more effectively connect producers with the latest science, husbandry techniques and technologies from within their industry via fellow producers, academics and advisors connected through thematic and regional platforms.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/727933>
- 2) <https://www.eupig.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications.

Results and recommendation

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/727933/reporting>

There are no recommendations just results which are on the link above.

OK-Net EcoFeed

Addressed topics

Rural values and income

Coordinator

INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE MOVEMENTS EUROPEAN UNION
REGIONAL GROUP (Sweden)

Full name

Organic Knowledge Network on Monogastric Animal Feed

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

1,990,368.75

Start/End

2018-2020

Participants

1. AARHUS UNIVERSITET, Denmark
2. PROGRESSIVE FARMING TRUST LTD LBG, United Kingdom
3. INSTITUT TECHNIQUE DE L'AGRICULTURE BIOLOGIQUE, France
4. FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG, Switzerland
5. BIOLAND BERATUNG GMBH, Germany
6. ASSOCIAZIONE ITALIANA PER L'AGRICOLTURA BIOLOGICA, Italy
7. DONAU SOJA GEMEINNUTZIGE GESELLSCHAFT MIT BESCHRANKTER HAFTUNG, Austria
8. SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET, Sweden
9. VALOR ECOLOGICO CAAE, Spain
10. THE SOIL ASSOCIATION LIMITED, United Kingdom.

Main objective

The overall aim of OK-Net EcoFeed is to help farmers, breeders and the organic feed processing industry in achieving the goal of 100% use of organic and regional feed for monogastrics, in particular pigs, broilers, laying hens and parents of broilers and laying hens.

Websites

- 1) <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773911>
- 2) <https://ok-net-ecofeed.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications yet project is ongoing.

Results and recommendation

There are no results or recommendations project is ongoing.

LIAISON**Addressed topics**

Innovation policies / rural values and income

Coordinator

HOCHSCHULE FUR NACHHALTIGE ENTWICKLUNG EBERSWALDE (Germany)

Full name

Better Rural Innovation: Linking Actors, Instruments and Policies through Networks

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

4,999,143.75

Start/End

2018-2021

Participants

1. STICHTING GROEP VAN BRUGGE, Netherlands
2. HIGHCLERE CONSULTING SRL, Romania
3. BOERENBONDVERENIGING VOOR INNOVATIEVE PROJECTEN VZW, Belgium
4. Institute for the Study of Societies and Knowledge, Bulgaria
5. INSTITUT DE L'ELEVAGE, France
6. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
7. STIFTELSEN RURALIS INSTITUTT FOR RURAL- OG REGIONALFORSKNING, Norway
8. CENTRUM DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO W BRWINOWIE, Poland
9. FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG, Switzerland
10. UNIVERSIDADE DE EVORA, Portugal
11. UNIVERSITA DI PISA, Italy
12. THE SOIL ASSOCIATION LIMITED, United Kingdom
13. NEMZETI AGRARKUTATASI ES INNOVACIOS KOZPONT, Hungary
14. AGRARGAZDASAGI KUTATO INTEZET, Hungary
15. THE UNIVERSITY OF EXETER, United Kingdom
16. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK, Belgium
17. UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID, Spain.

Main objective

LIAISON aims to make a significant and meaningful contribution to optimising interactive innovation project approaches and the delivery of EU policies to speed up innovation in agriculture, forestry and rural areas. Researchers, policy advisors, actors from interactive innovation projects, initiatives and networks, farm/forestry advisors, decision-makers and administrators will jointly investigate the design and implementation of interactive innovation project approaches.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/773418>
<http://liaison2020.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications yet, project is ongoing.

Results and recommendation

There are no results or recommendations yet, project is ongoing.

NEXTFOOD**Addressed topics**

Innovation policies

Coordinator

SVERIGES LANTBRUKSUNIVERSITET (Sweden)

Full name

Educating the next generation of professionals in the agrifood system"

Funding scheme

RIA - Research and Innovation action

Overall budget

€ 7,000,000.00

Start/End

2018-2022

Participants

1. LUNDS UNIVERSITET, Sweden
2. UNIVERSITATEA DIN ORADEA, Romania
3. JIHOCESKA UNIVERZITA V CESKYCH BUDEJOVICICH, Czechia
4. NORGES MILJO-OG BIOVITENSKAPLIGE UNIVERSITET, Norway
5. AMERICAN FARM SCHOOL POST SECONDARY EDUCATIONAL AND TRAINING ASSOCIATION, Greece
6. ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA, Italy
7. BIOINSTITUT OPS, Czechia
8. STIFTELSEN SKOGSBRUKETS FORSKNING SINSTITUT – SKOGFORSK, Sweden
9. AGRODIATROFIKI SIMPRAKSI TIS PERIFERIAS KENTRIKIS MAKEDONIAS ASTIKI MI KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA, Greece
10. CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE HAUTES ETUDES AGRONOMIQUES MEDITERRANEENNES, France
11. DEUTSCHE WELTHUNGERHILFE (E.V.), Germany
12. SEKEM DEVELOPMENT FOUNDATION – SDF, Egypt
13. MEKELLE UNIVERSITY, Ethiopia
14. DIETHNES PANEPISTIMIO ELLADOS, Greece
15. ALEXANDREIO TECHNOLOGIKO EKPAIDEITIKO IDRYMA THESSALONIKIS, Greece
16. ISEKI-Food Association, Austria
17. KOBENHAVNS PROFESSIONSHOJSKOLE, Denmark
18. UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI SCIENZE GASTRONOMICHE, Italy
19. UNIVERSIDAD DE CHILE, Chile
20. ROSKILDE UNIVERSITET, Denmark.

Main objective

NEXTFOOD will drive the crucial transition to more sustainable and competitive agrifood and forestry systems development by designing and implementing education and training systems to prepare budding or already practicing professionals with competencies to push the green shift in our rapidly changing society.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/771738>

<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications yet, project is ongoing.

Results and recommendations

There are no recommendations or results yet, project is ongoing.

FAIRshare

Addressed topics

Rural and digital

Coordinator

TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY (Ireland)

Full name

FAIRshare. Farm Advisory digital Innovation tools Realised and Shared”

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

€ 6,998,652.50

Start/End

2018-2023

Participants

1. THE CIRCA GROUP EUROPE LIMITED, Ireland
2. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK, Belgium
3. COMITE EUROPEEN DES GROUPEMENTS DE CONSTRUCTEURS DU MACHINISME AGRICOLE, Belgium
4. MREZA SAVJETODAVNIH SLUZBI JUGOISTOCNE EUROPE, Croatia
5. INAGRO, PROVINCIAAL EXTERN VERZELFSTANDIGD AGENTSCHAP IN PRIVAATRECHTELIJKE VORM VZW, Belgium
6. GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON, Greece
7. ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING, Netherlands/
8. INSTITUTO NAVARRO DE TECNOLOGIAS E INFRAESTRUCTURAS AGROALIMENTARIAS SA, Spain
9. INNOVATION FOR AGRICULTURE, United Kingdom
10. FUNDACION CAJAMAR, Spain
11. CONSULAI, CONSULTORIA AGROINDUSTRIAL LDA, Portugal
12. Association de Coordination Technique Agricole, France
13. MAGYAR AGRAR-, ELELMISZERGAZDASAGI ES VIDEKFEJLESZTESI KAMARA, Hungary 14. BERNER FACHHOCHSCHULE, Switzerland
15. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
16. OKO-BERATUNGSGESELLSCHAFT MBH, Germany
17. MINISTERIO DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA Y ALIMENTACION, Spain
19. ASSOCIATION DES CHAMBRES D'AGRICULTURE DE L'ARC ATLANTIQUE, France
20. PRASIDENTENKONFERENZ DER LANDWIRTSCHAFTSKAMMERN OSTERREICHS, Austria
21. VIESOJI ISTAIGA LIETUVOS ZEMES UKIO KONSULTAVIMO TARNYBA, Lithuania
22. STIFTELSEN RURALIS INSTITUTT FOR RURAL- OG REGIONALFORSKNING, Norway.

Main objective

FAIRshare aims to mobilise the rural advisory community to take ownership of digital tools and make best use of analytics and communication technologies for agricultural sustainability. The project engages the independent farm advisor community, through sharing of tools, expertise and motivations across various advisory and farming contexts across the EU.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/818488>

<https://fairshareproject.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications yet, project is ongoing.

Results and recommendation

There are no results or recommendations yet, project is ongoing.

EURAKNOS

Addressed topics

Territorial approaches and policies

Coordinator

UNIVERSITEIT GENT, (Belgium)

Full name

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs: towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System"

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

€ 2,101,286.25

Start/End

2019-2020

Participants

1. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK, Belgium
2. PROEFSTATION VOOR DE GROENTETEELT, Belgium
3. INSTITUT DE L'ELEVAGE, France
4. ROYAL AGRICULTURAL UNIVERSITY, United Kingdom
5. GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON, Greece
6. UNIVERSIDAD DE SANTIAGO DE COMPOSTELA, Spain
7. GRUENLANDZENTRUM NIEDERSACHEN/BREMEN (E.V.), Germany
8. LEAP FORWARD, Belgium
9. NEMZETI AGRARKUTATASI ES INNOVACIOS KOZPONT, Hungary
10. AGRARGAZDASAGI KUTATO INTEZET, Hungary
11. INNOVATION FOR AGRICULTURE, United Kingdom
12. AARHUS UNIVERSITET, Denmark
13. MAGYAR AGRAR-, ELELMISZERGAZDASAGI ES VIDEKFEJLESZTESI KAMARA, Hungary
14. Association de Coordination Technique Agricole, France
15. POLLUMAJANDUSUURINGUTE KESKUS, Estonia
16. INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE MOVEMENTS EUROPEAN UNION REGIONAL GROUP, Sweden.

Main objective

EURAKNOS aims to extend existing thematic network outputs in an interactive way, both contentwise and in terms of geographical coverage. EURAKNOS will stimulate the exchange of existing approaches, methodologies and tools between the different thematic networks and search for a harmonised approach for setting up future thematic networks in order to maximise the impact on the practitioner, farmer and forester

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/817863>

<https://www.euraknos.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications yet, project is ongoing.

Results and recommendations

There are no results or recommendations yet, project is ongoing.

AgriDemo-F2F

Addressed topics

Innovation policies

Coordinator

EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK (Belgium)

Full name

Building an interactive AgriDemo-Hub community: enhancing farmer to farmer learning

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

€ 1,985,363.75

Start/End

2017-2019

Participants

1. ASSOCIATION DES CHAMBRES D'AGRICULTURE DE L'ARC ATLANTIQUE, France
2. UNIVERSITY OF GLOUCESTERSHIRE, United Kingdom
3. GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON, Greece
4. UNIVERSIDAD DE SANTIAGO DE COMPOSTELA, Spain
5. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
6. ZUIDELIJKE LAND- EN TUINBOUWORGANISATIE VERENIGING, Netherlands
7. BIOSENSE INSTITUTE - RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN BIOSYSTEMS, Serbia
8. SEGES PS, Denmark
9. OSTERREICHISCHE AGENTUR FUR GESUNDHEIT UND ERNAHRUNGSSICHERHEIT GMBH, Austria
10. EUROPEAN LANDOWNERS ORGANIZATION, Belgium
11. FEDERACION EFA GALICIA, Spain
12. IDEELLA FORENINGEN ODLING I BALANS MED FIRMA ODLING I BALANS, Sweden
13. CENTRUM DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO W BRWINOWIE, Poland
14. LANDBRUG & FODEVARER (F.M.B.A.), Denmark.

Main objective

AgriDemo-F2F will deepen the understanding of effective on farm demonstration activities, detailing the sectors, themes and topics on which they provide expertise. It will perform a comparative analysis of their network structure, mechanisms and tools used for recruitment, interaction and learning, assessing the effectiveness of the different approaches. The project will deliver a set of best practices and recommendations on how to best support on farm demonstration.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/728061>

<https://agridemo-h2020.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/728061/results>

<https://agridemo-h2020.eu/publications-deliverables/>

There are 3 peer reviewed article and 1 dataset.

Results and recommendations

The results were: Developed an inventory of commercial demonstration farms, accessible online (www.farmdemo.eu). The development of an analytical framework. Put in place a good collaboration between PLAID and AgriDemo-F2F. Developed a Multi-Actor (MA) protocol. Ensured sound and ethical data management, by providing necessary background and guiding documents to all partners.

Constructed a Communication and Networking Plan and a Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results, both are guiding and living documents to support the coordination and synergies of all networking, exploitation, dissemination and communication activities of the different work packages and actions of the AgriDemo-F2F project. Put all pieces in position for a successful second year of AgriDemo-F2F.

There were no recommendations.

PLAID

Addressed topics

Innovation policies

Coordinator

THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE (United Kingdom)

Full name

Peer-to-Peer Learning: Accessing Innovation through Demonstration

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

€ 2,187,767.50

Start/End

2017-2019

Participants

1. NATIONAL AGRICULTURAL ADVISORY SERVICE, Bulgaria
2. Association de Coordination Technique Agricole, France
3. VINIDEA SRL, Italy
4. BOERENBONDVERENIGING VOOR INNOVATIEVE PROJECTEN VZW, Belgium
5. NODIBINAJUMS BALTIC STUDIES CENTRE, Latvia
6. MINISTARSTVO POLJOPRIVREDE, Croatia
7. HRVATSKA POLJOPRIVREDNO-SUMARSKA SAVJETODAVNA SLUZBA, Croatia
8. INSTITUTO NAVARRO DE TECNOLOGIAS E INFRAESTRUCTURAS AGROALIMENTARIAS SA, Spain
9. LINKING ENVIRONMENT AND FARMING LBG, United Kingdom
10. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
11. STIFTELSEN RURALIS INSTITUTT FOR RURAL- OG REGIONALFORSKNING, Norway/12. DELPHY POLAND SPOLKA Z OGRANICZONA ODPOWIEDZIALNOSCIA, Poland
13. FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG, Switzerland.

Main objective

PLAID will identify, compile and communicate the topics, locations, best practices and innovative approaches to demonstration on commercial farms in the EU, Switzerland and Norway. It will analyse the impact of various governance, financing and demonstration approaches on learning processes and access to knowledge. PLAID will also pilot test 'virtual demonstration', to identify good practice in enabling farmers to demonstrate their innovations on-line

Websites <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/72738>

<https://www.plaid-h2020.eu/>

Publications

There are no publications just 1 dataset.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/727388/results>

Results and recommendations

The results are: PLAID has established a positive, productive working relationship with AgriDemoF2F. It has completed its initial conceptual framework. It (in collaboration with AgriDemoF2F) has completed the inventories of demonstration farms in 27 countries. It has reviewed current on-line demonstration activities, identifying over 500 audio-video materials published on webpages, YouTube, Facebook, Vimeo, etc. Consortium members analysed existing practices to identify potential barriers and opportunities for use of on-line audio-visual material on commercial farming. It has produced: 5 blog posts, twitter accounts with 265 followers, 27 short videos (total 7000 views), 13 practice abstracts; and participated in 7 national events.

NEFERTITI

Addressed topics

Innovation policies

Coordinator

Association de Coordination Technique Agricole (France)

Full name

Networking European Farms to Enhance Cross Fertilisation and Innovation Uptake through Demonstration

Funding scheme

CSA - Coordination and support action

Overall budget

€ 6,999,991.25

Start/End

2018-2021

Participants

1. MINISTARSTVO POLJOPRIVREDE, Croatia
2. HRVATSKA POLJOPRIVREDNO-SUMARSKA SAVJETODAVNA SLUZBA, Croatia
3. CENTRUM DORADZTWA ROLNICZEGO W BRWINOWIE, Poland
4. ASSEMBLEE PERMANENTE DES CHAMBRES D'AGRICULTURE, France
5. BIOSENSE INSTITUTE - RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT INSTITUTE FOR INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN BIOSYSTEMS, Serbia
6. UNIVERSIDAD DE ALMERIA, Spain
7. FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU STIFTUNG, Switzerland
8. GRUENLANDZENTRUM NIEDERSACHEN/BREMEN (E.V.), Germany
9. SZECHENYI ISTVAN UNIVERSITY, Hungary
10. INNOVATION FOR AGRICULTURE, United Kingdom
11. INOVISA - ASSOCIACAO PARA A INOVACAO E DESENVOLVIMENTO EMPRESARIAL, Portugal
12. INRA TRANSFERT (S.A.)France
13. INTERNATIONAL FEDERATION OF ORGANIC AGRICULTURE MOVEMENTS EUROPEAN UNION REGIONAL GROUP, Sweden
14. THE JAMES HUTTON INSTITUTE, United Kingdom

15. NATIONAL AGRICULTURAL ADVISORY SERVICE, Bulgaria
16. PROAGRIA ETELA-POHJANMAA RY, Finland
17. Provincie Zuid-Holland Netherlands
18. REGIONE TOSCANA, Italy
19. SEINAJOEN AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY, Finland
20. TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY, Ireland
21. INSTITUTO NAVARRO DE TECNOLOGIAS E INFRAESTRUCTURAS AGROALIMENTARIAS SA, Spain
22. STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH, Netherlands
23. OKO OBSTBAU NORDDEUTSCHLAND VERSUCHS- UND BERATUNGSRING (E.V.) Germany
24. COMITE EUROPEEN DES GROUPEMENTS DE CONSTRUCTEURS DU MACHINISME AGRICOLE, Belgium
25. EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUUT VOOR LANDBOUW- EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK, Belgium
26. INAGRO, PROVINCIAAL EXTERN VERZELFSTANDIGD AGENTSCHAP IN PRIVAATRECHTELIJKE VORM VZW, Belgium
27. AUTONOOM PROVINCIEBEDRIJF HOOIBEEKHOEVE, Belgium
28. GEMEENTE WESTLAND, Netherlands
29. BIOLAND BERATUNG GMBH, Germany
30. DEMETER EV, Germany
31. NATURLAND - VERBAND FUR OKOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU EV, Germany
32. INSTITUTO SUPERIOR DE AGRONOMIA, Portugal.

Main objective

Building on the inventory of demonstration activities undertaken by PLAID and AGRIDEMO-F2F and on the work of running thematic networks, NEFERTITI will establish ten thematic networks of demonstration farms bringing together 45 regional clusters of demonstration farmers and other related actors in 17 countries. It will seek to boost innovation uptake and to improve peer-to-peer learning and connectivity across Europe.

Websites

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/772705>

<https://nefertiti-h2020.eu/>

Publications

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/772705/results>

There are 5 conference proceedings.

Results and recommendation

The project structured a Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) approach that serves two general functions: to increase the capacity for 'self-assessment' in the hubs and networks, and, to report on the activities, what is learned in the hubs, networks and the wider AKIS. Policy makers were approached (through ERIAFF and S3 Thematic Platforms) to become a member of the NEFERTITI network by signing a membership declaration. There were no further recommendations.

SHERPA

Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces